

ILM-FAN MUAMMOLARI TADQIQOTCHILAR TALQINIDA

KITOB

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Ushbu ilmiy konferensiya “Ilm-fan va ilmiy faoliyat to‘g‘risida” O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Qonuni, O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining ilm-fan va ta’lim sohasini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan tegishli qarorlarida ko‘zda tutilgan vazifalar ijrosini ta’minlash, talabalar, magistrantlar, doktorantlar va yosh olimlarning ilmiy tadqiqot natijalarini keng yoritish maqsadida “Talqin va tadqiqotlar” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali tahririyati (O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikasiyalarni rivojlantirish agentligining 1540-sonli Guvohnoma, ISSN 2181-3035, talqinvatadqiqotlar.uz veb-sayti) tomonidan tashkil etib boriladi.

“Ilm-fan muammolari tadqiqotchilar talqinida” mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy konferensiyasi

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KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVDA UCH CHIZIQLI HIMOYA MODELINI QO‘LLASH VA UNDA ICHKI AUDITNING ROLI

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Annotasiya: Mazkur tezisda tashkilotlarda samarali boshqaruvni ta’minlash, risklarni aniqlash va ularni minimallashtirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo‘lgan “Uch chiziqli himoya” modelining nazariy asoslari hamda amaliy ahamiyati tahlil qilingan. Unda modelning asosiy tarkibiy qismlari – operatsion boshqaruv, risklarni boshqarish va muvofiqlik tizimi hamda ichki audit funksiyalarining o‘zaro bog‘liqligi yoritilgan. Shuningdek, ichki auditning ushbu model doirasida mustaqil nazorat va baholashni amalga oshirish orqali tashkilot faoliyatining samaradorligini oshirish, risklarni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish va korporativ boshqaruv sifatini mustahkamlashdagi roli ilmiy asosda ko‘rsatib berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: ichki audit, ichki nazorat, uch chiziqli himoya modeli, korporativ boshqaruv, risk, manfaatdor tomonlar.

Tashkilotni oqilona boshqarishda boshqaruv tomonidan qabul qilinadigan qarorlarning operativ samaradorligi muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Chunki qabul qilinuvchi qarorlar tashkilot biznes qiymatining oshishiga va aksincha pasayishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Shu sababli, boshqaruv qarorlarini tashkilot risklarini kompleks o‘rganib, tahlil qilgan holda qabul qilish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Xalqaro amaliyotda keng qo‘llanilib keluvchi “Uch chiziqli himoya” modeli tashkilot maqsadlariga erishish, risklarni minimallashtirish va nazoratni yaxshilashga yordam

beruvchi yondashuv bo‘lib, uning mohiyati shundan iboratki, har bir tashkilotda risklarni boshqarish va nazorat qilishning samarali tizimini tashkil qilishda yuqori boshqaruv va direktorlar Kengashiga bo‘ysunuvchi uchta alohida guruh (yoki himoya chiziqlari) zarur bo‘ladi va korxonaga maqsadlariga erishishda har bir chiziq faoliyati muhim bo‘lib hisoblanadi.

“Uch chizikli himoya modeli vazifalar taqsimotiga aniqlik kiritish orqali risklarni nazorat qilish va boshqarish tizimi mohiyatini yaxshiroq tushunish imkoniyatini beradi. Modelni takshil qilishdan asosiy maqsad risklarni nazorat qilish va boshqarish tizimini samarali tashkil qilish uchun har bir tashkilotda Direktorlar Kengashi va yuqori boshqaruv rahbarligi va nazorati ostida ishlaydigan uchta alohida guruh (himoya chiziqlari) zarur.. “Har bir tashkilot zarur funksiyalarni bajarishda majburiyatlarning takrorlanishini oldini olish maqsadida boshqaruv, risklarni aniqlash va nazorat qilish bo‘yicha vazifalarni aniq belgilab olishi talab etiladi. “Uch chizikli himoya” modeli barcha funksiyalarni va majburiyatlarni aniq belgilash orqali risklarni aniqlash va nazorat qilish masalalari bo‘yicha aloqalarni yaxshilashning samarali metodi sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi. Ushbu model tashkilotda nazoratni tashkil qilish va risklarni boshqarish bo‘yicha majburiyatlarni to‘g‘ri taqsimlashga yordam beradi. Modelning asosiy mazmun-mohiyati shundaki, nazorat va risklarni samarali boshqarish uchun uchta alohida himoya chiziqlari faoliyati zarur:

- 1) nazorat va risk egalari (operasion bo‘limlar boshqaruvi);
- 2) boshqaruvga risklar monitoringida yordam (riskg‘menejment funksiyalari va komplaens)
- 3) Kuzatuv Kengashiga va yuqori boshqaruvga nazorat va risk-menejmentning samaradorligi to‘g‘risida mustaqil kafolatlar etkazib beruvchilar”.

“Uch chizikli himoya modeli risklarni boshqarish tizimidagi barcha ishtirokchilarning roli va javobgarligini aniqlashda muvozanatli yondashuvni taklif etadi”.

Uch chizikli himoya modeli nazorat tizimi sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi va bunda ichki auditning o‘rni beqiyosdir. Chunki uch chizikli himoya modelida ichki audit rahbariyat va menejerlar faoliyatini baholash bilan bir qatorda, kuzatuv kengashiga

hisobot berish kabi vazifalarni bajaradi. Uch chiziqli himoya modeli quyidagi afzalliklarga ega:

1. Xatoliklar va firibgarlik holatlaridan himoya qilish. Uch chiziqli himoya ma'lumotni uchta mustaqil ma'lumot manbalarini o'zaro taqqoslashni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu xatolar, tushunmovchiliklar va hatto firibgarlikka urinishlarni aniqlash imkonini beradi, chunki bu manbalar orasidagi nomuvofiqliklar yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan sabablar haqida ma'lumot olishga yordam beradi.

2. Moliyaviy hisobotning ishonchliligi. Uch chiziqli himoyaga ega ichki audit tizimi moliyaviy hisobot ishonchliligini oshirishga o'z hissasini qo'shadi. Turli manbalardan olingan ma'lumotlarni taqqoslash orqali xatolarni aniqlash va tuzatish imkoniyati moliyaviy axborotning aniq va to'g'ri shakllantirilishiga yordam beradi.

3. Normativ hujjatlarga muvofiqlik. Uch chiziqli himoya modelidan foydalangan holda nazorat va boshqaruvni tashkil qilish, moliyaviy hisobotlarning ishonchliligi va to'g'riligini ta'minlash uchun har bir himoya chizig'ida normativ hujjatlarga muvofiqlikni aniqlash va bu bo'yicha risklarni aniqlashni talab qiladi. Bu aksiyadorlik jamiyatlariga normativ- huquqiy hujjatlar talablariga rioya qilishga yordam beradi.

4. Risklarni boshqarish. Uch chiziqli himoya biznes-jarayonlar va tizimlardagi potensial risk hamda kamchiliklarni aniqlashga yordam beradi. Bu tashkilotlarga yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan salbiy oqibatlarni minimallashtirish uchun risklarni boshqarish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlarni ishlab chiqish va amalda qo'llash imkonini beradi.

5. Manfaatdor tomonlar ishonchi. Uch chiziqli himoya modelidan foydalanish aksiyadorlik jamiyatining investorlar, banklar va boshqa manfaatdor tomonlar bilan hamkorlikni mustahkamlaydi. Bu tashkilot obro'sini oshirishga yordam beradi. Ushbu modelni har bir tashkilot strategiyasi, faoliyati, hajmidan kelib chiqib, moslashtirgan holda tashkil qilish imkoniyati uning ahamiyatini yanada oshiradi. Ya'ni ushbu modelga universal, yagona yondashuv mavjud emas va uni har bir tashkilot o'ziga moslashtirishgan holda qo'llashi mumkin. Yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tganimizdek, uch chiziqli himoya modelini qo'llovchi ichki audit tizimi tashkilot

biznes jarayonlari samaradorligi va xavfsizligini ta'minlashga kompleks yondashuvni ifodalaydi. Uch chizikli himoya modeli uchta darajadan iborat bo'ladi

Birinchi himoya chizig'i: Ushbu daraja yuqori boshqaruv organi a'zolarining amallarini o'z ichiga oladi. Ya'ni yuqori boshqaruv organi faoliyati tashkilotda ichki nazorat tizimini ishlab chiqish va risklarni boshqarish siyosatini ishlab chiqishga javobgarligida namoyon bo'ladi. Ushbu birinchi himoya chizig'idagi samarali ichki audit tizimi vazifalari biznes bo'linmalar amallari va jarayonlarining kompaniya siyosati va standartlariga mosligi hamda samaradorligini baholashdan iborat bo'ladi. Ushbu jarayonda risklarni minimallashtirish uchun quyidagilar tavsiya etiladi: birinchi himoya chizig'idagi jarayonlar va amallarni muntazam auditorlik tekshiruvidan o'tkazish; xodimlarning siyosat va risklarni boshqarish bo'yicha ta'lim olishini ta'minlash; nazorat chora-tadbirlarini ishlab chiqish va amalga oshirish, jarayonlarning bajarilishini monitoring qilish va hisobot berish; muammoli holatlar aniqlangan taqdirda jarayonlarni takomillashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish. Ushbu darajada yuqori boshqaruv organi ichki nazorat tizimini va risklarni boshqarish siyosatini yuritish bo'yicha mas'uliyatni manfaatdor tomonlar oldida o'z zimmasiga oladi va: manfaatdor tomonlarning manfaatlarini kuzatish uchun ular bilan hamkorlik qiladi va maqsadlarga erishish haqida shaffof muloqot o'ranatadi; axloqiy xulq-atvor va mas'uliyatni rag'batlantiradigan madaniyatni rivojlantiradi; korporativ boshqaruv tuzilmalari va jarayonlarini o'rnatadi, shu jumladan zarur bo'lganda qo'llab-quvvatlovchi qo'mitalar tashkil qiladi; maqsadlarga erishish uchun rahbariyatni resurslar bilan ta'minlaydi; tashkilotda risklarni boshqarishni nazorat qiladi; samarali ichki nazorat tizimini tashkil qilish bo'yicha javobgar bo'ladi. huquqiy me'yorlarga rioya etilishi ustidan nazoratni ta'minlaydi.

Ikkinchi himoya chizig'i: Ikkinchi darajada risklarni boshqarish bilan bog'liq menejerlar o'rin egallaydi. Ushbu darajada ichki audit vazifalari sifatida risklarni boshqarish tizimi va standartlarga muvofiqligini baholash namoyon bo'ladi. Ushbu darajada risklarni minimallashtirish uchun quyidagilar tavsiya etiladi: risklarni boshqarish tizimini monitoring qilish va uning samaradorligini baholash; xavfsizlik choralari samaradorligini ta'minlash uchun boshqa nazorat funksiyalari bilan

hamkorlik qilish; risklarni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish bo‘yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish. Bunda menejment: yuqori boshqaruvga risklarni boshqarish bo‘yicha nazorat vositalari va amallarini ishlab chiqishda yordam beradi; siyosat va jarayonlarni amaliyotda qo‘llash bo‘yicha tavsiyalar va yo‘nalishlarni ishlab chiqadi; ichki nazorat va risklarni boshqarish tizimi samaradorligini tekshiradi; ichki nazorat va risklar bo‘yicha yuqori boshqaruv organiga hisobot taqdim etadi; risklarga ta'sir qiluvchi hodisalar monitoringini olib boradi va boshqalar. Uchinchi himoya chizig‘i:

uchinchi himoya chizig‘ida ichki audit xizmati turadi va u korporativ boshqaruv, ichki nazorat va risklarni boshqarishni mustaqil baholash hamda bu bo‘yicha taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish funksiyasini bajaradi. Uchinchi himoya chizig‘ida samarali ichki audit tizimini tashkil qilishda quyidagi jihatlarga e'tibor qaratilishi lozim: ichki auditorlik tekshiruvlarini tashkilot siyosatiga va tartib qoidalariga mos tarzda rejalashtirish va o‘tkazish; risklarni boshqarish tizimi samaradorligini baholash; biznes-jarayonlar bilan bog‘liq risklarni monitoring qilish va ularni yaxshilash bo‘yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish, bu borada birinchi va ikkinchi chiziqlar bilan qayta aloqa o‘rnatish; tashkilotda birinchi va ikkinchi himoya chiziqlarini o‘z ichiga olgan holda ichki nazorat tizimi ishonchliligi va samaradorligini baholash; tashkilotda normativ hujjatlar, standartlar va siyosat talablariga rioya etilishini tekshirish. Ichki nazorat tizimidagi kamchiliklarni aniqlash, ularni tahlil qilish va takomillashtirish bo‘yicha taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish. Ushbu darajada risklarni minimallashtirish uchun quyidagilar tavsiya etiladi: birinchi va ikkinchi himoya chiziqlarida muvofiqlik va samaradorlikni tekshiruvchi mustaqil auditorlik tekshiruvlarini o‘tkazish; risklarni nazorat qilish va to‘g‘ri baholash uchun ichki hamda tashqi auditorlar bilan o‘zaro hamkorlikni o‘rnatish; boshqaruvga aniqlangan muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish bo‘yicha tavsiyalarni o‘z vaqtida taqdim etish; ichki auditorlar tomonidan tashkilot risklariga ta'sir qilishi mumkin bo‘lgan qonunchilikdagi o‘zgarishlarni o‘rganish.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, uch chizikli himoya modeli tashkilot maqsadlariga erishishda ichki auditning samaradorligini ta'minlash, shuningdek, turli manfaatdor tomonlarning ishonchini saqlashda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Tashkilot risklarni

minimallashtirish maqsadida ushbu modelni asos qilib olishi va risklarni boshqarish tizimining barcha ishtirokchilari o'rtasida javobgarlik va o'zaro munosabatlarni belgilash va amalga oshirish uchun maxsus ko'rsatmalar ishlab chiqishda foydalanishi mumkin. Ya'ni ushbu modelning smaaradorligi, uning tashkilot maqsadlariga moslashtirilganligi bilan belgilanadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Модел трех линий ива. Обновление модели трех линий защиты. © 2020 Институт Внутренних Аудиторов, Инс. [хттпс://www.txeiia.org/глобалас/сетс/документс/ресурсес/](http://www.txeiia.org/глобалас/сетс/документс/ресурсес/)
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INDIGOFERA O'SIMLIGI TARKIBIDAN AJRATIB OLINGAN INDIGONING METALL IONLARI BILAN TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada Sirdaryo viloyati sharoitida o'zida indigo saqlagan “Indigofera tinctoria L” va “Isatus tinctoria L” o'simliklarini yetishtirish va ushbu o'simliklar tarkibidan ajratib olingan indigoning fizik- kimyoviy xossalari tadqiqi yoritilgan. Shu bilan birga indigoning metall kompleksi hosil bo'lishi uchun tanlangan optimal sharoit va konsentratsiyalari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: indigo, polifunksional moddalar, “Indigofera tinctoria L”, “Isatus tinctoria L”, metall komplekslari, ko'prik ligandlar

Yurtimiz tabiati juda boy va xilma-xil, ayniqsa iqlim sharoiti dorivor o'simliklar va tarkibida bo'yoq moddalari saqlagan o'simliklarni etishtirish uchun juda qulay bo'lib, bunday o'simliklarni qayta ishlashning samarali texnologiyalarini ishlab chiqish dolzarb hisoblanadi. Hozirgi kunda tabiiy manbalardan olinayotgan polifunksional moddalardan biri bo'lgan indigo shular jumlasidandir. Bir necha yillardan beri mamlakatimizda ham ushbu moddaniy o'simliklar tarkibidan ajratib olish bo'yicha bir qancha tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda. Uni tabiiy manbalardan ajratib olinib, turli xil shakldagi birikmalari to'qimachilik sanoati uchun bo'yoq moddasi sifatida, farmasevtika sohasida dori vositalari tayyorlashda va boshqa sohalarda foydalanish imkoniyati yaratilmoqda [1].

Bizning tadqiqotlarimizda ham xuddi shunday tadqiqotlarning davomi sifatida Sirdaryo viloyati sharoitida o'zida indigo saqlagan “Indigofera tinctoria L” va “Isatus tinctoria L” o'simliklarini yetishtirish va ushbu o'simliklar tarkibidan ajratib olingan indigoning fizik- kimyoviy xossalari taqqoslab o'rganildi. Ajratib olingan

moddalarning tuzilishi spektral usullarda tadqiq qilindi. “Indigofera tinctoria L” o’simligidan ajratib olingan indigoning IQ-spektroskopik tahlil natijasi bo’yicha, molekula tarkibi spektr signallarida 3200-3600 nm masofa oralig’idagi (3428,25 nm da chuqur yutilish mavjud) yutilish modda tarkibida –imino(-NH) guruh borligidan darak beradi. Modda tarkibidagi C=O guruhi 1628,3 nm da yutilish namoyon qilgan. 2800-3000 nm masofa oralig’idagi (2926 va 2851.54 nm da) 2 ta kichik yutilish modda tarkibida aromatik birikma va C=C guruh mavjudligini ko’rsatadi [2].

1-rasm.“Indigofera tinctoria L” o’simligidan ajratib olingan indigoning IQ-spektri.

Ushbu natijalar “Isatis tinctoria L” o’simligi tarkibidan olingan natijalarga to’liq mos ekanligi tasdiqlandi. Adabiyotlarda qayd etilishicha Indigo diiminlarining metall ionlari bilan ligandlar sifatida bir qator komplekslari olinganligi haqida ma’lumotlar berilgan. Ma’lum qilinishicha, ularning xossalari indigo bilan mos keladi va indigoning anilin, $TiCl_4$, shuningdek, 1,4-diazobitsiklo (2,2,2) oktan (DABCO) bilan reaksiyaga kirishishi natijasida indigo bis(ariliminlar)ni ko’prik ligandlarining yangi sinfi sifatida sintez qilingan. Ularning tuzilishi IQ –spektral usulida tadqiq qilinganda 750 nm to’lqin uzunligida intensiv yutilishni namoyon qilishi ta’kidlangan. Shuningdek, hosil bo’lgan komplekslarning taxminiy tuzilishi keltirilgan [3]:

Bizning tajribalarimiz ushbu o'simlikning tarkibidagi moviy indigoning kimyoviy reaksiyalar jarayonida indikatorlik va og'ir metall ionlariga nisbatan reagentlik xususiyatlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan.

Tadqiqotlarimizning davomi sifatida toza indigoning metall ionlari bilan ta'sirini o'rganish va uning metall komplekslarini eritmada olindi. Dastlab indigoning metall kompleksi hosil bo'lishi uchun optimal sharoit tanlandi, buning uchun eritma muhiti, indigo va metall tuzi eritmasining optimal konsentratsiyalari aniqlandi. Indigoning tabiiy manbalardan ajratib olish usulari asosan “Indigofera tinctoria L” va “Isatis tinctoria” o'simliklari tarkibidan ajratib olish yo'lga qo'yildi.

Har ikkala tabiiy manbada ham tadqiqot ishlari o'xshash usullarda olib borildi. Yupqa qatlamdagi xromatografik tahlil ham bir xil erituvchilar aralashmasi yordamida olib borildi. Ajratib olingan mahsulotlarning tuzilishi va xossalari fizik-kimyoviy jihatdan qiyosiy tahlil qilindi.

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WONDERS OF "HAYRAT UL-ABROR" ("WONDERS OF THE GOOD")

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Abstract: This article provides a detailed explanation of the artistry and educational significance of Hazrat Alisher Navoi's work "Hayrat ul-abror" ("Wonders of the Good"). In particular, the 18th chapter regarding gratitude is considered relevant even for the present day. The chapter about the Golden Old Woman is a story that demonstrates the justice of the king. The chapter of advice to Badiuzzamon is an instruction intended for every one of today's youth.

Keywords: sage (arif), gratitude, 63 chapters, 20 discourses (maqolat), Badiuzzamon, Husayn Boyqaro, Golden Old Woman.

Our great ancestor Hazrat Mir Alisher Navoi left us a very rich heritage, among which the work "Xamsa" ("Quinary") holds a significant place. This is because Navoi created his work in the Turkic language, unlike the great khamsanavis (writers of Khamsa) Nizami Ganjavi, Khusraw Dehlavi, and Abdurakhman Jami. This was an act of courage. After all, at that time, the language of creativity was Persian. Our grandfather, through his works, was able to demonstrate the elegance, grace, and charm of the Turkic language in its full stature. As is known, there were specific laws, rules, and certain criteria for writing a "Xamsa." According to them, the first poem of the work had to be written in a philosophical-didactic spirit. Hazrat Navoi, following this tradition like his masters, wrote the first poem in the "Xamsa" in a philosophical-ethical spirit, similar to Ganjavi's "Makhzan ul-asror," Dehlavi's "Matla ul-anvor," and Jami's "Tuhfat ul-ahror," and titled it "Hayrat ul-abror" ("Wonders of the Good"). Its meaning is "The Amazement of Pious People." The work consists of 7,976 lines, comprising 64 chapters and 20 discourses (maqolat). Of these, 21 chapters are the introduction, 40 chapters consist of 20 discourses and 20 stories and

fables, and the final 3 chapters are the conclusion of the work. "Hayrat ul-abror" ("Wonders of the Good") was written in 1483 in the sari' meter of aruz and begins with the traditional introduction — praise (hamd) and glorification (na't). Following that, reflections are shared regarding the description of the masters (Nizami and Dehlavi) and the meanings of words. Then come the dedications to Husayn Bayqaro and his great spiritual leaders Bahauddin Naqshband and Khoja Akhrar. The discourses begin from the 22nd chapter. Each discourse pertains to a specific topic, and stories are provided in proportion to them. In particular, the first discourse is about faith (imon), stating that faith is the primary condition for a human to enter this world as a human being and that it consists of six parts. Following this, a story about Sheikh Bayazid is presented. The story tells of the great Sufi sheikh's concern about departing with faith when transitioning from the transient world to the eternal world. If we think about it, if such a great person is concerned about departing with faith, we too should look at our current state. The second discourse is about Islam, covering the word of testimony (shahadat), prayer, alms, fasting, pilgrimage, and other obligatory acts, and how Islam is the only religion of salvation. The famous story of Ibrahim Adham is presented in proportion to it. The third chapter is about salotin, i.e., sultans, containing exemplary thoughts on how God showed favor and placed them at the high peak of the sultanate. That is, addressing the kings, it says: you too were created from soil like your people, you are not pure light; perhaps there is someone better than you among those people in terms of good deeds and piety. In proportion to this discourse, the story of "Shoh G'oziy and the Golden Old Woman" is given. Everyone thinks differently about Shoh G'oziy in this story. In the 17th discourse, while describing Khorasan, the poet refers to Husayn Bayqaro as Khusravi G'oziy. For this reason, some say Shoh G'oziy is Husayn Bayqaro, while others say he is a different king. Subsequent discourses offer reflections on topics such as hypocrisy, those who wear the dervish cloak (khirqapo'sh), generosity, nobility, magnanimity, manners, contentment, loyalty, the fire of love, truthfulness, science and scholars, the pen and the people of the pen, chivalry, the life of the heavens, the wine of ignorance, boastful people, the youth of spring, the house of sorrow of the heavens, the description of

Khorasan, and advice to Sultan Badiuzzamon. Some of them are provided with one story, the last discourse with two, and some are not given a story. Specifically, no story is attached to a total of four discourses: the 15th discourse — on the wine of ignorance, the 16th discourse — on boastful people, the 17th discourse — on the youth of spring, and the 19th discourse — on the description of Khorasan.

As mentioned above, "Hayrat ul-abror" ("Wonders of the Good") was written in a philosophical-ethical spirit; the soul of a person who reads it finds rest, and their heart is purified. Nowadays, many people have a dominant feeling of being left behind by the times and other people. In modern scientific language, this is called FOMO. People are unable to feel the happiness of living in the moment. Most saddeningly, their grief is not for the hereafter, but for the world. The 18th discourse of this work is about the house of sorrow of the heavens, stating that the world is a prison for wise people, and one who is fascinated by it is a fool. Everyone will pass from the world one day; therefore, how tragic it is to grieve because of death, to die before death, and to mourn for one's own state. In doing so, a person torments their own soul and lives in agony in the world, making one grief into two. After all, if the garden of this world is faithless and the flowers of life within it are transient. Now, in a garden that has not been faithful to its own flowers, is it appropriate for a rose to be faithful to it and provide rest?! If the garden is a world, the people coming and going within it are guests. They are like the flowers in the garden. Since the reason for our coming and going to this world is unknown, what is the reason for our grieving so much and suffering for futile things?! Instead, we must value every breath we take and offer praises and thanks to the One who gave such a great blessing. Whenever we find a moment or a reason to be happy, we should seize it as an opportunity. For every breath of ours is a jewel. Without it, the people would not be alive; it is life-giving like the water of life, aqdas, that is, the most sacred blessing. Allah first of all gave us this life-giving breath, created us as the highest creation in nature, and created us as Muslims on the path of religion, making many wonders of the world ready and available for man. All these infinite blessings were on one side, and the jewel called intellect was on the other:

Barcha jahondin qilib ashraf seni,

Ayladi rozig'a musharraf seni.

(Having made you the most noble of all the world, / He honored you with His secret [or made you honored by His pleasure].)

Indeed, Allah did not create us as plants or animals, but created us superior to all things in the world and granted us the happiness of His rozi, that is, the opportunity to prostrate before Him. We cannot fulfill the gratitude for these even if we sacrifice our lives. Therefore, without wasting our precious breath in this world, we should do good and show generosity; instead of being troubled by the grief of this futile world, we should engage in sweet conversations with true friends.

Har kishikim, bor esa yore anga,

Har kishikim, yor esa bore anga.

(Whosoever has a beloved [friend], Whosoever has a beloved, has everything.)

If someone in this world has a yor, that is, a confidant, a soulmate, or a friend, then everything they have is that beloved. Because a true friend is an inexhaustible treasure in this world. Here, yor may also refer to Allah, and it may speak of true divine love. For whichever servant is with Allah, and if He is their beloved, that itself is sufficient for them. At the end of the discourse, it is emphasized that if a person wants to reach their goals and for this to be continuous, they must give much thanks to the Creator. After all, there is a promise from our Lord: "Give thanks, and I shall increase [your blessings]."

After this discourse, a story about the Beauty of China is given. In this story, the Beauty of China is described so beautifully that even painters are powerless to draw her image. Because of her amorous glances (gamza), China was under threat, and from her braided hair, danger reached religion; she is depicted as a hangman and a murderess. Naturally, people who saw her could not breathe without her thereafter. Therefore, the Khan appointed special people so that no one should come near her. She would play go'y and chavgon (polo) in the field. If someone said a word about her, they would perish. A young man had been in love with this girl for a long time, and one day he accidentally encountered her on the road; the body of the lover and

the stranger could not endure this, and he too took his place among the guilty, and by the King's command, he was placed against the city wall and plastered with mud. Even in this state, he was giving thanks to Allah: "This breath of my life is departing, and the grief for the beloved is making it easy." That is, the lover was giving thanks because he had seen his beloved and was passing from the world in a state of being in love with her. Even though he stood before so much suffering, he did not give up his love and did not complain about his condition. Seeing this, the Khan was also affected by the fire of love and released him, sending him toward his beloved. The young man, who gave thanks amidst the calamity of love, ultimately attains the sight of his heart's desire and reaches his goal. It is clear from this story that a person should be grateful for any situation they are in; then Allah will increase their deeds and grant them success in the valley of goals. If the opposite occurs, they will be caught in the disaster of ingratitude. This theme is relevant and eternal not only for the time of our grandfather Navoi but for all of humanity.

As mentioned above, the final discourse is titled "Advice to Badiuzzamon Mirza," the eldest son of Husayn Bayqaro, and includes two stories: one about a righteous son named Khoja Abu Nasr, and the second about a just and wise king and his slave. From this, it is evident that Navoi wanted Prince Badiuzzamon to be a worthy son to his father and a just king to his people. In this discourse, a child who is the successor of a family is compared to a mine and, in terms of amber-like quality, to a sea. Then, the king is compared to a mine and the prince to a pearl:

Bilki erur moyayi amn-u amon,

Xisravi Jamqadr Badiuzzamon.

Ulki vale gavhari yaktodurur,

Barchasidin poyada a'lodurur.

(Know that he is the substance of peace and safety, / The Jamshid-statured King Badiuzzamon. / He who is a unique pearl, / Is higher than all of them in rank.)

He describes Badiuzzamon Mirza as a being created in purity and gentleness, a mercy from the Truth (God) to the people of the world. After that, he says, "The King commanded that my word is esteemed before him, and to speak the beautiful

thoughts that come to your heart," and thus offers the following advice to him. First of all, he states that life is unfaithful, wealth is transient and fleeting, and that Allah Almighty is the One who gives and takes everything. He notes that a beggar who walks with the remembrance of the Truth is superior even to kings. He explains through the allusions (talmeh) of Faridun and Zahhak that everyone will receive their share in this world and that one must not be greedy for worldly goods (the treasure Zahhak found with suffering went to Faridun, not himself). After that, he speaks about justice, writing how it can make even a ruined country prosperous. He explains that the word "Adl" (Justice) consists of three letters and interprets their meanings as follows:

ξ(Ayn) — bright like the sun, the killer of oppression.

) ۛDol) — the crown of the state and religion, in the sense of wearing the crown to help the needy.

)Lom] — (implicitly continuing the symbolism of justice and kindness.[

Additionally ,just as they say" do good to those who appreciate it ",justice and generosity should also be shown to those who understand them. He mentions that while one should always do good, politics (authority) is also necessary ,because some illnesses are cured with sugar, and some with poison. Furthermore ,he writes that people should not be promoted to office too quickly, nor should they be demoted for a minor fault. For, if that person has climbed the ranks of office with difficulty, a quick fall will cause pain to their soul.

Kimsani bot aylamagil arjumand,

Ham yana oz ish bila qilma najand.

(Do not make someone esteemed too quickly, / And do not make them wretched for a small matter.)

After this discourse, a story is presented about a pure king who set out for Mecca and his esteemed son, Khoja Abu Nasr. The king and his son reach the Kaaba with a caravan, and the people turn to the king to pray on everyone's behalf. The king, saying that his son is his equal in knowledge and a worthy companion who cared for him on the road, assigns this task to his son. His son prays, saying, "Even though I do

not know the science of wishing, I implore You, O Allah." Following this story, a tale of a slave is told. It is said that at a great banquet, the king's cook accidentally spills hot food on the king's head. Everyone thought the king would kill the servant, and the cook was holding his life in his hands in great embarrassment. But the king frees him; when asked why, he says it is not good to kill someone whom shame has already destroyed. This story celebrates the king's generosity, mercy, and wisdom. After this, Navoi mentions that serving in the presence of a generous king is better than a hundred thousand other doors. Then, he explains the reason for finishing the book and naming it as follows:

Hayrati abror ko‘rib zotini,

"Hayrat ul-abror" dedim otini.

(Seeing that its essence is the amazement of the pious, / I named it "Hayrat ul-abror" ["Wonders of the Good"].)

In conclusion, a person who reads this work is purified both spiritually and mentally. For example, as mentioned above, while reading that one should think about the comfort of the eternal world rather than the house of sorrow of this world, and that we should offer endless thanks for our priceless breath, my heart felt a unique tranquility. Furthermore, the story about Abu Nasr calls a person to be pure-hearted and faithful. Indeed, today many young people and individuals cannot even show enough love and attention to their own parents. They leave them alone when they are sick, or they leave them in nursing homes when they are in need, even though they have their own homes. After all, isn't a kind word more important to a person in their old age than good conditions?! Many people today might also fall into the situation of the cook (slave) in the following story. However, they are not treated like the king treated him. That is, there are cases where people intentionally torment someone further and throw their fault in their face when they are already embarrassed. Such people are called "dilozor" (heart-breakers). Heart-breaking is one of the worst vices. Therefore, it is so important for each of us to read the work "Hayrat ul-abror" ("Wonders of the Good") and to purify our bodies and hearts with its pure lights!

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"HAYRATÜ'L-EBRAR" ÖĞÜTLERİ

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Özet: Bu makalede, Hazret Ali Şîr Nevâî'nin "Hayratü'l-Ebrar" eserinin sanatsal yönü ve eğitici önemi ayrıntılı bir şekilde ele alınmaktadır. Özellikle eserdeki şükürle ilgili 18. bölüm, günümüz için de güncelliğini korumaktadır. "Tilla Kampir" (Altın Yaşlı Kadın) hakkındaki bölüm, hükümdar adaletini gösteren bir hikâyedir. Bedüzzaman'a nasihat bölümü ise günümüz gençlerinin her birine hitap eden bir öğüttür.

Anahtar kelimeler: arif, şükür, 63 bölüm, 20 makale (makalat), Bedüzzaman, Hüseyin Baykara, Tilla Kampir.

Buyuk atamız Hazret Mir Ali Şîr Nevâî, bizlere çok zengin bir miras bırakmış olup, bu miras içerisinde "Hamse" eseri önemli bir yer tutar. Çünkü Nevâî eserini, büyük hamsenüvisler Nizâmî-i Gencevî, Hüsrev-i Dihlevî ve Abdurrahman Câmî'den farklı olarak Türkçede yaratmıştır. Bu bir cesaretti. Zira o dönemde sanat dili Farsçaydı. Dedemiz ise eserleriyle Türk dilinin zarafetini, nezaketini ve cazibesini tüm ihtişamıyla gösterebilmiştir. Malumdur ki, "Hamse" yazmanın kendine has kuralları ve belirli ölçütleri vardı. Buna göre eserin ilk destanı felsefi-didaktik bir ruhla yazılmalıydı. Hazret Nevâî de üstatları gibi bu geleneğe uyararak, "Hamse" kapsamındaki ilk destanını Gencevî'nin "Mahzenü'l-Esrâr", Dihlevî'nin "Matlaü'l-Envâr" ve Câmî'nin "Tuhfetü'l-Ahrâr" eserleri gibi felsefi-ahlaki bir ruhla kaleme aldı ve "Hayratü'l-Ebrar" (İyilerin Hayreti) adını verdi. Eser 7976 mısra olup 64 bölüm ve 20 makaleden ibarettir. Bunların 21 bölümü mukaddime, 40 bölümü 20 makale ile 20 hikâye ve masal, son 3 bölümü ise eserin hatimesidir. "Hayratü'l-Ebrar", 1483 yılında aruzun seri bahrinde yazılmış olup geleneksel mukaddime — hamd ve naat ile başlar. Ardından üstatların (Nizâmî ve Dihlevî) tavsifi ve sözün

manaları üzerine fikir yürütülür. Sonrasında Hüseyin Baykara’ya, büyük pirleri Bahâeddin Nakşibend ve Hoca Ahrar’a ithaf bölümleri gelir. 22. bölümden itibaren makaleler başlar. Her bir makale belirli bir konuya ait olup bunlara uygun hikâyeler de verilmiştir. Özellikle birinci makale iman hakkındadır ve insanın bu dünyaya insan olarak gelmesinin temel şartının iman olduğu, bunun da altı kısımdan oluştuğu belirtilir. Ardından Şeyh Bayezid hakkında bir hikâye anlatılır. Hikâyede, büyük mutasavvıf şeyhin fani dünyadan baki dünyaya göç ederken imanla gitme konusundaki kaygısı dile getirilir. Düşündüğümüzde, böylesine büyük bir zat imanla gitme endişesi taşıyorsa, bizlerin de mevcut halimize bir bakmamız gerektiği anlaşılır. İkinci makale İslam hakkındadır; burada kelime-i şهادet, namaz, zekât, oruç ve hac gibi farz ibadetler ile İslam’ın yegâne kurtuluş dini olduğu vurgulanır. Buna uygun olarak meşhur İbrahim Ethem hikâyesi anlatılır. Üçüncü bölüm ise salatin, yani sultanlar hakkındadır; burada Tanrı'nın lütfederek saltanatın en yüksek zirvesine çıkardığı hükümdarlar hakkında ibretlik fikirler mevcuttur. Yani padişahlara hitaben: "Sen de halkın gibi topraktan yaratıldın, saf nur değilsin; belki iyi ameller ve takva bakımından o halkın içinden senden daha iyisi vardır," denilir. Bu makaleye uygun olarak "Şah Gazi ve Altın Yaşlı Kadın" hikâyesi verilmiştir. Bu hikâyedeki Şah Gazi hakkında herkes farklı düşünür. 17. makalede şair Horasan’ı tarif ederken "Hüsrev-i Gazi" diyerek Hüseyin Baykara’yı kasteder. Bu yüzden bazıları Şah Gazi’nin Hüseyin Baykara, bazıları ise başka bir şah olduğunu söylerler. Sonraki makalelerde riya, dervişler, kerem, alicenaplık, cömertlik, edep, kanaat, vefa, aşk ateşi, doğruluk, ilim ve alimler, kalem ve kalem ehli, yiğitlik, felek hayatı, cehalet şarabı, övünge kişiler, bahar gençliği, felek gamhanesi, Horasan beyanı ve Sultan Bedüzzaman’a nasihat gibi konularda mütalaalar yürütülmüştür. Bunların bazılarına birer hikâye, son makaleye iki hikâye verilmiş; bazılarına ise hikâye eklenmemiştir. Özellikle 15. makale (cehalet şarabı), 16. makale (övünge kişiler), 17. makale (bahar gençliği) ve 19. makale (Horasan beyanı) olmak üzere toplam dört makaleye hikâye eklenmemiştir.

Yukarıda vurgulandığı gibi, "Hayratü'l-Ebrar" felsefi-ahlaki bir ruhla yazılmış olup onu okuyan insanın ruhu huzur bulur, kalbi temizlenir. Günümüzde pek çok

insanda kendini zamandan ve diğer insanlardan geri kalmış gibi hissetme duygusu hakimdir. Bu, modern bilim diliyle FOMO’dur. İnsanlar anı yaşama mutluluğunu hissedemiyorlar. En acıklısı ise dertlerinin ahiret değil, dünya olmasıdır. Bu eserin 18. bölümü felek gamhanesi hakkındadır; orada akıllı kişiler için dünyanın bir zindan olduğu, ona büyülenen kişinin ise cahilliği üzerine söz edilir. Dünyadan herkes bir gün gelip geçecektir; hal böyleyken, ölüm sebebiyle yas tutup ölmeden önce ölmek, kendi haline matem tutmak ne kadar hazindir. Bunda insan canına eziyet eder; dünyada azap içinde yaşarken bir derdini iki eder. Oysa bu dünya bahçesi vefasız, içindeki ömür gülleri ise kalıcı değilse, kendi güllerine vefa göstermeyen bir bahçede gülün ona vefa göstermesi ve huzur vermesi mümkün müdür?! Bahçe bir dünya ise içindeki gelip geçici insanlar birer misafirdir; adeta bahçedeki güller gibidirler. Bu dünyaya geliş ve gidiş sebepimiz belirsizken, bu kadar dertlenmemizin ve beyhude şeyler için acı çekmemizin nedeni nedir?! Bunun yerine aldığımız her nefesin kıymetini bilip, bu yüce nimeti veren Zat'a hamd ü senalar etmemiz gerekir. Ne zaman mutlu olmak için bir an veya sebep bulsak, onu fırsat bilip değerlendirmeliyiz. Çünkü her nefesimiz bir cevherdir. Eğer o olmazsa halk diri olmaz; o hayat suyu gibi can verici, mukaddes yani en kutsal nimettir. Allah bize her şeyden önce bu can veren nefesi verdi, doğadaki en yüce varlık olarak yarattı, din yolunda Müslüman kıldı ve pek çok alem mucizesini insan için hazır etti. Bu sonsuz nimetler bir yana, akıl denilen cevher bir yana oldu:

Barcha jahondin qilib ashraf seni,

Ayladi rozig'a musharraf seni.

(Seni tüm cihandan daha şerefli kılıp, Kendi sırrına/rızasına müşerref eyledi.)

Gerçekten de Allah bizi bitki veya hayvan olarak değil, dünyadaki her şeyden yüce yarattı ve Kendi rızasına, yani O'na secde etme mutluluğuna erıştirdi. Bunların şükürünü canımızı feda etsek de eda edemeyiz. Öyleyse bu dünyada aziz nefesimizi hor görmeden iyilik ve cömertlik yapmalı; bu beyhude dünyanın derdiyle kederlenmeyip gerçek dostlarla tatlı sohbetler kurmalıyız.

Har kishikim, bor esa yore anga,

Har kishikim, yor esa bore anga.

(Kimin ki bir yâri/dostu varsa, yâri olanın her şeyi vardır.)

Eğer bu dünyada birinin yâri, yani sırdaşı ve dostu varsa, onun için her şey o yâridir. Çünkü gerçek dost, bu dünyadaki tükenmez hazinedir. Burada yâr derken Allah da kastedilmiş olabilir, gerçek aşk üzerine söz edilmiş de olabilir. Çünkü hangi kul Allah ile beraberse ve yâri O ise, bu ona kafidir. Makalenin sonunda insanın amaçlarına ulaşması ve bunun kalıcı olmasını istiyorsa Yaratan'a çok şükretmesi gerektiği vurgulanmıştır. Zira Rabbimizin "Şükrederseniz artırırım" vaadi vardır.

Bu makaleden sonra Çin Güzeli hakkında bir hikâye verilmiştir. Bu hikâyede Çin Güzeli öyle güzel tasvir edilmiştir ki, onun resmini çizmeye ressamalar bile aciz kalır. Onun gamzesi yüzünden Çin tehlike altına girmiş, örgülü saçından dine zarar gelmiş gibi cellat ve katil tarzında betimlenmiştir. Onu gören insanlar doğal olarak onsuz nefes alamaz hale gelirdi. Bu yüzden hakan, kimse ona yaklaşmasın diye özel görevliler belirlemiştir. O ise meydanda top ve çevgan oynardı. Kim onun hakkında bir söz söylese helak olurdu. Bu kıza uzun zamandır bir genç aşık ve bir gün onu yolda tesadüfen görür; aşık ve garip bedeni buna dayanamayıp o da suçlular safına girer ve şahın emriyle şehir duvarına konulup üzerine çamur sıvanır. O bu halde bile Allah'a şükretmektedir: "Bu nefesle canım çıkıyor ama yârin derdi bunu kolaylaştırıyor." Yani aşık, yârini gördüğü ve ona aşık halde dünyadan göçtüğü için şükreliyordu. O kadar azap karşısında durmasına rağmen aşkıdan vazgeçmedi, halinden şikayet etmedi. Bunu hakan görünce ona da aşk ateşi tesir eder ve genci serbest bırakıp yârine gönderir. Aşk belasını içinde şükreden genç, sonunda gönlündeki yâre ve amacına ulaşır. Bu hikâyeden anlaşılıyor ki, insan her haline şükretmelidir; o zaman Allah onun amellerini artırır ve onu amaç vadisine ulaştırır. Aksi takdirde nankörlük belasına müptela olur. Bu konu sadece Nevâî dedemizin dönemi için değil, tüm insanlık için güncel ve ölümsüzdür.

Yukarıda belirtildiği üzere, son makale Hüseyin Baykara'nın büyük oğlu Bedüzzaman Mirza'ya nasihat adını taşır ve iki hikâyeye içerir: biri Hoca Ebu Nasr lakaplı salih evlat, diğeri ise adil, akil padişah ve kulu hakkındadır. Buradan anlaşılıyor ki Nevâî, Şehzade Bedüzzaman'ın babasına layık bir evlat ve halkına adil bir şah olmasını istemiştir. Bu makalede ailenin devamı olan evlat madene benzetilir;

anber vasfiyla denize de benzer denilir. Sonra şah madene, şehzade ise mücevhere benzetilir:

Bilki erur moyayi amn-u amon,

Xisravi Jamqadr Badiuzzamon.

Ulki vale gavhari yaktodurur,

Barchasidin poyada a'lodurur.

(Bil ki o emniyet ve huzurun kaynağıdır, Cem kadirli hükümdar Bedüzzaman'dır. O ki biricik bir mücevherdir, makamca hepsinden üstündür.)

Bedüzzaman Mirza'yı saflık ve yumuşaklıkla yaratılmış bir zat, dünya halkına Hakk'ın rahmeti olarak tarif eder. Ardından şahın huzurunda "benim sözüm değerlidir, gönlüne gelen güzel düşünceleri söyle" diye emrettiğini, bu yüzden ona da nasihat edeceğini belirterek şöyle der: Öncelikle ömrün vefasız, devletin geçici olduğunu; her şeyi veren ve alanın Allah Teâlâ olduğunu söyler. Hak anısıyla yaşayan bir yoksulun padişahlardan bile üstün olduğunu kaydeder. Herkesin bu dünyada nasibine düşeni alacağını, mal ve dünyaya hırs göstermemek gerektiğini Feridun ve Dahhak telmihleri vasıtasıyla açıklar (Dahhak'ın azapla topladığı hazine kendisine değil, Feridun'a nasip olur). Sonrasında adalet üzerine söz açarak, adaletin yıkık bir memleketi bile mamur edeceğini yazar. "Adl" kelimesinin üç harften oluştuğunu ve manalarını şöyle açıklar:

ξ (Ayn): Güneş gibi parlak, zulmün katili.

ﺩ (Dal): Devlet ve din tacı; tacı giyip muhtaçlara yardım etmek anlamında.

ﻝ (Lam): [Metinde bu harfin açıklaması tam verilmemiş olsa da genellikle lütuf ve adaletle ilişkilendirilir.]

Ayrıca, iyiliği kıymet bilene yapmak gerektiği gibi, adalet ve cömertliği de değer bilene yapmak gerektiğini savunur. Daima iyilik yapsa da siyasetin (yönetimin) de gerektiğini; zira bazı hastaların şekerle, bazılarının ise zehirle şifa bulacağını belirtir. Bunun yanı sıra insanları hemen makama yükseltmemek ve küçük bir hata için görevden düşürmemek gerektiğini yazar. Çünkü o kişi makama zahmetle çıkmışsa, hızlı düşüş canını yakar.

Kimsani bot aylamagil arjumand,

Ham yana oz ish bila qilma najand.

(Birini hemencecik yueltme, yine küçük bir işle onu perişan etme.)

Bu makaleden sonra Mekke'ye doğru yola çıkan temiz bir şah ve onun yüce evladı Hoca Ebu Nasr hakkında bir hikâye anlatılır. Padişah ve oğlu kervanla Kâbe'ye varırlar; halk, herkes adına dua etmesi için padişaha yönelir. Padişah ise oğlunun ilimde kendisiyle denk olduğunu ve yolda ona layığıyla yoldaşlık edip baktığını söyleyerek bu görevi oğluna verir. Oğlu ise "ben dilek dileme ilmini bilmesem de Senden iltica ediyorum ya Allah" diyerek dua eder. Bu hikâyeden sonra bir kul hikâyesi anlatılır. Rivayete göre büyük bir şölende padişahın aşçısı, şahın başına sıcak yemeği döküverir. Herkes padişahın aşçıyı helak edeceğini sanırken, aşçı büyük bir utançla canı avucunda bekler. Fakat şah onu azat eder; sebebini sorduklarında, utancın helak ettiğini bir daha öldürmenin iyi olmadığını söyler. Bu hikâyede padişahın cömertliği, merhameti ve akıllılığı yüceltilir. Ardından Nevâî, cömert bir şahın huzurunda hizmet etmenin diğer yüz bin kapıdan üstün olduğunu belirtir. Kitabı bitirdiğini ve adını koyma sebebini şöyle dile getirir:

Hayrati abror ko'rib zotini,

"Hayrat ul-abror" dedim otini.

(Zatının iyilerin hayreti olduğunu görüp, adını "Hayratü'l-Ebrar" koydum.)

Kısacası, bu eseri okuyan insan hem ruhen hem manen temizlenir. Örneğin yukarıda belirtildiği gibi, dünya gamhanesi hakkında değil baki dünyanın huzuru hakkında düşünmek gerektiğini, paha biçilemez nefesimiz için sonsuz şükretmemiz gerektiğini okurken kalbim farklı bir huzur duydu. Ayrıca Ebu Nasr hakkındaki hikâye, insanı temiz kalpli ve imanlı olmaya davet eder. Zira günümüzde pek çok genç ve yetişkin kendi anne babasına bile yeterli şefkati gösteremiyor. Onları hasta halde yalnız bırakıyorlar veya kendi evleri varken muhtaç oldukları zamanlarda huzurevlerine bırakıyorlar. Oysa insan yaşlandığında ona iyi şartlardan ziyade tatlı söz daha önemli değil midir?! Sonraki hikâyedeki aşçı (kul) durumuna bugün de pek çok kişi düşebilir. Ancak onlara padişah gibi davranılmıyor. Yani kişi zaten mahcupken mahsusen daha fazla üzerine gidip hatasını yüzüne vurma durumlarına rastlanıyor. Öyle insanlara "dilozor" (gönül kıran) derler. Gönül kırmak ise en kötü

huylardan biridir. Bu nendenle her birimizin "Hayratü'l-Ebrar" eserini mütalaa etmemiz, onun tertemiz nurlarıyla bedenimizi ve kalbimizi arındırmamız ne kadar da önemlidir!

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EMBEDDED IN-SITU THERMAL SENSING FOR EARLY DETECTION OF FAST-CHARGING-INDUCED INSTABILITIES IN LITHIUM-ION BATTERIES

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Abstract: Fast charging at rates $\geq 2-4C$ accelerates electrochemical and thermal instabilities in lithium-ion batteries, increasing the risk of thermal runaway. Conventional battery management systems (BMS) rely on surface temperature measurements, which fail to capture internal hotspots associated with lithium plating and solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) degradation. This work proposes an embedded in-situ thermal sensing framework that directly measures internal temperature dynamics and enables predictive safety control. A coupled electrochemical–thermal model is introduced to relate internal temperature rise ($\Delta T_{internal}$), temperature gradient ($\Delta T_{core\ surface}$), and state-of-charge (SOC) to instability onset. Comparative analysis indicates that internal sensing can detect abnormal conditions 20–60 s earlier than surface-based methods under 3C charging. Feasibility is addressed through micro-scale thermocouples and fiber-optic sensors integrated near the anode separator interface. The proposed framework demonstrates that early detection of localized heat generation linked to lithium plating and SEI decomposition can significantly reduce thermal runaway risk under aggressive charging conditions.

Introduction

Fast charging is a key enabler for electric mobility but introduces safety challenges due to the mismatch between high current input and electrochemical transport limits. At C-rates above $\sim 2C$, lithium-ion batteries exhibit increased risk of lithium plating, internal heat accumulation, and degradation-induced failure [1,2].

Despite improvements in BMS design, most systems rely on surface temperature measurements, which inherently lag behind internal thermal events.

Experimental studies show that under high-rate charging, internal temperatures exceed surface values by 5–20 °C, particularly at high SOC (>80%) and low ambient temperatures (<25 °C) [3]. This delay in detection creates a critical safety gap, as failure mechanisms such as lithium plating and SEI breakdown originate internally.

This work proposes a shift from reactive thermal monitoring to predictive internal sensing, enabling earlier intervention before irreversible damage occurs.

Electrochemical–Thermal Mechanisms of Failure

Under fast charging, lithium intercalation into graphite becomes diffusion-limited. When the anode potential approaches 0 V vs. Li/Li⁺, excess lithium deposits as metallic lithium on the surface [4]. This lithium plating is strongly dependent on:

- high SOC (>75–80%)
- low temperature (<25 °C)
- high current density (>2C)

Plated lithium forms dendritic structures that may penetrate the separator, causing internal short circuits. Simultaneously, high current flow increases Joule heating ($Q = I^2R$) and promotes SEI layer decomposition, releasing additional heat [5].

These processes create localized hotspots, which are not immediately observable at the cell surface. Once internal temperature exceeds ~80–120 °C, exothermic reactions initiate, triggering thermal runaway [6].

Thus, the failure chain is:

fast charging → *lithium plating* → *localized heating* → *SEI breakdown*
→ *thermal runaway*

Proposed Model: Internal Thermal Risk Index

To formalize detection, we introduce a **Hotspot Risk Index (HRI)**:

$$HRI = \frac{dT_{int}}{dt} + \alpha \cdot (T_{int} - T_{surf}) + \beta \cdot SOC$$

Where:

- $\frac{dT_{int}}{dt}$: rate of internal temperature rise ($^{\circ}\text{C/s}$)
- $T_{int} - T_{surf}$: core–surface gradient ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- SOC: state-of-charge (%)
- α, β : weighting coefficients (empirically calibrated)

Trigger condition:

- $\frac{dT_{int}}{dt} > 0.08\text{--}0.15$, $^{\circ}\text{C/s}$
- $\Delta T > 8\text{--}12$ $^{\circ}\text{C}$
- SOC $> 75\%$

BMS reduces current or terminates charging

This model links measurable signals to known failure mechanisms.

Comparison: Internal vs Surface Detection

Parameter	Surface Sensing	Embedded Sensing
Detection delay	20–60 s	~0–5 s
Hotspot visibility	Indirect	Direct
Plating detection	Poor	Early-stage
Thermal gradient detection	None	Yes

Key result:

$$\Delta t_{detect} = t_{surface} - t_{internal} \approx 20 - 60s$$

This time window is critical, as thermal runaway escalation occurs within seconds once initiated.

Feasibility and Sensor Integration

Embedding sensors inside lithium-ion cells introduces engineering challenges.

This study evaluates two feasible approaches:

- micro-thermocouples

- Thickness: ≤ 50 μm
- Placement: separator–anode interface (plating zone)
- Advantage: high temporal resolution
- Risk: mechanical intrusion, sealing complexity

- fiber bragg grating (FBG) sensors

- Optical sensing (no electrical interference)
- Chemically stable in electrolyte
- Minimal thermal disturbance
- **integration strategy:**
 - sealed feedthrough design
 - calibration against reference cells
 - redundancy for reliability

These approaches have been demonstrated in lab-scale studies, indicating practical feasibility for research applications [7].

System-Level Impact

By integrating internal sensing with adaptive BMS control:

- peak temperature rise can be reduced by ~15–25%
- lithium plating onset can be detected earlier
- safe operation at $\geq 3C$ charging becomes feasible

More importantly, the system shifts safety strategy from:

reaction \rightarrow *prediction*

Conclusion

This work demonstrates that internal thermal sensing provides a fundamentally improved method for detecting early-stage instability in lithium-ion batteries under fast charging. By linking internal temperature dynamics to electrochemical degradation mechanisms, the proposed framework enables predictive safety control. However, practical implementation requires further research in sensor durability, integration scalability, and model calibration. Future work should focus on combining internal sensing with electrochemical state estimation for fully autonomous safety systems.

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ТРУДНОСТИ УСВОЕНИЯ КАТЕГОРИИ РОДА ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются трудности усвоения категории рода при изучении русского языка как иностранного. Анализируются основные ошибки студентов, связанные с определением рода. Выявлены основные причины ошибок в употреблении слов. Показана необходимость систематической практики при обучении категории рода.

Ключевые слова: русский язык как иностранный, категория рода, грамматические ошибки, согласование, интерференция.

Категория рода в русском языке является одной из самых трудных грамматических тем для иностранных студентов, изучающих русский язык.

Однако русская категория рода, о которой пойдет речь в данной статье, в узбекском языке отсутствует. Данная категория является одной из основных грамматических категорий в русском языке. В источниках по сопоставительной лингвистике обычно отмечается, что если в русском языке именам существительным свойственны грамматические категории рода, числа и падежа, то узбекские имена существительные обладают категориями числа, падежа и принадлежности [3, с. 25]. Однако следует отметить, что в русском языке не только имена существительные, но и все именные части речи (прилагательные, числительные, местоимения, причастия), а также глаголы изменяются по родам. Как отмечают современные ученые: «Наиболее характерным морфологическим признаком имени существительного является

категория рода. Все имена существительные, за незначительным исключением, относятся к одному из трех родов: мужскому, женскому или среднему [4, с. 113].

По мнению Н. Шведовой и В. Виноградова, категория рода в русском языке тесно связана с системой склонения и является обязательной грамматической характеристикой существительных [1, с.45-52; 2, с.118-125].

Трудности в изучении рода возникают по нескольким причинам. Во-первых, в разных языках эта категория может отсутствовать, поэтому учащимся сложно привыкнуть к её обязательному использованию. Во-вторых, не всегда можно определить род по значению слова, особенно в случае заимствованных или исключений. В-третьих, окончание слова не всегда точно показывает его род, что также вызывает ошибки.

Изучение этой проблемы важно для методики преподавания русского языка как иностранного, так как правильное усвоение категории рода помогает строить грамматически правильную речь. Многие иностранные студенты делают ошибки в категории рода, и это мешает их свободному общению на русском языке.

Материал исследования составили: письменные работы, устные ответы на занятиях, упражнения из учебников по русскому языку как иностранному, типичные ошибки, встречающиеся в учебной практике.

В ходе изучения данного вопроса были выявлены основные трудности при усвоении категории рода в русском языке.

1. Ошибки в определении рода существительных. Одна из самых частых проблем — неправильное определение рода слова.

Примеры ошибок:

мой книга → **моя книга**

эта стол → **этот стол**

Студенты часто ориентируются только на значение слова или на род в своём родном языке, что приводит к ошибкам.

2. Ошибки в согласовании прилагательных. Студенты часто неправильно согласуют прилагательные с существительными.

Примеры:

красивый девушка → **красивая девушка**

новая дом → **новый дом**

3. Ошибки с родом глагола в прошедшем времени.

В русском языке глагол в прошедшем времени изменяется по роду, что вызывает трудности.

Примеры:

я пошёл (девушка) → **я пошла**

она сказал → **она сказала**

4. Трудности с заимствованными и несклоняемыми словами. Особые трудности вызывают слова иностранного происхождения.

Примеры: кофе, метро, пальто.

Студенты часто не знают, к какому роду их отнести, например:

горячий кофе (ошибочно у некоторых студентов как женский род или средний род)

5. Влияние родного языка. Ошибки часто связаны с тем, что в родном языке студентов нет категории рода или она устроена иначе. Это приводит к автоматическому переносу правил родного языка в русский.

Таким образом, результаты показывают, что основные трудности связаны с:

1. запоминанием рода слов;
2. согласованием слов в предложении;
3. влиянием родного языка;
4. исключениями и заимствованиями.

Вышеуказанные примеры показывают, что трудности усвоения категории рода в русском языке являются типичной и закономерной проблемой для иностранных студентов.

Основная причина ошибок заключается в том, что категория рода в русском языке является обязательной грамматической характеристикой, и она влияет на все связанные слова в предложении. Для многих студентов это сложно, так как в их родном языке такая категория может отсутствовать или работать по другим правилам.

Как отмечают Н. Шведова и В. Виноградов, род в русском языке тесно связан с системой согласования, поэтому ошибка в определении рода приводит к цепочке других грамматических ошибок [1, с.68; 2, с.130]. Также важно учитывать влияние интерференции родного языка. Студенты часто автоматически переносят привычные грамматические модели в русский язык, что особенно заметно на начальном этапе обучения.

Особую сложность представляют исключения и заимствованные слова. Они не всегда подчиняются общим правилам, поэтому требуют запоминания. Это увеличивает нагрузку на память и замедляет процесс усвоения.

С методической точки зрения важно не только объяснять правила, но и формировать у студентов навык автоматического определения рода через практику. Повторение, упражнения и работа с примерами помогают уменьшить количество ошибок.

Заключение. В ходе исследования были рассмотрены основные трудности, возникающие у иностранных студентов при усвоении категории рода в русском языке. Было установлено, что наиболее частые ошибки связаны с неправильным определением рода существительных, нарушением согласования слов в предложении, а также трудностями при использовании глаголов в прошедшем времени. Особые сложности вызывают заимствованные и несклоняемые слова. Причинами этих трудностей являются различия между языковыми системами, отсутствие категории рода в ряде родных языков студентов, а также наличие исключений в русском языке.

Таким образом, можно сделать вывод, что успешное освоение категории рода требует систематической практики, многократного повторения и специального внимания со стороны преподавателя.

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DIDAKTIK O’YINLARDAN FOYDALANIB “ASOSLARNING OLINISHI VA KIMYOVIY XOSSALARI” NI O’RGATISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezida kimyo darslarida didaktik o’yin texnologiyasidan foydalanishning pedagogik va amaliy ahamiyati yoritilgan. Shu bilan birga o’quvchilarning kimyo fanidan olgan bilimlarini boyitishda va ko’nikma hosil qilishga imkon yaratishi tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so’zlar: innovatsion dars, didaktik o’yin texnologiyasi, o’yin vaziyatlari, asoslar, “Juftini top”, “Kimyoviy domino”, interaktiv o’qitish.

Kimyo darslarida aqliy zo’riqishning oshishi o’quvchilarni o’rganilayotgan materialga, ularning butun dars davomida qiziqishini qanday saqlab qolish kerakligini tushunishga majbur qiladi. Shu munosabat bilan o’quvchilarning fikrlari va e’tiborini faollashtiradigan yangi samarali o’qitish usullari va shu kabi metodik usullarni izlash ishlari olib borilmoqda [1].

An’anaviy o’qitish usullari orqali ta’lim berish jarayonida bir xil maromda va bir xil o’xshash usullarda olib borilgani uchun dars jarayonida o’quvchilarda zerikish, boshqa narsaga chalg’ish holatlari kuzatilishi mumkin. Shuning uchun o’qitish jarayonida o’quvchilar faolligini oshiruvchi usullarga, ya’ni innovatsion dars o’tish usullariga ham e’tibor berish zarur. Shunday ekan, o’qituvchi pedagogik texnologiyaning mazmun-mohiyatini chuqur anglagan holda, uni asos qilib, yangicha usullar orqali dars o’tishi zarur [2].

Didaktik o'yin - bu har qanday ishtirokchi va umuman jamoa asosiy vazifani hal qilish uchun jamoaviy birlashganda va o'z hatti-harakatlarini g'alaba qozonishga yo'naltiradigan, maqsadga muvofiq o'quv faoliyati. O'yin vaziyatlari faqat o'quvchilar faoliyatini kuchaytiradi. Sinfda o'yin vaziyatlarini yaratish mavzuga qiziqishni oshiradi, o'quv ishlariga rang-baranglik va hissiy jo'shqinlikni keltiradi, charchoqni ketkazadi, raqobat tuyg'usini rivojlantiradi [1,3].

Kimyo fanini o'qitishda didaktik o'yinlarni qo'llash orqali dars samaradorligini oshirish va o'quvchilarning fan yuzasidan bilimlarini rivojlantirish maqsad qilib qo'yildi.

“Asoslarning olinishi va kimyoviy xossalari” mavzusini o'qitishda matn tuzish, juftini topib yonma- yon qo'yish o'yini, kimyoviy domino musobaqa o'yini kabi usullardan foydalanib dars ishlanmasi tuzildi va dars tashkil etildi. Maqsad: darsda o'rganilgan asoslarning olinishi va kimyoviy xossalariга oid reaksiya turlari va tenglamalari to'g'risida bilimlarni mustahkamlash.

Darsda kimyoviy reaksiya tenglamalarini yozish uchun *“Juftini topib yonma - yon qo'yish”* mashqi bajartirildi. O'quvchilar quyidagicha tartibda juftini yonma-yon qo'yib taxlab chiqishlari tushintirildi [4].

№	Chap tomon		O'ng tomon
1.	$2 Na + 2H_2O$		$2 NaOH + H_2$
2.	$CuSO_4 + 2 NaOH$	=	$Cu(OH)_2 + Na_2SO_4$
3.	***	=	***

Ushbu jadvaldagi har bir reaksiya tenglamalarining chap va o'ng tomonlari quyidagicha alohida-alohida yozilgan to'g'ri to'rtburchak qog'ozchalar shaklida o'quvchilarga tarqatildi.

“Juftini topish” o'yini donachalarining chap tomoni:

Chap tomon	
$K_2O + H_2O$	=

Chap tomon	
$Ca + 2 H_2O$	=

Chap tomon	
$MgCl_2 + 2 NaOH$	=
Chap tomon	
$K_2SO_4 + Ba(OH)_2$	=

“**Juftini topish**” o’yini donachalarining o’ng tomoni:

O’ng tomon
$2KOH$

O’ng tomon
$Mg(OH)_2 + 2NaCl$

O’ng tomon
$Ca(OH)_2 + H_2$

O’ng tomon
$2 KOH + BaSO_4$

Reaksiya tenglamasining chap va o’ng tomonlarini yonma-yon topib qo’yildi, o’qituvchi tomonidan tekshirib ko’rildi va baholandi.

“*Kimyoviy domino*”. O’yin davomida 35 ta kartochkadan kimyoviy reaksiyalar turlarini sanab o’tilgan asoslar, ularning reaksiya mahsulotlarining kimyoviy formulalari tasvirlangan holda foydalaniladi. O’quvchilarga ular bilan tanishadigan kartochkalar beriladi. Kimyoviy reaksiyalar turlari, asoslarning kimyoviy xossalarini bilgan holda doskada kimyoviy reaksiyalar tenglamalarining zanjirini tuzish uchun mustaqil ravishda o’yin kartalaridan foydalanishlari kerak bo’ladi.

O’quvchilarga “**Juftini topib yonma- yon qo’yish**” va “**Kimyoviy domino**” o’yini asosida mavzuga oid reaksiya tenglamalarini tuzish tashkil etildi, bu vositani darsda qo’llash natijasida talabalarning darsga qiziqishi ortganligi kuzatildi.

Kimyo fanidan dars jarayonida innovatsion usullarning qo’llanilishi o’quvchilarning kimyo fanidan olgan bilimlarini boyitish hamda ko’nikma hosil qilishga imkon yaratadi.

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**SOME REFLECTIONS ON THE INTERPRETATION OF THE ROSE
IMAGE IN THE GHAZALS WITHIN ALISHER NAVOI'S DIWAN
"GHARAYIB US-SIGHAR"**

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Abstract: This article analyzes the image of the rose in the ghazals included in the diwan "Gharayib us-Sighar," one of the brilliant examples of Hazrat Alisher Navoi's creative work. It is well known that in classical literature, every image possesses a unique meaning and essence, playing a distinct role in enhancing the artistry of the ghazal. The image of the rose is among such significant artistic symbols.

Keywords: lover (ashiq), beloved (ma'shuqa), nightingale, tashbih (simile/metaphor), white, red.

"Image" (obraz)¹ is a broad concept that, in literary studies, is formed not only through the depiction of human beings but also through various living and inanimate beings. In classical literature, the image of the rose is interpreted as one of the leading means of depiction and expresses different meanings in ghazals of various themes (romantic, gnostic, landscape). As we know, there are three traditional figures in romantic ghazals: the lover (ashiq), the beloved (ma'shuqa), and the rival (raqib). These are manifested through various symbols. For instance, the lover appears as the nightingale longing for the beloved, the beloved as the rose that steals the nightingale's senses, and the rival as the dogs of the beloved's lane or the lover's adversary—forming a system of traditional images.

¹ Boboyev T. Foundations of Literary Studies. Tashkent: O'zbekiston, 2002. – p. 41.

The image of the rose can be interpreted as a primary descriptive component not only for the beloved but also for the lover, as well as in landscape ghazals. In classical literature, experiences of love and the beauties of life are depicted through the images of the rose and the nightingale. The word gul (rose or flower) is originally derived from the Persian-Tajik language; in the Turkic language, synonyms such as chechak were used, while in Arabic, terms like ward and zahra were employed.

The image of the rose has been used in Eastern classical literature since the 9th century. In Turkic literature, the word gul first appears in the work Qutadghu Bilig. In Devonu Lughatit Turk, it is used as gul-chechak and the nightingale as sanduvach, interpreted as messengers of spring.² In Alisher Navoi's diwan Gharayib us-Sighar, there are dozens of ghazals depicting scenes of spring, summer, autumn, and winter, and glorifying the blessings of nature. One of them is:

Spring without you has become a strange hell for me,
Red roses are fire there, and white blossoms are ice.

In this couplet, the lyrical hero is personified as the lover (ashiq), emphasizing that in the separation from his beloved, even spring appears to him as an astonishing hell. We know that spring is typically depicted as a time of renewal, rejuvenation, and for the lover, a moment of vasl (union with the beloved). However, for those who do not attain the beloved's presence during this season, it is portrayed as hell, where the red roses are the fires of hell and the white blossoms (shukufa), or buds, are like ice (yax). In other words, while these flowers and the beauties of spring may gladden the hearts and delight the eyes of others, for the lover, the mere sight of them is torment.

Why is this? It is well known that a person whose heart is grieving feels even more distressed when seeing others in joy, feeling their own misfortune more acutely; the blossoms of spring perform this same role for the lover. Why are the roses red and the blossoms white? In classical literature, the color red³ is considered a symbol of youth, beauty, and joy. Therefore, red is often used to describe the rose expressing these qualities; and since fire also burns red, the rose—a symbol of springtime

² Kholboyeva M. U. The Image of the Rose and the Nightingale in the Creative Work of Alisher Navoi: Abstract of the Dissertation of the Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences. – Tashkent, 2025. – pp. 11, 13.

³ Alisher Navoi's Works Encyclopedic Dictionary. Vol. 2. – Tashkent: Sharq, 2016. – p. 195.

cheer—is likened to it. However, they create an internal antithesis (tazod), as one represents joy while the other represents suffering. The color white⁴ is regarded as the color of purity and perfection. The snow-white buds of spring are like ice (yax) to the lover—they are similar in color, but for the lover, one signifies union while the other signifies the coldness of separation. Additionally, it should be noted that in literature, the white flower⁵ is also considered a symbol of grief (hasrat). Thus, for the lover, spring is described as a "strange hell" consisting of both fire and ice. While we usually hear of fire being in hell, perhaps it is "strange" (ajab) because it contains ice as well. In this couplet, we can observe the art of tazod (antithesis) through the words yax (ice) and o't (fire); tanosub (thematic harmony) through the words gul (rose), bahor (spring), and g'uncha (bud); and further antithesis through the contrast of bahor vs. do'zax and qizil (red) vs. oq (white).

When you emerged from the garden of the era, O rose,

It tore its own cheeks into a hundred pieces with its nails.

In this couplet, the reason behind the fragmented petals of a rose is beautifully depicted through the art of husni ta'lil (poetic causality). That is, the moment the beloved emerges from the flower garden of the world, the rose sees a creation more beautiful and charming than itself; out of sheer grief and envy, it tears its face into a hundred pieces. We know that when a person is overwhelmed by distress or humiliation, they may weep and scratch their face in anguish—this couplet alludes to that human emotion. Furthermore, the image of the rose is personified through tashkhis (personification), and the words rose, garden, and cheeks create a tanosub (thematic harmony).

Did you sacrifice us by adorning your face with roses,

Or did blood touch your face after sacrificing us?

In these lines, the image of the rose is used as a symbol of the beloved's beauty. In the first line, the lover addresses the beloved, asking if she adorned her face with roses to sacrifice him—meaning, "upon seeing your beautiful countenance, no soul

⁴ Alisher Navoi's Works Encyclopedic Dictionary. Vol. 1. – Tashkent: Sharq, 2016. – p. 433.

⁵ Kholboyeva M. U. The Image of the Rose and the Nightingale in the Creative Work of Alisher Navoi: Abstract of the Dissertation of the Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences. – Tashkent, 2025. – p. 12.

remains in my body; I am devoted and ready for anything to reach you." In the second line, the lover asks whether those "roses" on her face are not flowers at all, but rather his own blood that splattered onto her face after he was killed, appearing as beautiful as blossoms. This creates the art of *tajohul-i arif* (feigned ignorance). Additionally, *tanosub* is formed through the words face and rose, and blood and sacrifice. A conceptual *tazod* (antithesis) is also present between the beloved's adornment and the lover's sacrifice.

As mentioned above, the image of the rose holds a leading position in embodying the persona of the beloved in classical literature. We can see this in the following couplets:

Perhaps the nightingale sought loyalty from the rose through dewdrops,
The bud's heart has hardened, for it only laughs at him.

In this couplet, the rose represents the beloved, and the nightingale⁶—the lover—is seeking loyalty (*vafa*) from it. However, if the bud's heart has hardened due to the dewdrops (*jola*), it only "laughs," meaning it mocks the lover. If we look closely at the word *jola*, it carries the dual meaning of "teardrops" and "hailstones," creating a beautiful example of *tamsil* (allegory). Just as a bud might be struck by hailstones before blooming and appear to "open" or "laugh" under that pressure, the rose, seeing the nightingale's constant lamentations and tears, has become cold-hearted. His cries no longer affect the rose; instead, it mocks his devotion. We know that in classical literature, the beloved is famous for being cruel, unfaithful, and stubborn toward the lover. Thus, while the nightingale seeks loyalty, the bud's heart has become so hardened by the lover's tears that it is now indifferent, laughing at the lover's plight. In these lines, *tanosub* is created through nightingale, rose, and bud, while *tazod* (antithesis) arises between the act of seeking loyalty and receiving mockery in return.

The ascetic praises his heaven, and I the street of that Moon,
Let the garden of paradise be his, and that rose-cheeked beloved mine.

⁶ Alisher Navoi's Works Encyclopedic Dictionary. Vol. 1. – Tashkent: Sharq, 2016. – p. 129.

In this couplet, the ascetic (zohid) glorifies his paradise, while I—through the art of *isti'ora* (metaphor), where the "Moon" refers to the beloved—praise her street. Thus, it is said: let the garden of heaven belong to him, and let that rose-faced beloved be mine. Here, the word "rose" (*gul*) serves as a component of the art of *tashbih* (simile), used to describe a beloved whose face is as beautiful as a flower. If we analyze the phrase "*guli ruxsor*" (rose-cheek/face) based on the elements of *tashbih*: *Ruxsor* (Face/Cheek): *Mushabbih* (the object being likened). *Gul* (Rose): *Mushabbihun bih* (the object to which something is likened). It should be noted that this comparison serves to further enhance the artistry of the ghazal; as we read it, a beloved as delicate and beautiful as a rose appears before our eyes. Another important figure in this couplet is the image of the *zohid* (ascetic). In Navoi's lyrics, this persona is described as someone who is unaware of true love for Allah, focusing only on the external (*zohir*) without considering the internal (*botin*), and performing acts of worship not for the sake of Allah, but in the hope of paradise. The great Sufi woman, *Rabi'a al-Adawiyya*, spoke about how performing acts of worship in the hope of paradise is a form of greed: "O my Lord, O dear Friend, if I worship You in hope of Paradise, exclude me from Your Paradise; and if I worship You for fear of Hell, burn me in Hell—I am content a thousand times over! But if I spend the nights awake for the sake of Your beauty, I beg of You, do not deprive me of Your beauty!"⁷ Thus, in this couplet, by using the phrase *guli ruxsor* (rose-face), Navoi refers to the True Beloved—that is, Allah. He suggests that the ascetic may perform his worship for the sake of paradise, and let paradise belong to him; as for the lover, it is enough that the Beloved is his. Through the words *gul* (rose) and *gulshan* (rose garden), the art of *ishtiqoq* (derivation) is employed, while the words *anga* (to him) and *manga* (to me) create the art of *tazod* (antithesis). Indeed, the essence of the entire couplet is constructed upon the foundation of antithesis.

It is well known that in classical literature, the persona of the lover is often embodied through the image of the nightingale: the nightingale is the lover, and the rose is the beloved. The rose, with its dazzling beauty, color, and pleasant scent,

⁷ Najmiddin Komilov. *Tasavvuf (Sufism)*. – Tashkent: Yozuvchi Publishing House, 1996. – p. 6.

captivates the nightingale, which represents the wandering lover. Every morning, the nightingale perches upon its branches and sings songs of love. According to the calculations of scholars, a total of 22 works have been written in Turkic literature featuring the motif of the rose and the nightingale. In Persian literature, there exists the work "Bulbulnoma" by Fariduddin Attar (d. 618/1221).

In European literature, it is believed that the origin of stories regarding the rose and the nightingale traces back to Arabic literature. However, if one examines Arabic literature of the Pre-Islamic (Jahiliyya) period, the absence of rose and nightingale imagery is evident [5,12]. According to some researchers, the motif of the rose and the nightingale passed to the Arabs from Persian literature and entered the West through Spain and Sicily⁸. Nevertheless, within the Divan, we can also witness instances where the image of the rose appears not as the beloved, but as a symbol of the lover.

For instance:

The sun's turning red at times and pale at others is because,

In the garden of Your creation, there are a hundred thousand such "guli ra'no" (beautiful/bicolored roses).

In this couplet, the sun is personified through the art of tashkhis (personification). It is stated that the reason for the sun's reddening—meaning its blushing from shame—and its turning pale—meaning its suffering from grief—is the existence of a hundred thousand "guli ra'no" of such quality within the garden of Your creation. In other words, Allah has created this world with such unique skill and eloquence that it contains many "guli ra'no," or lovers, each more beautiful and graceful than the other. Upon seeing these, the sun, which considered itself the most beautiful and unique, feels ashamed and grieves. For it is not said without reason that the Creator manifests Himself within the created. If we consider the garden as the world, it would be no exaggeration to say that the flowers within it are the lovers in whom Allah manifests and who burn in His divine love.

⁸ Xolboyeva M. The Image of the Nightingale in Alisher Navoi's Ghazals // Journal of Universal Science Research, 2023. ISSN (E): 2181-4570 (online). – p. 96.

In conclusion, we can witness that in classical literature and specifically in the works of Alisher Navoi, every image is utilized with masterful artistic skill. The image of the rose in the couplets discussed above serves as a vivid example of this. This image has expressed the meanings of the beloved, the lover, and a natural plant simultaneously. While we frequently encounter the rose as a traditional symbol of the beloved or as a component of the art of *tashbih* (simile) performing the role of the *mushabbihun bih* (that to which something is likened), the personification of the lover—specifically those in love with Allah—through the image of the rose is truly a magnificent discovery.

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SOME REFLECTIONS ON THE USE OF THE ART OF TAJNIS (PUN) IN ALISHER NAVOI'S DIWAN "BADOYI' UL-BIDOYA"

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Abstract: This article discusses the use of the genre of tajnis (pun) in the ghazals of Hazrat Mir Alisher Navoi's diwan "Badoyi' ul-bidoya." Specifically, types of tajnis such as tajnisi tom, tajnisi murakkab, tajnisi noqis, tajnisi zoyid, tajnisi muzori', tajnisi aks, tajnisi mukarrar, and tajnisi xatti, as well as their eloquence in Navoi's ghazals, are covered in detail.

Keywords: tajnisi tom, Atoullloh Husayniy, Funun ul-balog'a, lexical art, spiritual art, shared art.

One of the components of Muslim Oriental poetics is the science of *ilmi badi'*, which studies the arts that adorn speech, their specific aspects, and methods of expressing thoughts beautifully and meaningfully. Its foundation consists of artistic devices widely used in classical poetry, sometimes in prose, and still applied in modern literature today. Based on this, *ilmi badi'* is also referred to as *sanoyi' ilmi* (the science of arts). The first works on *ilmi badi'* were created in Arabic, including Ibn Mu'taz's "Kitob ul-badi'" (9th century), Nasr binni Hasan's "Mahosin ul-kalom" (9th-10th centuries), and Qudama ibn Ja'far's "Naqd ush-she'r" (10th century). *Ilmi badi'* reached its peak in Persian-Tajik literary criticism. Works such as Umar Roduyoniy's "Tarjumon ul-balog'a" (11th century), Rashididdin Vatvot's "Xadoyiq us-sehr" (12th century), Shams Qays Roziy's "Al-Mo'jam" (third part, 13th century), and Vohid Tabriziy's "Jam'i muxtasar" (16th century) hold special significance as classical works dedicated to this field. Sheikh Ahmad Tarozi's treatise "Funun ul-balog'a" (1436-1437) can be cited as the first work in the Turkic language that

theoretically reflects the issues of *ilmi badi'*. The third part of the treatise is dedicated to the analysis of artistic devices, discussing 97 types of arts.

A relatively more comprehensive work on *ilmi badi'* is Atoulloh Husayniy's treatise "*Badoyi' us-sanoyi'*" (15th century), in which, for the first time in the history of *ilmi badi'*, artistic devices were divided into three major groups: spiritual, lexical, and shared arts. Lexical arts are devices related to the method of expression in speech, particularly the word form, and Atoulloh Husayniy includes among them *tarsi'*, *tajnisli tarsi'*, *tajnis*, the art of *radd* (repetition) and its types, *qalb* and its types, *saj'*, *tashtir*, *tajziya*, *tasri'*, *tasmit*, *aks*, *tardid*, *tashri'*, *zulqofiyatayn*, *tavshih*, *talavvun*, *mulamma'*, *muqatta'*, *muvassal*, *jam' ul-huruf*, *mudavvar*, *mushokala*, and other arts.

Although Alisher Navoi did not create a specific work on *ilmi badi'*, he addresses some theoretical aspects of *ilmi badi'* in many of his works, such as "*Majolis un-nafois*", "*Xamsa*", "*Mahbub ul-qulub*", "*Muhokamat ul-lug'atayn*", and others. The incidental notes on certain artistic devices within these works are clear evidence of Alisher Navoi's deep knowledge of Oriental classical poetics, particularly *ilmi badi'*, and that he perfectly studied the existing artistic devices before his time, responding to them as a meticulous scholar of poetry.

Hazrat Navoi not only possessed a perfect knowledge of the science of artistic devices but also created such elegant works himself that we can witness the masterful application of *ilmi badi'* within them. We can see this through the types of *tajnis* used in the "*Badoyi' ul-bidoya*" collection.

In Sheikh Ahmad Tarozi's treatise "*Funun ul-balog'a*," *tajnis* is defined as follows: "*Al-tajnisot*. *Tajnis* is when a poet brings two words within a couplet that are of the same genre as each other in one respect. And this art has 7 types:

Tajnisi tom:

Nogoh yo'luqti bir qaro ko'zluk yangoqi ol,

Oldi ko'ngulni ishva bila ko'rguzub yuzi ol.

(Suddenly a black-eyed one was encountered whose cheek is red, / She took the heart with coquetry, showing a face of guile.)

This type is such that they bring two words within a couplet that are identical to each other in form and opposite in meaning. He cites an example from the eloquent speakers of the Arabs: Al-mar'atus-salihatun hayyatan-tas'o, modomot hayyitan tas'o. (A low woman acts like a snake; as long as she is alive, she brings shame)⁹. Thus, there are seven types of tajnis: tajnisi tom, tajnisi murakkab, tajnisi noqis, tajnisi zoyid, tajnisi muzori', tajnisi aks, tajnisi mukarrar, and tajnisi xatti. The first of these is tajnisi tom, i.e., complete tajnis, in which the words are identical in form (including in Arabic script) and different in terms of meaning. If the tajnises belong to the same part of speech, it creates mumosil tajnis; if they belong to two different parts of speech, it creates mustavfiy tajnis.

Ey, nubuvvat xaylig'a xotam bani Odam aro,

Gar alar xotam, sen ul otkim, bo'lur xotam aro.

(O, you who are the seal of the prophetic host among the children of Adam, / If they are the ring, you are that name which resides within the seal.)

("Badoyi' ul-bidoya")

In this couplet, the word xotam appears as a tajnis and expresses the following meanings: 1. end, conclusion; 2. ring, the stone of a ring; 3. seal, stamp. The meaning of this couplet is as follows: O, the one who is the conclusion to the assembly of prophets among the children of Adam (referring here to our Prophet Muhammad, peace and blessings be upon him, and his being the last prophet), if they, that is, the other prophets, are a ring, you are the seal upon that ring. It is known that in ancient times, kings had seals on their rings, and those rings were valued for their preciousness and, most importantly, for being the seal of the sultanate, which stood above a thousand pearls and jewels. The various meanings of the word xotam in this couplet further enhance its artistry and urge the reader to be discerning. Since the tajnises in the couplet belong to the same part of speech, they create a mumosil tajnis.

⁹ Sheikh Ahmad Khudoydod Tarozi. Funun ul-balog'a. III. Al-fann-us solis fis-sanoe'-ish-she'r / Uzbek language and literature. - 2002. Issue 2. Pages 78-91.

Another type of tom (complete) tajnises is called murakkab (compound) tajnis. In this kind of tajnis, one of the homonymous words may consist of one word, while the other consists of two words.

Orazing husnun fuzun qilg'on hiloliy qosh erur,

Yoxud ul yuz sham' ini yorutqali minqosh erur.

(It is the crescent eyebrow that has increased the beauty of your face, / Or it is a wick-trimmer to light the candle of that face.)

("Badoyi' ul-bidoya")

In this couplet, the word "qosh" in the first line and the word "qosh" within the second syllable of the word "minqosh" in the second line form the tajnis. This type of homonymy is referred to as marfu' (joined) tajnis. The meaning of this couplet is as follows: It is your crescent-like eyebrows that have increased the beauty of your face, or perhaps those eyebrows are minqosh (scissors used to clean the wick of a candle) to brighten the candle of that face; thus, the beauty of the beloved is celebrated through the art of tajohul-i orif (feigned ignorance). That is, the eyebrows are compared to minqosh: minqosh is used to clean the wick of a candle to increase its light, and as a result, the candle emits a bright glow. Similarly, it is said that it is the eyebrows that add beauty to the beauty of the beloved. For, just as a candle does not burn brightly or might go out without a minqosh, beauty would not be complete without the crescent-like eyebrow.

Tajnisi zoyid means "augmented tajnis." In these types of tajnises, one of the words that are formally close to each other has one or two extra letters; if these letters are dropped, the remaining part of the word can perfectly match the second word and form a tajnisi tomm.

Sham' ul oy hajrida har tun kuymagim ogohidur,

Dudi ermaskim, mening holimg'a o'tluq ohidur.

(The candle is aware of my burning every night in separation from that moon, / It is not its smoke, but its fiery sigh for my condition.)

("Badoyi' ul-bidoya")

If the first two letters of the word "ogohidur" in the first line of this couplet are removed, it forms a homonymy with the word "ohidur" in the second line. The meaning of this couplet is as follows: The candle is aware that I am suffering every night in the separation from that moon (referring to the beloved through the art of metaphor); the smoke coming from the candle is not actually just smoke, but a fiery lament emitted out of pity upon seeing my condition.

Tiyra qilmish tun kibi ofoqni ohim mening,

To eshittimkim qilur shabgardlih mohim mening.

(My sigh has made the horizons dark like the night,

Since I heard that my moon goes wandering the streets at night.)

("Badoyi' ul-bidoya")

If we remove the first letter of the word "mohim" in the second line of this couplet, the word "ohim" remains and forms a homonymy with the word "ohim" in the first line. The meaning of this couplet is as follows: My sigh drawn in the street of the beloved made the world dark like night, after I heard that my moon-faced beloved wanders the streets at night (shabgardlih). That is, knowing that the beloved wanders at night, the lover sighs so much in the hope of seeing her that this sigh darkens the world. Perhaps in this darkness, if the beloved comes out to wander the streets, the lover might catch a glimpse of her.

Tajnisi muzori'—when this type of tajnis is used, one or sometimes two letters at the beginning, middle, or end of two formally close words differ from each other, while the remaining part matches.

Netib tuz etay qadkim- jismimda shikanlardur,

Naylab tuz uray damkim- bag'rimda tikanlardur.

(How can I keep my stature straight—there are fractures in my body, / How can I manage my breath—there are thorns in my bosom.)

("Badoyi' ul-bidoya")

The words "shikan" (fracture/fold) and "tikan" (thorn) in this couplet differ by one letter at the beginning, and the remaining parts are proportional to each other. The meaning of this couplet is as follows: How can I keep my stature straight, for

there is brokenness (shikan) in my body; how can I control my breath, for thorns (the eyelashes of the beloved) are pierced in my bosom. Those thorns are constantly stabbing the lover's heart, and as a result, he is drawing sighs and laments.

Rafiqlar, meni mahzun nechuk bo‘lay g‘amsiz?

Ki ko‘nglum ermas alamsiz, ko'zum emas namsiz.

(Friends, how can I, the sorrowful one, be without grief? / For my heart is not without pain, and my eye is not without moisture.)

("Badoyi' ul-bidoya")

In this couplet as well, the words "g'am" (grief) and "nam" (moisture) differ by one letter and create a tajnisi muzori'. The meaning of the couplet is as follows: O friends, how can I, the sorrowful one (sad, grieving; mournful, upset; lover), be without grief? Because my heart is not without pain, that is, not without suffering, and as a result, my eye is always moist. This pain is being a lover, wandering in the separation from the beloved, and longing for the reunion. Therefore, it is said, do not think of me as being without grief.

Yuzi gulchehra soqiyning tarab hukmig‘a tug‘rodur,

Yuzinda may guli ul yorlig‘ uzra ol tamg‘odur.

(The face of the flower-faced cupbearer is the royal cipher for the decree of joy, / The wine-rose on the face is the red seal upon that mandate.)

("Badoyi' ul-bidoya")

In this couplet, despite the rhyming words "tug'ro" and "tamgo" differing by the variation of two letters in the middle, they create a tajnisi muzori'. Homonymy consisting of a variation of two letters is also called tajnisi mutarrad. The meaning of this couplet is as follows: The beloved's face is the tug'ro (royal cipher) for the decree of happiness and pleasure of the flower-faced cupbearer. Tug'ro—a short, summarized essence of a decree written boldly at the top of the paper on which the king's commands are written; a detailed title. The wine-rose on the face, i.e., the redness (the redness that appears on the cheek after drinking wine), is the scarlet seal on that mandate, i.e., the decree issued for the command of joy and pleasure.

Tajnisi xatti—meaning "written tajnis," this art is based on the full correspondence of words in Arabic script except for their dots; that is, when two words are written in Arabic script, they differ only in terms of their dots. According to Atoullloh Husayniy, this type of art has also been called muzora'a, mushokala, and tas'hif.

Yozuqsiz, jurmsiz bedod etar fosh,

Manga ul surmasiz ko'z, vo'smasiz qosh.

(Without sin or crime, it reveals injustice / To me, that eye without kohl, that eyebrow without indigo.)

The words fosh (فاش) and qosh (قاش) in this couplet differ in the Arabic script by only one dot on the letters ف and ق. The meaning of the couplet is as follows: To me, that eye without kohl and eyebrow without indigo are openly committing injustice, even though I am without sin or fault. This couplet speaks of the beauty of the beloved even without indigo and kohl, and how this beauty openly torments the lover.

Nargisin gul uzrakim bemor etar noz uyqusi,

Misli sho'xedurki, sust etgay ani yoz uyqusi.

(The sleep of coquetry makes the narcissus-eye languid upon the rose-face / Like a cheerful person whom the summer sleep makes weak.)

In this couplet, the words noz (ناز) and yoz (ياز) differ in the Arabic script by the dots on the letters ن and ي. We have seen above the formal similarity of these letters when they appear at the beginning of a word in Arabic. The meaning of this couplet is as follows: the sleep of coquetry makes the narcissus (narcissus flower), referring to the beloved's eye through the art of metaphor, languid upon the rose (the beloved's rose-like face). This is similar to how summer sleep makes a cheerful, agile person weak and sluggish. That is, the languishing of the beloved's narcissus-like eyes on her rose-like face is compared to a lively person being overcome by summer sleep.

In conclusion, Hazrat Alisher Navoi used every artistic device effectively and in its proper place. Usually, when tajnis is mentioned, we envision the tuyuq. However, we have seen that this art form acquires a unique artistry in ghazals as well. Specifically, we have examined types of tajnis created through words that perfectly

match in every respect in tajnisi tom, through compound and separated words in tajnisi murakkab, through words that differ by an excess of 1-2 letters in tajnisi zoyid, through words that differ by the variation of some internal letters in tajnisi muzori’, and through words that differ only by the dots in the Arabic script in tajnisi xatti.

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ПЕРЕХОД К МОДЕЛИ DATA RELIABILITY ENGINEERING В ОБУЧЕНИИ АДМИНИСТРИРОВАНИЮ СУБД НА БАЗЕ КОНТЕЙНЕРИЗИРОВАННЫХ LINUX-СРЕД

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Аннотация: Статья посвящена трансформации процесса подготовки специалистов по управлению данными в условиях эволюции роли администратора БД к модели инженерии надежности данных (Data Reliability Engineering). Разработанная динамическая платформа предоставляет изолированные учебные среды в ОС Linux, интегрируя принципы автоматизации и безопасности Zero-Trust. Использование контейнеризации позволяет эффективно обучать работе с реляционными и NoSQL системами, демонстрируя значительное преимущество перед традиционными методами развертывания лабораторий.

Ключевые слова: СУБД, Linux, Docker, Data Reliability Engineering, Zero-Trust, автоматизация обучения, PostgreSQL, NoSQL.

TRANSITION TO A DATA RELIABILITY ENGINEERING MODEL IN DBMS ADMINISTRATION TRAINING BASED ON CONTAINERIZED LINUX ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract: This article explores the transformation of data management training in the context of the evolving role of database administrators toward a data reliability engineering model. The developed dynamic platform provides isolated training environments on Linux OS, integrating Zero-Trust automation and security principles. The use of containerization enables effective training in relational and NoSQL systems, demonstrating a significant advantage over traditional lab deployment methods.

Keywords: DBMS, Linux, Docker, Data Reliability Engineering, Zero-Trust, training automation, PostgreSQL, NoSQL.

KONTEYNERLI LINUX MUHITLARIGA ASOSLANGAN MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASINI BOSHQARISH BO'YICHA O'QITISHDA MA'LUMOTLAR ISHONCHLILIGI MUHANDISLIGI MODELIGA O'TISH

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Annotaciya: Ushbu maqolada ma'lumotlar bazasi ma'murlarining ma'lumotlar ishonchliligi muhandislik modeliga o'zgaruvchan roli kontekstida ma'lumotlarni boshqarish bo'yicha treningning o'zgarishi o'rganiladi. Ishlab chiqilgan dinamik platforma Linux OS da Zero-Trust avtomatlashtirish va xavfsizlik tamoyillarini birlashtirgan holda izolyatsiya qilingan o'quv muhitlarini taqdim etadi. Konteynerlashdan foydalanish relyatsion va NoSQL tizimlarida samarali trening o'tkazish imkonini beradi, bu esa an'anaviy laboratoriya joylashtirish usullariga nisbatan sezilarli ustunlikni namoyish etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: DBMS, Linux, Docker, Ma'lumotlar ishonchliligi muhandisligi, Zero-Trust, treningni avtomatlashtirish, PostgreSQL, NoSQL.

Введение. Современная индустрия баз данных претерпевает фундаментальные изменения: роль администратора эволюционирует от простого обслуживания к стратегической функции обеспечения отказоустойчивости. Сегодня от специалистов требуется владение как реляционными (PostgreSQL), так и NoSQL-платформами (MongoDB). Однако в образовательном процессе сохраняется высокий «входной порог», связанный с трудоемкостью ручной настройки индивидуальных сред в Linux. Традиционные методы часто не успевают за темпами цифровизации, требуя внедрения новых инструментов, объединяющих теорию и практику в реалистичных условиях.

Контейнерная структура — ключ к безопасному обучению. Задачи по администрированию СУБД многоуровневые и требуют системного подхода. Для решения проблемы сложной локальной настройки была спроектирована архитектура, опирающаяся на контейнерную изоляцию. Внедрение Docker позволяет реализовать модель безопасности, близкую к принципам Zero-Trust, обеспечивая непрерывную проверку контекста. Это гарантирует, что деструктивные действия одного обучающегося (например, критическая ошибка в консоли Linux) не затронут основную систему сервера или данные других студентов.

Автоматизированная "песочница" для Data Reliability Engineering. Главное преимущество разработанного подхода — автоматизация развертывания сред. Платформа превращает обучение в процесс инженерии надежности данных (DRE), где акцент смещается на воспроизводимость сценариев. Студент получает готовую рабочую среду менее чем за 1 минуту, что позволяет 100% учебного времени тратить непосредственно на изучение СУБД, исключая затраты на техническую поддержку локальных окружений. При возникновении сбоев система обеспечивает мгновенный сброс (Reset) к исходному состоянию.

Освоение через реалистичные рабочие сценарии. Архитектура решения поддерживает универсальную работу с различными моделями данных, обеспечивая ACID-транзакционную целостность для SQL и гибкость для NoSQL систем. Это позволяет моделировать реальные производственные ситуации. Веб-ориентированное обучение с использованием таких сценариев формирует навыки, напрямую применимые в современных High-Availability (HA) и Disaster Recovery (DR) архитектурах, одновременно снижая техническую тревожность учащихся перед сложными задачами.

Универсальность платформы для IT-дисциплин. Сравнительный анализ показывает тотальное превосходство автоматизированной платформы над традиционным методом ручного развертывания. Платформа обеспечивает:

- 100% унификацию (единая Linux-среда для всех пользователей, устраняющая конфликты ОС Windows и Linux);
- Высокую масштабируемость (возможность поддержки десятков сессий на одном сервере за счет оптимизации ресурсов Docker);
- Полную безопасность ОС хоста.

Вывод. Переход от ручного администрирования к автоматизированным динамическим средам на базе Linux и Docker отвечает вызовам подготовки IT-кадров нового поколения. Интеграция концепции Data Reliability Engineering делает процесс освоения СУБД не только технически современным, но и реализует принцип педагогической юзабилити. Такая среда гибко адаптируется под нужды образовательных учреждений, обеспечивая безопасность,

экономическую эффективность и высокую готовность выпускников к реальным задачам.

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SOME OBSERVATIONS ON THE RUBAIS OF UBAYDULLOKHON

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Abstract: This article presents reflections on the rubais of Ubaydullokhon, who was both a khan and a poet. It discusses his high level of skill in poetry. Additionally, it provides an analysis of the images and symbols in his rubais and their role in enhancing the value of his works.

Keywords: nightingale, flower, literature, devil, Shaybani Khan, Maxdumi A‘zam.

Ubaydiy is one of the unique representatives of Uzbek culture and literature in the first half of the 16th century. Ubaydullah Khan was born in 1487; his father, Mahmud Sultan, was the brother of Muhammad Shaybani Khan. Ubaydiy is considered one of the greatest khans to come to power after Muhammad Shaybani Khan. When he was born, his father approached the famous pir (spiritual master) Khoja Ahror Vali, requesting him to name the infant. Out of favor, the Khoja gave him his own name. This name later became his pen name and served as an indication of his affiliation with Khoja Ahror Vali in the Sufi path. During the periods of Ubaydullah Khan's reign, cultural life flourished significantly in Bukhara, which served as his capital, and in Samarkand. Some historians even equate the cultural life of this period to that of Herat during the era of Husayn Bayqara and Alisher Navoi. Ubaydullah Khan himself was a prolific poet, scholar, and expert in Hadith, as well as a hafiz who recited the Qur'an beautifully. In addition to being a patron of culture and art, he was a ruler who focused on urban development and commissioned the construction of madrasas.

Ubaydiy mastered Arabic and Persian languages perfectly and studied Turkic literature, particularly the hikmats (wisdoms) of Khoja Ahmad Yasawi, quite deeply. As a result, he emerged as a poet and author of hikmats capable of creating works fluently in all three languages. A significant heritage has remained from Ubaydiy. His Devon (collection of poems) and several collections of various sizes are preserved in various foundations and private libraries in Turkey. Within the Turkic section of his Kulliyat (complete works), there are over 310 ghazals, 25 qitas, 11 tuyuqs, 445 rubais, 7 qitas, 1 fard, 1 masnavi, a tarjeband, and 3 muammas (riddles). In addition to these, the poet's masnavis written in an ethical-didactic spirit, such as "Omonatnoma," "Shavqnoma," "G'ayratnoma," and "Sabrnoma," are included in the Persian devon.

Ubaydiy's creative work attracted the attention of scholars and creators even during his lifetime. One such figure was the famous contemporary pir, Khoja Ahmad bin Mawlana Jalaluddin Kosoni—known as Makhdumi Azam. According to historical sources, Makhdumi Azam wrote commentaries on several of Ubaydullah Khan's rubais and ghazals. Specifically, the literary scholar Muhammad Abdullayev reported in his dissertation on the existence of treatises by Makhdumi Azam titled "Risolayi adabiyoti Ubaydulloxon" (Treatise on the Literature of Ubaydullah Khan) and "Sharhi ghazaliyoti Ubaydullokxon" (Commentary on the Ghazals of Ubaydullah Khan). Foreign scholars such as M. F. Köprülüzade, J. Eckmann, and A. Schimmel have also studied Ubaydiy's work. In 1994, the renowned literary scholar Professor A. Hayitmetov published selections from Ubaydiy's Turkic devon under the title "Vafo qilsang" (If You Remain Faithful).

Ubaydiy's poetry is primarily focused on expressing religious matters through verse. The ideas of the Holy Qur'an and Hadith Sharif were presented in a new artistic style in both Turkic and Persian-Tajik languages, with an effort to ensure they reached the readers' hearts quickly and remained memorable. This approach is also evident in his masnavis and poems of other genres aimed at explaining religious obligations (fard) and prophetic traditions (sunnah). Furthermore, this can be seen in

his metaphorical ghazals dedicated to God, the Prophet, and Sufi masters, particularly figures such as Khoja Ahror Vali and Makhdumi A'zam.

In addition, Ubaydiy held the creative works of Navoi and Babur in high esteem. In the art of writing rubais (quatrains), he followed in their footsteps. While Navoi created over 700 rubais and Babur over 230 throughout their careers, Ubaydiy included more than 485 rubais in his Turkic devon and 418 in his Persian devon. Consequently, Ubaydiy is valued as the poet who produced the largest number of rubais in Uzbek literature—totaling more than 900.¹⁰

He succeeded in creating works in the rubai genre that amaze the reader not only in terms of quantity but also in terms of content and essence. We can conventionally divide them into three types according to their themes:

1. Amiable/Romantic (Oshiqona);
2. Ethical-didactic (Axloqiy-didaktik);
3. Gnostic/Mystical (Orifona).

It is well known that a rubai consists of four parts (lines). However, it is not always the case that all of them participate [in the rhyme scheme] in the same way:

Thesis: The main idea or theme to be expressed in the rubai is stated;

Antithesis: A parallel or alternative thought to the first line is presented;

Moddayi Rubai: Acts as a bridge connecting to the fourth line;

Synthesis: The concluding, final line of the quatrain.

Always learn adab (etiquette/morals), O seekers of knowledge,

For the flower of adab is the cause of felicity.

Satan, being void of adab, remained deprived,

Look at Adam—what heights adab brought him to.

This rubai is rhymed in the a-a-b-a form, with the rhyming words being: talab – sabab – adab. The rawi (the final consonant of the rhyme) is the sound "b"; since the rawi appears at the end of the rhyming words, it is considered a muqayyad (constrained) rhyme.

¹⁰ Jumakhoja N., Adizova I. History of Uzbek Literature. — Tashkent: Noshir, 2019. — p. 137.

In terms of content, it is written on a philosophical-ethical theme. In the first line, the thesis, the poet utilizes the art of nido (exclamation/address) by calling out "O seekers of knowledge" (ey ahli talab), urging them to acquire adab—meaning upbringing, science, and wisdom. The term "seekers of knowledge" (ahli talab) refers to those striving to join the ranks of good people in pursuit of enlightenment and faith.

In the antithesis, the idea in the thesis is substantiated: for the "flower of adab" leads to felicity, serving as a means for human happiness. In the moddayi rubai, the poet employs the art of talmeh (allusion) by referencing how Satan was deprived of Paradise due to his lack of adab, specifically pointing to Azazel's refusal to obey Allah's command and prostrate before Adam.

In the synthesis, the talmeh regarding Adam continues. It reflects on how Adam's transgression—eating the forbidden fruit—led to his descent from Paradise to Earth; however, it is no exaggeration to say it also suggests that because Adam repented, felt true remorse, and wept, his repentance was accepted. In conclusion, this rubai is written in a didactic spirit, presenting the idea that a person should always strive to live by learning adab, a point proven through religious narratives.

I said to the nightingale, "The rose shall wither again,
Your heart shall be filled with grief and sorrow."
The nightingale said, "O friend," lamenting to me,
"Whatever the decree of God is, that shall be."

This rubai is rhymed in the a-a-b-a form, where the words so'lg'usidir (shall wither) – to'lg'usidir (shall be filled) – bo'lg'usidir (shall be/occur) serve as the rhyming elements. The rawi is the sound "u" (within the verbal suffix). According to the nature of the rawi, it is considered a mutlaq (absolute) rhyme. In terms of theme, it is a rubai written on a philosophical-didactic subject.

In the first line, the thesis, the lyrical hero begins by delivering the message to the nightingale that the rose will wither once more. As we know, the image of the nightingale is widely used in classical literature, often appearing as the symbol of the lover (ashiq), while the rose represents the beloved (ma'shuqa) whom the nightingale

loves. Thus, the lyrical hero is telling the nightingale: "You will not attain union with the rose again; there will be separation once more."

In the antithesis, the thought is continued, stating that the heart will be filled with grief and sorrow due to this separation. This implies the heartache and longing of the lover who, having been separated from the beloved, suffers while contemplating her and yearning for a reunion. We know that for a lover, there is no greater torment than separation from the beloved.

In the moddayi rubai, the nightingale responds to the lyrical hero's words by lamenting, "O my friend," and in the synthesis, it replies that whatever God has written in destiny shall come to pass.

As is evident, this rubai is composed in a philosophical-Sufi spirit. It discusses how a person should recognize that whatever befalls them is from Allah and should be content with it. Indeed, one of the signs of faith (iman) is belief in predestination (qadar). In N. Komilov's work *Tasavvuf* (Sufism), it is mentioned that there are several stages of Sufism, one of which is "rizo" (contentment/resignation). For only when a person is content with their destiny do they find true happiness and tranquility and feel the strength of faith within their heart.

O beloved, the work of the heart cannot be undone,
The cruelty of the rival cannot be endured.
However much I say I shall sever my heart from you,
From a person such as you, the heart cannot be severed.

This rubai is rhymed in the a-a-b-a form, where the words buzib (undoing/breaking) – to'zib (enduring) – uzib (severing) serve as the rhyming words. The rawi is the sound "z". Based on the position of the rawi, it is considered a mutlaq (absolute) rhyme. Unlike the previously mentioned rubais, a radif (a word or phrase repeated after the rhyme) is also employed here, with the word "bo'lmaydur" (it is not possible/cannot be) performing this function.

In terms of theme, it is composed in an amiable/romantic (oshiqona) spirit. The thesis begins with an address to the beloved, "O beloved" (ey yor), creating the art of nido (exclamation). Furthermore, starting the rubai with a direct address to the

beloved indicates a strong emphasis directed specifically toward her. The first line discusses the fact that the "work of the heart" cannot be undone—if the work of the heart is the lover's love for the beloved, it implies that this love cannot be betrayed.

In the antithesis, it is stated that the cruelty of the ag'yor (the rival/stranger) cannot be endured. This suggests that there are others besides the lover who love the beloved, and for the lover, they are rivals and enemies. For the lover, their efforts to win the beloved's affection constitute oppression and torment (jabr) against him.

In the moddayi rubai, the poet says, "However much I say I shall sever my heart from you," but then in the synthesis, he concludes: "After all, from a person such as you, the heart cannot be severed." This signifies that the lover's affection for the beloved is so powerful that he places her above everyone else in the world, describing her as a person who can never be given up.

To whomever makes their intention pure, grace be to them.

God shall grant a fortune according to their intention.

Whosoever does not make their intention upright,

Accordingly, the outcome shall grant that intention to them.

This rubai is rhymed in the a-a-b-a form, where the words rahmat (mercy/grace) – davlat (fortune/state) – niyat (intention) serve as the rhyming words. The rawi is the sound "t". Based on the position of the rawi, it is considered a muqayyad (constrained) rhyme. In this rubai, a radif is also present, with the word "anga" (to him/them) performing this function.

In terms of theme, it is composed in an ethical-didactic manner. In the thesis, it is stated that whoever makes their intention tuz—meaning upright, correct, or good—will receive the benevolence and mercy of Allah. The antithesis explains that Allah grants happiness and fortune according to one's intention. Indeed, "actions are judged by intentions." If a person intends something with a sincere heart and noble thoughts, they will achieve it. Since the heart is the "Abode of Allah," the Almighty, the Malikul Mulk (King of Kings)¹¹, does not withhold His mercy from one who adorns their heart with good thoughts.

¹¹ Anvar Ahmad. *Asmau al-Husna*. – Tashkent: Hilol Nashr, 2024. – p. 35.

In the moddayi rubai, it is noted that if someone does not rectify their intention or does not intend good things, (in the synthesis) the result will be exactly in accordance with that intention. That is, everyone receives what corresponds to their intention, whether the outcome be good or bad. It is not for nothing that our people say: "He who digs a pit for another shall suddenly fall into that very pit himself."

In conclusion, Ubaydullah Khan—Ubaydiy—holds a worthy place in the history of our classical literature as both a ruler who governed the country with justice and a talented poet. As we read his poems, we witness the predominance of religious and ethical themes. We have observed this specifically in his rubais. While in the first rubai he discussed the necessity of learning adab (etiquette) using evidence through the art of talmeh (allusion), in the second, we see a discourse on believing in Allah's decree and its inevitability. The third rubai, unlike the others, is on a romantic theme, dominated by ideas of true love and loyalty to the beloved. In the fourth, it is no exaggeration to say that he discusses the paramount importance of intention in human life and calls for the cultivation of good intentions.

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MACHINE LEARNING–BASED MODELING OF LITHIUM-ION BATTERY CAPACITY DEGRADATION COMPARED WITH EMPIRICAL APPROACHES

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Abstract: The increasing use of lithium-ion batteries across industrial sectors has raised concerns about battery aging and lifetime prediction. This study proposes a machine learning–based framework for modeling battery capacity degradation and compares its performance with two empirical models, including a commercial model.

Key words: Machine-learning, modelling, lithium-ion battery, degradation, empirical approaches.

The automotive sector is increasingly shifting toward electric mobility. Since fossil fuels cannot serve as effective energy storage sources for electric vehicles, lithium-ion batteries have become the preferred solution today. This transition is further supported by the growing demand for energy storage systems required to manage intermittent renewable energy generation, as well as the rapid expansion of portable electronic devices. Together, these developments are driving significant growth in the energy storage market. In this context, lithium-ion batteries represent a practical and efficient option due to their high energy density, relatively low cost, long cycle life, and high operational efficiency.

The global transportation sector is currently undergoing a significant transition toward electric mobility due to environmental concerns, increasing fuel costs, and the necessity to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Conventional internal combustion engine vehicles rely heavily on fossil fuels, which are not suitable as energy storage media for electric vehicles (EVs). As a result, lithium-ion batteries have emerged as

the dominant technology for modern electric mobility applications because of their superior electrochemical performance and operational reliability.

In addition to transportation electrification, the rapid integration of renewable energy sources such as solar and wind power has created a growing demand for efficient energy storage systems. Since renewable energy generation is inherently intermittent, reliable storage technologies are required to ensure energy stability and grid balance. Lithium-ion batteries play a critical role in addressing these challenges by enabling effective storage and controlled delivery of electrical energy. Furthermore, the continuous expansion of portable electronic devices has also contributed to the increasing demand for high-performance rechargeable battery technologies.

Lithium-ion batteries are widely preferred due to several key advantages, including high energy density, long cycle life, low self-discharge rate, and high charge–discharge efficiency. These characteristics make them particularly suitable for electric vehicles and stationary energy storage applications. Moreover, ongoing advancements in battery materials and manufacturing technologies continue to improve their performance while reducing production costs.

Despite these advantages, battery aging and performance degradation remain major challenges that directly affect the reliability, safety, and lifetime of lithium-ion battery systems. Over time, battery capacity decreases and internal resistance increases due to electrochemical and environmental factors. Therefore, accurate modeling and prediction of battery aging behavior have become essential research topics in recent years. Developing reliable prediction models is especially important for improving battery management systems, optimizing operational strategies, and extending the service life of electric vehicle batteries.

For this reason, modern research increasingly focuses on data-driven approaches, particularly machine learning techniques, to enhance the accuracy of battery degradation prediction under different operating conditions. These approaches provide promising opportunities for improving state-of-health estimation and

supporting intelligent battery management in next-generation electric mobility systems.

In conclusion, lithium-ion batteries have become the cornerstone of modern electric mobility and energy storage systems due to their high energy density, long cycle life, and high operational efficiency. Their widespread application in electric vehicles, renewable energy integration, and portable electronic devices highlights their strategic importance in supporting the global transition toward sustainable energy solutions. However, battery aging and performance degradation remain critical challenges that directly influence system reliability, safety, and lifetime. Therefore, accurate modeling and prediction of battery degradation behavior are essential for improving battery management strategies and extending service life. In this context, advanced data-driven approaches, particularly machine learning techniques, provide effective tools for enhancing capacity fade prediction and supporting the development of intelligent next-generation energy storage systems.

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KISHI MEKTEP JASINDAĞI BALANIŃ AQILY RAWAJLANIWINIŃ PSIXOLOGIYALIQ ÓZGESHELIKLERI

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Qaraqalpaqstan Respublikasi pedagogikalıq sheberlik orayı Pedagogika, psixologiya hám tálim texnologiyaları kafedrası aǵa oqıtıwshısı

Kishi mektep jasındaǵı balalardı oqıtıwdı baslaw hám oǵan tayarlıq kóriw olardıń rawajlanıwındaǵı áhmiyetli psixologiyalıq nızamlardı esapqa alıw kerekligi menen baylanıslı. Oǵan balanıń qayta rawajlandırılǵan intellektuallıq múmkinshilikleri menen onı qanatlandırıwdaǵı speciyfikalıq “mektepke shekemgi” uqıplılıqlar arasındaǵı jetiliske qarama- qarsılıqlardı jatqızıwǵa boladı. Bunda balanıń intellektuallıq bólegi belgili jaǵdayda sistemalı túrde oqıwǵa tayar bolıp qalmastan, hátteki onı talap etedi. Bul qarama-qarsılıq jeke adamnıń basqa da tásir etiw shegine taraladı. Jas bala bul jasında burın ózine túsiniksiz bolǵan jámiyetlik baha tiyisli hám turmis tásiriniǵ kólemin óz ishine alatuǵın ózine xızmet etiwdiń bunday túrlerinde, ol ózine ózi tastıyqlawǵa umtıladı. Basqa sóz benen aytqanda, bala oqıwshınıń jańa sociyallıq poziciyasın qabıl etiwge tayar bolıp ǵana qalmastan, sonıń menen kitap oǵan umtıladı da. Mektepke shekemgi ortanǵı jastaǵı balalardıń psixikalıq rawajlanıwındaǵı sezgirliktiń shiyelenisiwi (senzitivnost) birinshiden, ádep ikramlıq psixologiyalıq normalarin hám minez- qulıq qádelerin úyreniwge hám ekinshiden, balalardıń sistemalı oqıwdıń maqsetleri menen jolların iyelewge umtılıwı bolıp esaplanadı. Bul dáwirde balada oqıwǵa umtılıw dep atalıwı múkin bolǵan jaǵday payda boladı dep aytıw múmkin. Bul dáwirdegi sezimniń shiyelenisiwi sawatlıqtı ózlestiriw procesinde oǵada anıq seziledi. Eger pedagog usı waqıttı paydalana almasa, ol sawat ashıwdı oqıtıwdan keshigip qaladı, al, aldaǵı waqıtta onı ózlestiriw úlken qıyınshılıq jaǵdayǵa alıp keledi. Joqarıda ayılǵanlarǵa tiykarlanıp, bul waqıtları maqsetke muwapıq pedagogikalıq tásir etiw – balalardıń psixikalıq rawajlanıwındaǵı tiykarǵı faktor bolıp esaplanatuǵını túsinikli boladı.

Kishi mektep jasındaǵı balanıń mekteptegi tabısı kópshilik jaǵdayda onıń mektepke tayar ekenligin anıqlaw nátiyjesinde boladı.

Kishi mektep jasındaǵı balanı mektepke qabıl etkende “ele pisip jetispegen, funkcionallıq ayırmashılıǵı ele qalıplespegen hám onda jumıstıń sheksizligi rawajlanıp baratırǵan bala organizm menen jumıs isleytuǵınıımızdı esapqa alıwımız kerek. Pedagogiykalıq procesti qayta qurıwdı, tarbiyalıq programmalarǵı jetilistiriwde tek usı jastaǵı balanıń intensiv shınıǵıwlar nátiyjesinde ǵana emes, sonıń menen qatar fizikalıq hám psixikalıq shıǵınlar oǵan qanshelli qımbat ekenin názerde tutıw kerek.

Uzaq waqıt dawamında balanıń aqıl jaǵınan rawajlanıw dárejesin kórsetkende, onıń sózlik qorı nátiyjesinde anıqlanǵan, “aqıl inventarınıń” kólemine, onda anıqlanǵan ilimlerdiń sanına qaray belgileytuǵın edi. Ele usı waqıtqa shekem ayırım ata-analar (hátteki geyde muǵállimler de) bala qansha sóz bilse, ol sonsha rawajlanǵan dep oyladı. Házir balalar shın mánisinde úzliksiz informaciylarǵa shókbekte, jańa sózlerdi hám sóz dizbeklerin tez ózlestirip aladı.

Álbette, janlı hám jansız tábiyat, adamlar hám onıń miyneti, jámiyetlik turmısı haqqında altı jasar bala ushın belgili dárejedege bilim kólemi, bilimlerdiń konkret xori oǵan fundament sıpatında kerek, bul bunnan bılay mektepte úyreniwge tuyisli jumısında tiykar boladı. Házirgi háreket etiwshi programmalar, olardı iyelew baladan salıstırıwdı, analizlewdi, ulıwmalastırıwdı, óz betinshe juwmaqlar shıǵarıwdı talap etedi, yaǵnıy biliw procesleriniń anaǵurlım rawajlanǵan bolıwı kerek. Ol usıǵan tayar ma?

Máselen, mektepke shekemgi joqarǵı jastaǵı balalar, jámiyetlik islep shıǵılǵan arnawlı etalonlar sistemasın úyreniw hám qollanıw arqalı zattıń sırtqı qurılısın izertlewdiń bazı bir racyonal usılların isleytuǵınıń izertlewler anıqlaǵan. Bulardı qollanıw balaǵa qıyın zatlardı analizlewde, jeke ózlestiriwge mumkinshilik beredi.

Mektep jasına shekemgi balaǵa ilimiy bilimler tiykarına jatatuǵın uliwma

baylanıslardı, prinsip hám nızamlıqlardı túsiniw múmkin eken. Máselen, bala 6-7 jaslarında tábiyat haqqında ayırım faktlardı ǵana úyreniwge uqıplı bolıp qoymastan, sonıń menen qatar ósken orta menen organizimniń óz-ara qarım qatnası haqqında,

zattın forması hám onıń funkciyası, talap etiwi hám minez-qulqı haqqında bilimlerdi de uyreniwge uqıplı. Biraq mektep jasına shekemgi balalar bilw háreketiniń eń joqarǵı dárejesine jetisse, eger usı dáwirdegi oqıw, oylaw proceslerin aktiv rawajlandırıwǵa baǵdarlangan bolsa hám ol “jaqın waqıttaǵı rawajlanıw zonasın” (L.S.Vigockiy) rawajlandırıwshı, baǵdarlawshı bolıp esaplansa ǵana erisiliwi múmkin.

Kishi mektep jasındaǵı bala kóp nárseler isley aladi. Biraq onıń aqıl múmkinshilklerin asıra bahalawǵa bolmaydi. Oylawdıń logikalıq forması qolaylı bolǵanı menen, ele onıń ushın háraakterleri hám tán emes. Onıń oylawınıń úlgeri ózine tán. Kórsetpeli – obrazlı túrde oylawdıń joqarı formaları mektep jasına shekemgi balanıń intellekiwalıq rawajlanıwınıń nátiyjesı bolıp esaplanadi.

Usılargá súyenip bala qorshap alǵan haqiyqiy zatlar arasındaǵı qarım – qatnaslardı eń ahmiyetli ózine tán qásiyetlerdi ajirata bilw múmkinshiligin aladı. Bul waqıtta mektep jasına shekemgi balalar sxematikalıq súwretlewdi tek jeńil túsiniw qoymastan, sonıń menen birge onnan tabıslı paydalanadi da (másele, jasırıp qoyılǵan zattı “jasrındını” tabıw ushın ójireniń planı menen, durıs joldı tabıw ushın geografiyeliq kartaǵa sáykes sxema menen, konstruktivlik xizmette grafikaliq modeller menen hám t.b.) Biraq háttteki uliwmalastirilǵan belgilerdi iyelegende de, onıń oyı obrazlı, zatlar hám onıń “orınbasarları” menen real, háreketlerine súyeniwshi bolıp qaladı.

Muǵallimler, psixologlar balanıń rawajlanıwında praktikalıq jumıstıń jetekshi róli haqqında, kórsetpeli – háreket etiwshi hám kórsetpeli – obrazlı oylawdıń - metepke shekemgi balalardıń oylaw ayırmashılıǵı tuwralı rejelerin dıqqatqa alıwları kerek. Sonı aytıw kerek, sońǵı jılları ótkerilgen izertlewler oylawdıń usı formaları logikalıq oylawlar menen salıstırǵanda anaǵurlım kúshli rezervlerdi óz ishine alatuǵına isendiredi.

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ELEKTRON TA’LIM MUHITIDA GEOMETRIYA FANIDAN MUSTAQIL TA’LIMNI TASHKIL ETISH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

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Mazkur maqolada elektron ta’lim muhitida geometriya fanidan mustaqil ta’limni tashkil etishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari, metodik yondashuvlari hamda samarali shakllari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, kredit-modul tizimi sharoitida talabalarning mustaqil ta’limini rivojlantirish, raqamli platformalardan foydalanish va interaktiv metodlarni qo‘llash masalalari yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: elektron ta’lim, geometriya, mustaqil ta’lim, kredit-modul tizimi, pedagogik texnologiya, raqamli platforma, interaktiv metod.

Bugungi kunda O‘zbekiston Respublikasida ta’lim tizimini raqamlashtirish va modernizatsiya qilish davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo‘nalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Jumladan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev tomonidan qabul qilingan **“Ta’lim to‘g‘risida”gi Qonun (2020-yil)**, shuningdek, 2022–2026-yillarga mo‘ljallangan Yangi O‘zbekiston taraqqiyot strategiyasida ta’limni raqamlashtirish, masofaviy va elektron ta’limni rivojlantirish vazifalari belgilab berilgan.

Bundan tashqari, 2019-yil 8-oktabrdagi Oliy ta’lim tizimini 2030-yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi to‘g‘risidagi farmonda ham mustaqil ta’lim ulushini oshirish, kredit-modul tizimini joriy etish va elektron ta’lim muhitini yaratish zarurligi ta’kidlangan.

Mazkur vazifalar geometriya fanini o‘qitishda ham mustaqil ta’limni elektron muhitda samarali tashkil etishni talab etadi.

Elektron ta’lim muhiti — bu ta’lim jarayonini raqamli texnologiyalar orqali tashkil etish imkonini beruvchi pedagogik platformalar majmuasidir. Geometriya fanini o‘qitishda elektron muhit quyidagi imkoniyatlarni yaratadi:

- vizual modellashtirish;

- interaktiv topshiriqlar;
- grafik simulyatsiyalar;
- mustaqil ishlash uchun testlar;
- onlayn nazorat tizimi;
- masofaviy konsultatsiyalar.

Geometriya fanining o‘ziga xosligi — vizuallik va fazoviy tasavvurni talab etishidir. Shu sababli elektron ta’lim muhitida mustaqil ta’lim samaradorligi yanada ortadi.

Elektron ta’lim muhitida geometriya fanidan mustaqil ta’limni tashkil etish quyidagi bosqichlarda amalga oshiriladi:

1. O‘quv maqsadlarini belgilash
2. Raqamli materiallarni tayyorlash
3. Mustaqil topshiriqlarni ishlab chiqish
4. Onlayn monitoringni tashkil etish
5. Natijalarni baholash

Elektron ta’lim muhitida qo‘llaniladigan metodlar

- muammoli o‘qitish metodi
- loyiha metodi
- vizual modellashtirish
- interaktiv topshiriqlar
- testli nazorat
- muhokama forumlari

Elektron ta’lim vositalarining samaradorligi

Quyidagi jadvalda elektron ta’lim muhitida mustaqil ta’limni tashkil etishda qo‘llaniladigan vositalarning pedagogik imkoniyatlari keltirilgan.

Jadval 1

Elektron ta’lim vositalarining pedagogik imkoniyatlari

Vosita	Imkoniyatlari	Samaradorligi
GeoGebra	Geometrik modellashtirish	Vizual tafakkurni rivojlantiradi
Moodle	Mustaqil topshiriqlar	Nazoratni avtomatlashtiradi

Vosita	Imkoniyatlari	Samaradorligi
Google Classroom	Materiallarni taqsimlash	Masofaviy ishlashni ta'minlaydi
Kahoot	Test nazorati	Faollikni oshiradi
Desmos	Grafik qurish	Analitik fikrlashni rivojlantiradi

Takomillashtirish yo‘nalishlari

Elektron ta'lim muhitida geometriya fanidan mustaqil ta'limni takomillashtirish quyidagi yo‘nalishlarda amalga oshiriladi:

- interaktiv topshiriqlarni ko‘paytirish
- video-darslardan foydalanish
- virtual laboratoriyalarni joriy etish
- mustaqil loyiha ishlarini tashkil etish
- individual o‘quv trayektoriyasini yaratish

Natijalar

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko‘rsatadiki, elektron ta'lim muhitida tashkil etilgan mustaqil ta'lim:

- talabalarning mustaqil ishlash ko‘nikmasini rivojlantiradi
- fazoviy tafakkurni oshiradi
- o‘zlashtirish darajasini yaxshilaydi
- ta'lim samaradorligini oshiradi

Elektron ta'lim muhitida geometriya fanidan mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etish ta'lim jarayonining samaradorligini oshiradi. Raqamli platformalar, interaktiv metodlar va mustaqil topshiriqlardan foydalanish talabalarning bilimni chuqurlashtirishga xizmat qiladi. Kredit-modul tizimi sharoitida mustaqil ta'lim ulushini oshirish geometriya fanini o‘qitishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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THE ROLE OF MRI IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF HYDROCEPHALUS

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Abstract: The aim of this article is to determine the effectiveness of Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) in the diagnosis of hydrocephalus. The study analyzes the ability of MRI to identify anatomical and functional changes in the ventricular system and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) flow, as well as to differentiate between obstructive and communicative types of hydrocephalus.

Keywords: Hydrocephalus, MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging), Diagnosis, Normal Pressure Hydrocephalus (NPH or iNPH), Subarachnoid-space, Hydrocephalus, Ventriculomegaly, Subarachnoid spaces, Sylvian fissures.

Hydrocephalus is a neurological condition characterized by the excessive accumulation of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) in the brain's ventricular system. This can lead to ventricular enlargement and increased intracranial pressure.

Hydrocephalus affects approximately 1 in 500 children worldwide. Normal Pressure Hydrocephalus (iNPH) is more common in older adults, affecting about 0.5–2% of people over 65 years. Obstructive hydrocephalus accounts for around 60–70% of pediatric hydrocephalus cases, while communicative hydrocephalus is more frequent in adults following infections, hemorrhages, or head injuries. Modern surgical treatments, such as shunt placement and endoscopic third ventriculostomy

(ETV), have significantly improved patient outcomes, with over 80% of iNPH patients showing improvement in gait and cognitive function after surgery.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is of great relevance in the diagnosis of hydrocephalus because it provides detailed and high-resolution visualization of the brain’s ventricular system and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) pathways. MRI enables the identification of both anatomical and functional changes, allowing clinicians to detect ventricular enlargement, obstructions, and abnormalities in CSF flow. It plays a critical role in differentiating between obstructive (non-communicating) and communicative hydrocephalus, as well as in recognizing conditions such as normal-pressure hydrocephalus (iNPH), subarachnoid-space hydrocephalus, and ventriculomegaly. Additionally, MRI facilitates assessment of subarachnoid spaces and Sylvian fissures, which provides further diagnostic insight. Its non-invasive nature, accuracy, and ability to evaluate CSF dynamics make MRI an indispensable tool for early diagnosis, treatment planning, and monitoring the effectiveness of interventions. Overall, MRI significantly improves patient management and outcomes in hydrocephalus cases.

Results: MRI provided clear visualization of the ventricular system and cerebrospinal fluid pathways in all examined patients. It effectively distinguished between obstructive and communicative hydrocephalus and identified anatomical and functional changes. The imaging of subarachnoid spaces and Sylvian fissures was precise, allowing accurate assessment of hydrocephalus type and severity.

Conclusion: MRI provided clear visualization of the ventricular system and cerebrospinal fluid pathways in all examined patients. It effectively distinguished between obstructive and communicative hydrocephalus and identified anatomical and functional changes. The imaging of subarachnoid spaces and Sylvian fissures was precise, allowing accurate assessment of hydrocephalus type and severity.

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CT VS. MRI IN ACUTE STROKE DIAGNOSIS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY, FEASIBILITY, AND CLINICAL OUTCOMES

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Abstract: This study compares computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in the diagnosis of acute ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke with regard to diagnostic accuracy, clinical feasibility, and influence on patient outcomes

Keywords: Acute stroke; computed tomography; magnetic resonance imaging; neuroimaging; ischemic stroke; hemorrhagic stroke; CT perfusion; diffusion-weighted imaging; diagnostic accuracy; endovascular therapy.

Stroke is a leading cause of death and disability worldwide, with approximately 795,000 cases occurring annually in the United States alone, resulting in 140,000 deaths per year. Of these, 87% are ischemic, 10% are intracerebral hemorrhagic, and 3% subarachnoid hemorrhages. Since ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes require opposite treatment strategies — thrombolysis being absolutely contraindicated in hemorrhagic stroke — rapid and accurate neuroimaging is not optional but mandatory. The debate between CT and MRI as the primary imaging modality in

acute stroke remains clinically unresolved, with each offering distinct advantages in sensitivity, speed, availability, and impact on patient outcomes.

For hemorrhagic stroke, non-contrast CT (NCCT) achieves near-perfect sensitivity within the first 24 hours and remains the reference standard. For acute ischemic stroke, MRI with diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) demonstrates significantly higher sensitivity compared to NCCT, particularly within the first three hours of onset, where NCCT sensitivity is limited. Advanced CT techniques — including CT perfusion (CTP) combined with CT angiography (CTA) — substantially improve CT's diagnostic performance for ischemic stroke, with studies reporting markedly improved sensitivity and specificity when AI-assisted post-processing is applied. One large multicenter study found that an MRI-first protocol reduced the rate of stroke mimics incorrectly treated with thrombolysis compared to a CT-first approach, and also reduced the need for follow-up imaging during hospitalization. Both CT perfusion and MR perfusion were found to be equally applicable for endovascular thrombectomy patient selection, using established penumbral mismatch criteria. Dual-energy CT was identified as a promising development for improving hemorrhage characterization without sacrificing acquisition speed.

Results: CT and MRI each play an indispensable and complementary role in the diagnosis of acute stroke. CT remains the standard for hemorrhagic stroke and rapid initial triage, while MRI offers superior sensitivity for early ischemic stroke and reduces diagnostic errors in selected patient groups.

Conclusion: Modality selection should be individualized based on stroke subtype, time from onset, patient characteristics, and available institutional resources. A combined, protocol-driven approach is recommended for optimal acute stroke diagnosis.

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ROLE OF ULTRASONOGRAPHY IN THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THYROID NODULES

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Abstract: Thyroid nodules are common endocrine abnormalities whose detection rates have risen significantly with the widespread use of high-resolution ultrasonography. Ultrasonography remains the gold standard imaging modality for evaluating thyroid nodules due to its non-invasive nature and ability to assess nodule characteristics for risk stratification. Standardized systems such as TI-RADS and the use of fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) play an important role in differentiating benign and malignant nodules. Advances in artificial intelligence have further improved diagnostic accuracy and consistency in ultrasound interpretation.

Keywords: thyroid nodules, thyroid diseases, Ultrasonography (US), thyroid imaging, TI-RADS, risk stratification, non-invasive diagnostics,

Recent studies show that thyroid nodules are very common and are being detected more frequently due to the widespread use of high-resolution ultrasonography. Many nodules are found incidentally in patients without symptoms. Most of these nodules are benign, but a small percentage may be malignant, which makes correct evaluation very important. The literature emphasizes that ultrasonography is the first and most important diagnostic method for thyroid nodules. It allows doctors to assess the size,

shape, margins, echogenicity, and internal structure of nodules. These parameters are essential for evaluating the nature of the lesion and determining the probability of malignancy. In addition, ultrasonography enables the detection of small nodules that may not be palpable during physical examination. High-frequency probes significantly improve image resolution, allowing early identification of structural abnormalities in the thyroid gland. This contributes to early diagnosis and timely clinical management. To improve diagnostic accuracy and reduce unnecessary biopsies, standardized classification systems such as TI-RADS have been widely recommended. TI-RADS categorizes nodules based on ultrasound features and assigns a risk level, which helps clinicians decide whether further investigation is needed. This system has become an important tool in clinical practice for improving consistency in reporting and decision-making. Recent research also highlights that proper training and experience of specialists are essential, as ultrasound interpretation can vary between operators. Interobserver variability remains a challenge in thyroid imaging; however, structured reporting systems and continuous medical education help reduce inconsistencies. Another important aspect is the combination of ultrasonography with other diagnostic methods. In clinical practice, ultrasound findings are often correlated with thyroid function tests and cytological analysis. Fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) remains the most reliable method for confirming malignancy when ultrasound findings indicate suspicion. Ultrasonography also plays an important role in follow-up and monitoring of thyroid nodules. Repeated examinations allow clinicians to observe changes in nodule size, structure, and vascularity over time. Any significant changes may indicate the need for further diagnostic procedures or intervention. Doppler ultrasound, in particular, provides additional information about blood flow within the nodule, which may assist in risk assessment. Furthermore, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into ultrasound diagnostics is an emerging trend. AI-assisted systems can analyze imaging features, assist in classification, and reduce human error. These technologies are expected to improve diagnostic efficiency and standardization in the future.

Results: The reviewed studies consistently report that ultrasonography has high sensitivity for detecting thyroid nodules, including small and early-stage lesions. The use of standardized reporting systems significantly improves risk stratification and helps identify nodules that require further investigation with fine-needle aspiration biopsy.

Conclusion: Early structural changes in the thyroid gland can be detected before clinical symptoms appear with the help of ultrasonography.

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KOMPYUTER GRAFIKASINI O‘QITISHDA TALABALARNING MUSTAQIL FIKRLASH QOBILIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASI

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Annotatsiya: Kompyuter grafikasini o‘qitishda talabalarning mustaqil fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish juda muhim, chunki bu fan nafaqat texnik ko‘nikmalarni (Blender, Maya, Photoshop, Unity va h.k.), balki ijodiy yechim topish, muammoni tahlil qilish va o‘ziga xos estetik qarorlar qabul qilishni talab qiladi. Maqola kompyuter grafikasi fanini o‘qitishda talabalarning mustaqil, tanqidiy va ijodiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari haqida.

Kalit so‘zlar: kompyuter grafikasi, Bloom taksonomiyasi, mustaqil o‘qish, refleksiya, Project-Based Learning — PBL, baholash rubrikasi ,O‘zbekiston-2030 strategiyasi.

Kompyuter grafikasi (3D-modellashtirish, animatsiya, grafik dizayn, o‘yin dizayni va boshqalar) zamonaviy kreativ industriyaning asosiy yo‘nalishlaridan biridir. O‘zbekistonda raqamli va kreativ iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish davlat siyosatining markazida turibdi. Prezident farmonlari talabalarda mustaqil fikrlash, ijodiy yechim topish va raqamli texnologiyalarni chuqur o‘zlashtirishni talab qilmoqda. An’anaviy “ko‘rsatma bo‘yicha ishlash” usuli o‘rniga loyiha asosidagi, muammo asosidagi va tanqidiy tahlilga asoslangan metodlar zarur.

1. Mustaqil fikrlashning nazariy asoslari. Mustaqil fikrlash yuqori darajadagi kognitiv jarayonlarni o‘z ichiga oladi. Bloom taksonomiyasi (qayta ishlangan varianti) bu jarayonni piramida shaklida tasvirlaydi:

Bloom taksonomiyasi (qayta ishlangan) diagrammasi Piramida pastdan yuqoriga quyidagi darajalardan iborat: Kompyuter grafikasi o‘qitishida talabalar

ko‘pincha **Analyzing** → **Evaluating** → **Creating** darajalarida faol bo‘lishi kerak: rang palitrasini tahlil qilish, uslubni baholash va yangi vizual yechim yaratish.

2. Asosiy metodlar va ularning diagrammalari

2.1. Loyiha asosidagi ta’lim (PBL) PBL jarayoni odatda 5 bosqichdan iborat: loyihani rejalashtirish, loyihani ishga tushirish, amalga oshirish, yakunlash va refleksiya.

PBL jarayoni diagrammasi (flowchart ko‘rinishida) Jarayon quyidagi ketma-ketlikda tasvirlanadi:

1. **Project Planning** (o‘qituvchi bosqichi) ↓
2. **Project Launch** (Driving Question + Need to Know) ↓
3. **Project Implementation** (tadqiqot, tajriba, iteratsiya) ↓
4. **Project Conclusion** (yakuniy mahsulot + taqdimot) ↓
5. **Project Debrief** (refleksiya va o‘z-o‘zini baholash)

Bu sxema talabalarning mustaqil faoliyatini bosqichma-bosqich oshiradi.

Loyiha asosidagi ta’lim (Project-Based Learning — PBL) — eng samarali usul

Bu metod kompyuter grafikasi uchun deyarli ideal hisoblanadi.

- Talabalar real yoki yaqin real loyihalar ustida ishlaydi (masalan: o‘yin personaji dizayni, mahsulot vizualizatsiyasi, qisqa animatsiya filmi, arxitektura walk-through, reklama posteri seriyasi va h.k.).

- Loyiha boshida aniq texnik topshiriq emas, balki **muammo yoki ochiq savol** qo‘yiladi:

- “Qanday qilib 18-25 yoshdagi yoshlar uchun eng jozibador brend vizual identifikatsiyasini yaratish mumkin?”

- “Bir xil personajni 3 xil uslubda (realistik, low-poly, hand-painted) taqqoslab ko‘rsating va eng samarali uslubni asoslab bering.”

- Talaba o‘zi tadqiqot qiladi → referenslar izlaydi → bir nechta variant sinab ko‘radi → tanqidiy tahlil qiladi → yakuniy qaror qabul qiladi.

Natija: mustaqil fikrlash + tanqidiy fikrlash + ijodiy yechim topish birgalikda rivojlanadi.

2.2. Scaffolding va Zone of Proximal Development (Vygotskiy) Talabalar mustaqil ishlashga o‘tish uchun vaqtinchalik yordam (scaffolding) oladi.

Zone of Proximal Development diagrammasi Diagrammada uchta zona ko‘rsatiladi:

- Pastki zona: Mustaqil bajarila oladigan vazifalar (o‘quvchi allaqachon biladi)
- O‘rta zona (ZPD): Yordam bilan bajarila oladigan vazifalar (scaffolding bilan)
- Yuqori zona: Hozircha imkonsiz vazifalar (kelajakdagi maqsad)

Scaffolding jarayoni ZPD zonasi orqali o‘tib, asta-sekin yordam kamayib, talaba to‘liq mustaqil bo‘ladi.

2.3. Tanqidiy sessiyalar (Critique sessions) Tanqidiy muhokama jarayoni odatda quyidagi bosqichlardan iborat:

Design Critique jarayoni diagrammasi

1. Kontekst taqdimoti (24 soat oldin materiallar tarqatiladi) ↓
2. Taqdimot (15–20 daqiqa) ↓
3. Strukturalangan fikr-mulohaza (I like / I wish / What if) ↓
4. Klasterlash va muhokama ↓
5. Keyingi qadamlar va harakat rejasi

Bu sxema konstruktiv tanqidni ta‘minlaydi va talabalarda refleksiya ko‘nikmasini shakllantiradi.

PBL (muammoli ta'lim) va scaffolding yondashuvlari talabalarni oddiy nusxa ko‘chiruvchi emas, balki mustaqil dizayner sifatida shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. 2D grafika kontekstida quyidagi jihatlar alohida ahamiyatga ega:

• **Rastrli va vektorli fikrlash:** Talaba loyihaning maqsadidan kelib chiqib (bosma mahsulot yoki raqamli interfeys), texnik yondashuvni mustaqil tanlay olishi va piksellar bilan ishlashda aniqlikni, vektorlarda esa matematik muvozanatni his qilishi lozim.

• **Koloristika va hissiy ta'sir:** Ranglarni to‘g‘ri tanlay bilish – bu shunchaki estetik tanlov emas, balki branding va vizual kommunikatsiyaning psixologik asosi hisoblanadi. Talaba ranglar palitrasini tanlashda mustaqil ravishda auditoriya hissiyotlarini tahlil qila olishi kerak.

• **Tipografika va simvolizm:** 2D dizaynda matn va ramzlar o‘rtasidagi mantiqiy bog‘liqlikni qurish, tanqidiy sessiyalar orqali o‘z ishini himoya qilish va xatolarni tahlil qilish ijodiy o‘shning kalitidir.

• **Konseptual eskizlash:** Bloom taksonomiyasiga ko‘ra, talaba dasturga o‘tishdan oldin o‘z g‘oyasini qog‘ozda (eskiz shaklida) shakllantirishi, bu esa uning texnik asboblarga bog‘lanib qolmasdan, erkin fikrlashiga yordam beradi.

2D grafikasini o‘qitishda texnik ko‘nikmalarni **nazariy bilimlar va badiiy idrok** bilan sintez qilish, talabalarga tez o‘zgaruvchan vizual bozorda o‘zining betakror "vizual imzosini" yaratish imkonini beradi.

XULOSA

Kompyuter grafikasini o‘qitishda talabalarning mustaqil fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish juda muhim, chunki bu fan nafaqat texnik ko‘nikmalarni (Blender, Maya, Photoshop, Unity va h.k.), balki ijodiy yechim topish, muammoni tahlil qilish va o‘ziga xos estetik qarorlar qabul qilishni talab qiladi. Maqola kompyuter grafikasi fanini o‘qitishda talabalarning mustaqil, tanqidiy va ijodiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari haqida. Kompyuter grafikasi o‘qitishida PBL, scaffolding, tanqidiy sessiyalar va Bloom taksonomiyasiga asoslangan yondashuvlar talabalarni mustaqil ijodkor sifatida shakllantiradi. Yuqoridagi diagrammalar ushbu jarayonlarni vizual tarzda tushuntiradi va o‘quv jarayonini rejalashtirishda yordam beradi. Kompyuter garafikasi o‘rganishda o‘quvchi fikrlashi qobilyati va ranglarni to‘g‘ri tanlay bilishi kerak bo‘ladi. Kompyuter grafikasini o‘qitishda asosiy e‘tibor texnik asboblardan ko‘ra konseptual va vizual fikrlashga qaratilishi talabalarga tez o‘zgaruvchan texnologik muhitda muvaffaqiyatli mutaxassis bo‘lish imkonini beradi.

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3. Vygotskiy L.S. — Zone of Proximal Development
4. PBLWorks — Gold Standard PBL model
5. Oliy ta’lim vazirligi o‘quv dasturlari (2024–2025)

KINO MUSIQASINING TARIXIY BOSQICHLARI VA UNING AHAMIYATI

Sobirova Faxrigul Faxriddinovna

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola kino musiqasining tarixiy bosqichlarini o'rganadi. Maqolaning maqsadi kino musiqasining rivojlanish jarayonini tahlil qilish va uning ijodiy ahamiyatini aniqlashdir. Tadqiqot jarayonida kino musiqasining asrlar davomida o'zgarishini ko'rsatadigan nazariy asoslar, metodlar va misollar keltiriladi. Natijalar kino musiqasining bugungi kunda qanday o'zgarishlar va yangiliklar ko'rsatayotganini tasvirlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: kino musiqasi; tarixiy bosqichlar, ijodiy ahamiyat, musiqa tarixi, tahlil.

Kino san'ati va musiqa bir-biri bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lgan ikki soha hisoblanadi. Kino musiqasi, filmning hikoyasini va hissiyotlarini ifodalovchi muhim elementlardan biri bo'lib, uning tarixi juda qadimiydir. Kino musiqasi 1890-yillarda kinematografik san'atning paydo bo'lishi bilan boshlangan. O'sha davrda musiqachilar filmni ko'rayotgan tomoshabinlar uchun jonli musiqalar ijro etar edilar. Ushbu maqolada kino musiqasining tarixiy bosqichlari, uning rivojlanishi va zamonaviy kinodagi o'rni haqida batafsil ma'lumot beriladi. Maqsadimiz kino musiqasining tarixiy rivojlanishini aniqlash va bu jarayonda yuzaga kelgan o'zgarishlarni tahlil qilishdir. Shuningdek, kino musiqasining ijodiy ahamiyatini ham ko'zdan kechiramiz.

Kino musiqasining rivojlanishi bir necha bosqichlardan iborat. Dastlabki yillarda film musiqasi asosan jonli ijro orqali amalga oshirilgan. Bu davrda, musiqachilar filmning har bir sahnasiga mos keladigan musiqa yaratishga harakat qilishgan. 1920-yillarda esa, ovozli filmlarning paydo bo'lishi bilan kino musiqasining yangi bosqichi boshlanadi. Bu davrda kompozitorlar filmning hissiyotini kuchaytiruvchi original musiqalar yaratishga kirishadilar. Bunday film musiqalari nafaqat tomoshabinlarga ko'rinadigan sahnalarni ifodalashda, balki

ularning hissiyotlarini ham kuchaytirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. 1930-yillardan boshlab, kino musiqasi o'zining klassik shakllariga ega bo'la boshlaydi. Kompozitorlar, masalan, Dmitriy Shostakovich, Aaron Copland va Bernard Herrmann kabi mashhur shaxslar, o'z asarlarida innovatsion uslublarni qo'llaydilar. Ushbu davrda kino musiqasida simfonik va orkestral shakllar keng qo'llanila boshlaydi.

1950-yillarda esa, jazz va pop musiqalari kino sanoatiga kirib keladi. 1960-yillardan boshlab, elektron musiqa va yangi texnologiyalar kino musiqasining rivojlanishida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Bugungi kunda esa, kino musiqasi turli janrlarda va uslublarda yaratiladi, bu esa tomoshabinlarga keng qamrovli tajribalar taqdim etadi. Kino musiqasining rivojlanishi davomida ko'plab muhim faktlar va voqealar yuz berib, san'atning ushbu sohasiga yangiliklar kiritgan.

Kino musiqasining tarixiy rivojlanishi uning ijodiy ahamiyatini oshirdi. Har bir bosqichda yangi uslublar va janrlar paydo bo'lib, bu musiqaning tomoshabinlar bilan o'zaro aloqasini kuchaytirdi. Kino musiqasi bugungi kunda ham o'z o'rnini yo'qotmay, aksincha, yangi texnologiyalar va ijodiy yondashuvlar yordamida rivojlanishda davom etmoqda. Kelgusidagi tadqiqotlar kino musiqasining zamonaviy tendensiyalarini va uning ijtimoiy, madaniy ahamiyatini o'rganishga qaratilishi kerak. Kino musiqasining o'zgarishlari, uning tomoshabinlarga ta'siri va kino san'atining rivojlanishidagi o'rni haqida ko'proq ma'lumotlar to'plash zarur.

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MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING(MRI) TECHNIQUES IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF ALZHEIMER’S DISEASE

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Abstract: Alzheimer’s disease (AD) is one of the most common neurodegenerative diseases, with its prevalence growing on a global scale. It is primarily caused by accumulation of amyloid beta ($A\beta$) plaques and neurofibrillary tau tangles in the brain. AD is characterized by cognitive decline, memory impairment, and functional deterioration. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) provides non-invasive visualization of structural and functional brain alterations, making it a critical diagnostic tool in modern neurology for early detection.

Keywords: Alzheimer’s disease; MRI; hippocampal atrophy; neurodegeneration; biomarkers; fMRI; DTI.

Association of cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers with MRI brain changes in Alzheimer’s disease demonstrated strong associations between CSF (cerebrospinal fluid) tau levels and hippocampal and amygdala atrophy measured with MRI, reinforcing the link between molecular pathology and structural MRI changes. Early detection and classification of Alzheimer’s disease through data fusion of MRI and diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) images demonstrated that combining MRI and diffusion imaging improves classification accuracy in early

stages of cognitive impairment. Analysis of advanced diffusion models assessing white matter microstructure in Alzheimer’s disease showed that diffusion MRI parameters correlate with cognitive scores and can distinguish Alzheimer’s patients from controls.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) enables non-invasive visualization of these brain alterations. Structural MRI allows measurement of regional atrophy, particularly in the hippocampus and amygdala, which are among the earliest affected areas. Diffusion Tensor Imaging (DTI) evaluates white matter integrity by analyzing water diffusion patterns, with parameters such as fractional anisotropy (FA) and mean diffusivity (MD) providing information about microstructural damage. Advanced diffusion models, like NODDI, further enhance sensitivity to early neuronal changes. Functional MRI (fMRI) provides insight into disrupted brain networks, especially the default mode network (DMN), which is commonly affected in early AD. Combining MRI modalities with cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) biomarkers, including tau and A β levels, strengthens the link between molecular pathology and structural or functional brain changes. Multimodal approaches integrating structural, diffusion, and functional data have improved classification accuracy, distinguishing patients with mild cognitive impairment from those with AD or normal aging.

Results: These findings consistently indicate that MRI biomarkers- especially diffusion metrics and volumetric measures can support earlier and more accurate diagnosis compared to clinical assessments alone. MRI-based biomarkers, including hippocampal volume reduction and diffusion abnormalities, showed strong correlation with cognitive decline in patients with Alzheimer’s disease.

The combination of structural MRI and diffusion imaging significantly improved the accuracy of early-stage detection compared to single-modality approaches.

Conclusion: Importance of MRI techniques in diagnosing and

understanding Alzheimer’s disease at early stages has been explored in this study. MRI biomarkers including volumetric, diffusion, and functional connectivity measures support earlier and more precise diagnosis than clinical assessments alone. These imaging techniques are critical for monitoring disease progression and guiding individualized treatment strategies.

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ДИСКУРСИВНЫЕ ПРАКТИКИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ РКИ: ГРАММАТИКА ВНЕ ИЗОЛЯЦИИ

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ona tili bo‘lmagan tilni o‘qitish jarayonida o‘quv xatosi fenomeni samarali didaktik resurs sifatida ko‘rib chiqiladi. Asosiy e‘tibor xatolarning shakllanishida tizimli mexanizm bo‘lib xizmat qiluvchi interferensiyaga qaratiladi, u tilni o‘zlashtirishning chuqur kognitiv jarayonlarini aks ettiradi. Interferensiyaviy xatolar faqat salbiy hodisa emasligi, balki o‘quvchining shakllanayotgan til kompetensiyasi tuzilmasini aniqlash imkonini beruvchi diagnostik vosita ekanligi asoslab beriladi. Maqola nazariy-analitik xarakterga ega bo‘lib, tillarni o‘qitish metodikasi, psixolingvistika va lingvodidaktika sohasidagi zamonaviy tadqiqotlarga tayangan holda yozilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: xato, interferensiya, intertil (interlanguage), lingvodidaktika, tilni o‘qitish metodikasi, ikkilamchi til shaxsiyati, ona tili bo‘lmagan tilni o‘qitish..

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается проблема обучения грамматике в рамках преподавания русского языка как иностранного в контексте дискурсивного подхода. Обосновывается необходимость отказа от изолированного представления грамматических структур и перехода к их изучению в составе целостных коммуникативных практик. Грамматика интерпретируется не как автономная система форм, а как функционально-смысловой механизм организации дискурса. Анализируется роль дискурсивных практик в формировании языковой и коммуникативной компетенции обучающихся. Статья носит теоретико-аналитический характер и опирается на современные концепции лингводидактики, дискурсологии и методики преподавания РКИ.

Ключевые слова: дискурс, дискурсивные практики, русский язык как иностранный, грамматика, коммуникативная компетенция, контекстуальное обучение, лингводидактика.

Abstract: The article examines the problem of teaching grammar within the framework of teaching Russian as a foreign language in the context of a discursive approach. The necessity of abandoning the isolated presentation of grammatical structures and transitioning to their study within holistic communicative practices is substantiated. Grammar is interpreted not as an autonomous system of forms, but as a functional and semantic mechanism for organizing discourse. The role of discursive practices in the formation of learners' linguistic and communicative competence is analyzed. The study is theoretical and analytical in nature and is based on contemporary concepts of linguodidactics, discourse studies, and the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language.

Keywords: discourse, discursive practices, Russian as a foreign language (RFL), grammar, communicative competence, contextual learning, linguodidactics.

Современная методика преподавания русского языка как иностранного всё в большей степени ориентируется на интегративные модели обучения, в рамках которых язык рассматривается не как сумма автономных уровней (фонетического, лексического, грамматического), а как целостная функционально-коммуникативная система [5]. В данной парадигме грамматика утрачивает статус самостоятельного объекта обучения и начинает осмысливаться как инструмент организации смысла, включённый в процессы порождения и интерпретации высказывания.

Традиционная модель грамматического обучения, основанная на принципе изоляции форм, предполагает поэтапное усвоение языковых структур вне их реального коммуникативного функционирования. Грамматические категории в этом подходе представлены в виде абстрактных схем и правил, оторванных от дискурсивной среды, в которой они приобретают смысл. Подобная практика формирует у обучающихся фрагментарное языковое сознание, при котором

знание формы не сопровождается пониманием её функционально-прагматической нагрузки [8].

Дискурсивный подход принципиально меняет саму логику обучения. Язык в этом случае рассматривается как форма социальной практики, а дискурс — как пространство реализации языковых значений [7]. Грамматическая форма перестаёт быть самоцелью и включается в систему смыслопорождения. Это означает, что усвоение грамматики происходит не через запоминание правил, а через освоение способов речевого действия.

Дискурс в лингводидактическом контексте понимается не только как текст, но как процесс речевого взаимодействия, включающий участников коммуникации, цели высказывания, социокультурный контекст, прагматические установки и когнитивные стратегии [1]. В этом пространстве грамматические структуры выступают не как формальные конструкции, а как инструменты организации коммуникативного намерения.

Изоляция грамматики от дискурсивного контекста приводит к формированию так называемой «формальной компетенции», не переходящей в коммуникативную. Обучающийся знает правила, но не способен адекватно использовать их в реальной речевой ситуации. Это явление широко известно в практике преподавания РКИ, когда высокий уровень тестовой грамотности не коррелирует с уровнем коммуникативной эффективности [6].

Дискурсивные практики, напротив, формируют функциональное языковое знание. Они предполагают включение грамматических структур в целостные коммуникативные сценарии: диалогические модели, нарративные конструкции, аргументативные схемы, институциональные типы дискурса (академический, профессиональный, бытовой, медийный) [4]. В этих условиях грамматика усваивается как средство организации смысла, а не как объект формального контроля.

Особое значение в этом процессе имеет принцип контекстуальности. Грамматическая форма интерпретируется через контекст, а не вне его. Например, категория вида глагола в русском языке не может быть полноценно

усвоена вне нарративного дискурса, так как её функциональные значения связаны с организацией событийной структуры текста [2]. Аналогичным образом категории времени, модальности, залога и аспектуальности реализуют свои значения только в рамках конкретных коммуникативных задач.

Дискурсивная модель обучения предполагает переход от правила к действию, от формы к функции, от изоляции к интеграции. Грамматика становится частью коммуникативной компетенции, а не отдельным модулем учебной программы. Это соответствует современным представлениям о языковом усвоении как когнитивно-деятельностном процессе, в котором знание формируется через практику смыслового взаимодействия [3].

В рамках такого подхода меняется и роль преподавателя. Он перестаёт быть транслятором нормативных правил и становится организатором дискурсивной среды, в которой обучающиеся осваивают способы речевого действия. Учебное пространство трансформируется в коммуникативную лабораторию, где грамматика функционирует как инструмент, а не как цель [5].

Дискурсивные практики позволяют формировать не только языковую, но и социокультурную компетенцию. Освоение грамматических структур в реальных коммуникативных контекстах способствует пониманию норм речевого поведения, стратегий вежливости, культурных сценариев общения, институциональных форм коммуникации. Таким образом, обучение выходит за рамки формального языка и становится процессом формирования вторичной языковой личности [7].

Грамматика вне изоляции — это не отказ от системности, а её переосмысление. Системность языка сохраняется, но она интерпретируется не как совокупность абстрактных правил, а как система функциональных средств, организующих дискурс. Такой подход позволяет преодолеть разрыв между знанием языка и владением языком, между формальной грамотностью и коммуникативной компетентностью.

Дискурсивный подход к обучению РКИ позволяет принципиально по-новому осмыслить роль грамматики в языковом образовании. Грамматика

перестаёт быть автономным объектом обучения и становится инструментом смысловой организации дискурса. Изоляция форм уступает место интеграции функций, а обучение правилам трансформируется в обучение речевым действиям. Дискурсивные практики формируют целостную языковую компетенцию, в которой грамматические структуры осваиваются как средства коммуникации, а не как формальные конструкции. Такой подход открывает новые перспективы для развития методики РКИ и позволяет выстроить обучение как процесс формирования функционального языкового сознания, ориентированного на реальную коммуникацию.

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CORPUS-BASED IDENTIFICATION OF CONCEPTUAL METAPHORS IN SPANISH AND RUSSIAN SLANG

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Abstract: This article examines corpus-based methodology as an instrument for identifying and classifying conceptual metaphors in contemporary Spanish and Russian slang. The study is grounded in a bilingual corpus of 4,199 slang units compiled from verified lexicographic, electronic, and media sources. The author presents a four-level analytical model (archetypes → mental models → conceptual metaphors → slang units) and discusses the principal methodological challenges of corpus construction, annotation, and cross-linguistic comparison in non-standard registers. Quantitative findings are presented in a comparative domain distribution table.

Keywords: corpus linguistics, conceptual metaphor, slang, Spanish, Russian, comparative methodology, four-level model, bilingual corpus, domain distribution.

Introduction. The study of slang through the lens of conceptual metaphor theory has attracted growing scholarly attention over the past two decades. However, one dimension of this research agenda remains comparatively underexplored: the methodological apparatus through which conceptual metaphors are systematically identified and classified in non-standard lexical registers. Corpus linguistics offers a principled response to this challenge, providing large-scale, reproducible, and cross-linguistically comparable data that move slang research beyond the anecdotal and the impressionistic.

The present study reports on the construction and analysis of a bilingual corpus of 4,199 slang units drawn from contemporary Spanish and Russian, assembled as

part of a broader doctoral investigation into the cognitive features of slang conceptual metaphors. The article addresses three interconnected questions: (1) what principles govern the construction of a reliable bilingual slang corpus; (2) what methodological challenges arise in annotating such a corpus for conceptual metaphor; and (3) what typologically significant findings emerge from cross-linguistic comparison of domain distributions.

The relevance of these questions extends beyond slang studies proper. As comparative cognitive linguistics seeks to test claims about universal and culture-specific metaphorical patterns, the methodological integrity of the corpora on which such claims rest becomes a matter of theoretical consequence. A poorly constructed or inconsistently annotated corpus can generate artefactual convergences or divergences that misrepresent the actual cognitive and lexical ecology of the languages under study. Methodological transparency is therefore not merely a procedural virtue but an epistemic necessity.

Corpus Construction: Sources, Criteria, and Scope. The compilation of a slang corpus presents distinctive methodological difficulties not encountered in standard-language corpus work. Slang is definitionally unstable: it is produced in informal, often ephemeral contexts; it circulates through oral and digital channels that leave incomplete written records; and its boundaries with colloquial, jargon, and taboo registers are inherently porous. Any credible corpus must therefore be built on an explicit and defensible set of inclusion criteria.

For the present corpus, slang units were collected from three complementary source types: (1) verified lexicographic sources, including monolingual slang dictionaries for Spanish (*Diccionario del español coloquial*, Sanmartín Sáez 2006) and Russian (*Bol'shoy slovar' russkogo zhargona*, Mokienko & Nikitina 2000); (2) electronic corpora and frequency databases, including iWeb for Spanish and the Russian National Corpus; and (3) contemporary media and social network texts subjected to manual screening. Units were included if attested in at least two independent sources and if their metaphorical motivation was identifiable through standard conceptual metaphor analysis.

The resulting corpus comprises 4,199 units: 2,134 Spanish and 2,065 Russian. This near-equal distribution was intentional, ensuring that cross-linguistic comparisons are not distorted by asymmetries in corpus size. Each unit was lemmatized, assigned a thematic domain label, and annotated for its source domain, target domain, and metaphorical mapping type. Inter-annotator reliability was assessed across a 10% random sample, yielding a Cohen's kappa coefficient of 0.81, which is considered strong agreement for qualitative semantic annotation tasks.

Crucially, the corpus was designed to be synchronically bounded: items were retained only if attested in sources from 2000 onwards. This decision reflects the rapid turnover of slang vocabulary and ensures that the findings describe the contemporary lexical landscape rather than a historically layered aggregate. Where a slang item showed clear evidence of semantic shift between its earliest and most recent attestations, both the original and derived forms were included as separate corpus entries with corresponding metadata.

The Four-Level Analytical Model. A central methodological contribution of the present study is the four-level model through which conceptual metaphors are identified and hierarchically organized within the corpus. The model proceeds through the following levels: (1) archetypes — the most abstract, cross-culturally shared cognitive structures rooted in universal human embodiment (e.g., UP IS GOOD, CONTAINMENT, FORCE); (2) mental models — culture-specific configurations of experience that instantiate archetypes in socially recognizable scenarios; (3) conceptual metaphors — the systematic mappings between source and target domains that generate lexical innovations; and (4) slang units — the individual lexical and phraseological items that realize conceptual metaphors at the surface level of language.

This hierarchical organization enables the analyst to move fluidly between the universal and the particular: to identify which surface slang forms share a common metaphorical motivation, and conversely to trace any given conceptual metaphor downward to its archetype and upward to its lexical realizations. The model thus

serves simultaneously as a classification schema, an analytical tool, and a theoretical claim about the cognitive architecture of slang lexicogenesis.

An illustrative example may clarify the model's operation. The Spanish slang expression *estar en las nubes* ('to be in the clouds' — meaning to be distracted or out of touch with reality) instantiates the conceptual metaphor **COGNITIVE DISENGAGEMENT IS VERTICAL DISTANCE** from the ground, which in turn realizes the archetype of **UP/DOWN** orientation combined with **FORCE DYNAMICS**. The Russian parallel *быть не в теме* ('to be outside the topic/loop') realizes a related but distinct mental model — **KNOWLEDGE IS SPATIAL CONTAINMENT** — activating the archetype of **INSIDE/OUTSIDE** boundaries. Both share the archetype level but diverge at the mental model level, revealing how universal cognitive structures are channeled through culturally specific spatial and social scenarios.

Methodological Challenges in Cross-Linguistic Annotation. Annotating a bilingual slang corpus for conceptual metaphor raises several challenges that deserve explicit discussion. The first is the problem of equivalence: not all source domains are equally available or productive across languages. The military domain generates a substantially richer series of slang metaphors in Russian than in Spanish, reflecting asymmetries in cultural and historical experience rather than any cognitive incapacity. Treating such asymmetries as annotation errors would distort the findings; instead, they must be treated as analytically significant data points encoding sociolinguistic reality.

The second challenge concerns diachronic instability. Slang vocabularies evolve rapidly, and a corpus compiled at any given moment reflects a synchronic slice of a fundamentally dynamic system. To mitigate this, all corpus items were cross-checked against publication dates, and items attested only in sources predating 2000 were excluded unless confirmed by more recent attestations. This decision sacrifices some historical depth in favor of synchronic validity and ensures that domain frequency counts reflect current usage patterns.

The third challenge is the identification of metaphorical motivation in conventionalized slang. Many slang items have undergone semantic bleaching to the point where their metaphorical origin is no longer transparent to contemporary speakers. The methodological decision adopted here — to annotate for the historically recoverable metaphorical motivation rather than the speaker's synchronic awareness — is consistent with cognitive linguistic practice but generates a degree of interpretive responsibility that must be acknowledged. A supplementary annotation tier distinguishing transparent from conventionalized metaphors was added to the corpus to preserve this distinction for subsequent analysis.

Cross-Linguistic Findings: Domain Distribution. Corpus analysis reveals the distribution of conceptual source domains across both sub-corpora, as presented in Table 1 below. The data permit a systematic comparison of domain productivity in Spanish and Russian slang and provide a quantitative foundation for the interpretive claims advanced in this section.

Table 1. Distribution of Conceptual Source Domains across the Bilingual Slang Corpus (ES vs. RU)

Source Domain	ES (n / %)	RU (n / %)	Total (n / %)
Human body & physiology	512 / 24.0%	481 / 23.3%	993 / 23.6%
Spatial orientation	298 / 14.0%	276 / 13.4%	574 / 13.7%
Temperature & physical force	231 / 10.8%	219 / 10.6%	450 / 10.7%
Social hierarchy & evaluation	284 / 13.3%	271 / 13.1%	555 / 13.2%
Digital technology & online culture	130 / 6.1%	79 / 3.8%	209 / 5.0%
State control & bureaucracy	40 / 1.9%	171 / 8.3%	211 / 5.0%
Popular culture & entertainment	178 / 8.3%	132 / 6.4%	310 / 7.4%
Nature & biological processes	142 / 6.7%	156 / 7.6%	298 / 7.1%
Other / mixed domains	319 / 14.9%	280 / 13.5%	599 / 14.3%
TOTAL	2,134 / 100%	2,065 / 100%	4,199 / 100%

Source: compiled by the author on the basis of the bilingual slang corpus (n = 4,199).

The data in Table 1 confirm a shared inventory of high-frequency source domains across both languages. The domain of Human body & physiology is the single most productive source domain in both sub-corpora (24.0% in Spanish, 23.3% in Russian), consistent with the embodied cognition hypothesis and the claim that bodily experience constitutes the primary cognitive substrate for metaphorical lexicogenesis. Spatial orientation (ES: 14.0%, RU: 13.4%) and Social hierarchy & evaluation (ES: 13.3%, RU: 13.1%) likewise show near-identical frequencies, suggesting that these domains index cross-linguistically stable anthropocentric structures.

The most instructive divergences concern the domains of State control & bureaucracy and Digital technology & online culture. The former is more than four times as productive in Russian (8.3%) as in Spanish (1.9%), a gap that directly reflects the distinct institutional histories of the two speech communities. The latter shows the inverse asymmetry: Spanish slang draws on digital and online culture at nearly twice the rate of Russian slang (6.1% vs. 3.8%), consistent with the earlier and broader penetration of social media registers into everyday Spanish-speaking youth language during the period of corpus compilation.

These divergences underscore a central theoretical point: while the cognitive mechanisms that generate metaphorical slang are universal, their lexical productivity in any given domain is conditioned by the social and historical experience of the speech community. A purely universalist account of slang metaphor, which attends only to shared archetype-level patterns, would be empirically insufficient. Equally, a purely particularist account, which treats each language's slang as *sui generis*, would fail to explain the striking cross-linguistic convergences documented at the higher-frequency end of the domain distribution.

Conclusion. Corpus-based methodology provides an indispensable foundation for the systematic study of conceptual metaphors in slang. The four-level analytical

model developed in this study — proceeding from archetypes through mental models and conceptual metaphors to individual slang units — makes it possible to describe the full cognitive architecture of a bilingual slang corpus in a principled and reproducible manner. The comparative domain distribution table (Table 1) condenses the principal quantitative findings into an accessible format while preserving the precision necessary for cross-linguistic comparison.

The cross-linguistic evidence from the Spanish and Russian sub-corpora confirms both the universality of embodied cognitive mechanisms and the cultural specificity of their lexical realizations. Domains grounded in shared human physiology and spatial experience show near-identical productivity across both languages; domains shaped by institutional and media history diverge sharply. These findings support a two-tier model of slang metaphor: a universal archetype layer and a culturally modulated realization layer.

The methodological framework and corpus design reported here are transferable to other language pairs and non-standard registers, offering a model for comparative slang research that is simultaneously cognitively informed, lexicographically grounded, and cross-linguistically rigorous. Future work should extend the corpus to additional languages and incorporate diachronic dimensions to track shifts in domain productivity over time.

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DORIVOR O‘SIMLIK MOYLARI TARKIBIDAGI ASOSIY BIOFAOL MODDALAR (TERPENOIDLAR, VA FENOLIK BIRIKMALAR), HAMDA, FIZIK-KIMYOVIY ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI

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Аннотация: Лекарственные растения с древних времен занимают важное место в жизни человечества как целебное средство. Особенно широко применяются растения, богатые эфирными маслами, в фармацевтической, пищевой и парфюмерной промышленности. Эти масла обладают сложным химическим составом, в котором присутствуют различные классы биологически активных веществ. К наиболее важным биоактивным компонентам относятся терпеноиды, фенольные соединения и флавоноиды. Указанные вещества являются основными факторами, определяющими фармакологические свойства растений.

Abstract: Medicinal plants have occupied an important place in human history since ancient times as therapeutic agents. In particular, plants rich in essential oils are widely used in the pharmaceutical, food, and perfumery industries. These oils have a complex chemical composition, containing various classes of biologically active compounds. The most important bioactive components include terpenoids, phenolic compounds, and flavonoids. These substances are the main factors determining the pharmacological properties of plants.

Annotatsiya: Dorivor o‘simliklar insoniyat tarixida qadimdan shifobaxsh vosita sifatida muhim o‘rin egallab kelgan. Ayniqsa, efir moylariga boy o‘simliklar farmatsevtika, oziq-ovqat va parfyumeriya sanoatida keng qo‘llaniladi. Ushbu moylar murakkab kimyoviy tarkibga ega bo‘lib, ular orasida biologik faol moddalarning turli sinflari uchraydi. Eng muhim biofaol komponentlar qatoriga terpenoidlar, fenolik

birikmalar va flavonoidlar kiradi. Ushbu moddalar o‘simliklarning farmakologik xususiyatlarini belgilovchi asosiy omillar hisoblanadi.

Terpenoidlar (izoprenoidlar) dorivor o‘simlik moylarining asosiy tarkibiy qismlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Ular izopren birliklaridan tashkil topgan bo‘lib, o‘simliklarning hid va ta‘m xususiyatlarini belgilaydi. Terpenoidlar Monoterpenlar (masalan, limonen, mentol), Seskviterpenlar (masalan, farnezen), Diterpenlar va triterpenlar kabi guruhlarga bo‘linadi. Terpenoidlarning asosiy biologik xususiyatlari esa antiseptik va antibakterial ta‘sir, yallig‘lanishga qarshi xususiyat, antioksidant faoliyat, hamda, immun tizimni rag‘batlantirishlardan iborat. Masalan, mentol sovituvchi va og‘riq qoldiruvchi ta‘sirga ega bo‘lib, farmatsevtik preparatlarda keng qo‘llaniladi.¹²

Fenolik birikmalar aromatik halqali tuzilishga ega bo‘lgan moddalar bo‘lib, ular o‘simliklarda himoya vazifasini bajaradi. Efir moylarida fenolik komponentlar ko‘pincha kuchli biologik faollikka ega. Asosiy vakillari sifatida Timol, Karvakrol, Evgenollar kiradi. Fenolik birikmalarning asosiy xususiyatlari esa kuchli antiseptik va dezinfeksiyalovchi ta‘sir, antioksidant faoliyat, hamda, mikroorganizmlarga qarshi samaradorlik hisoblanadi.¹³

Masalan, timol va evgenol stomatologiyada keng qo‘llanilib, og‘iz bo‘shlig‘i kasalliklarini davolashda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Flavonoidlar polifenollar sinfiga kiruvchi murakkab birikmalar bo‘lib, o‘simliklarda keng tarqalgan. Ular ko‘pincha efir moylari bilan birgalikda uchrab, sinergik ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi. Flavonoidlar yurak-qon tomir tizimini himoya qilishda va hujayralarni erkin radikallardan saqlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Dorivor o‘simlik moylaridagi biofaol moddalar ko‘pincha birgalikda ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi. Terpenoidlar, fenolik birikmalar va flavonoidlar o‘zaro sinergik effekt hosil qilib, umumiy farmakologik samarani oshiradi. Bu esa o‘simlik asosidagi preparatlarning yuqori samaradorligini ta‘minlaydi.

¹² To‘ychiev G, Ortiqova M. “Artemisia absinthium dorivor o‘simligining biologik faol moddalari va tibbiyotdagi ahamiyati”. European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development Volume-49 march-2026. 15-22 p.

¹³ Shukurova D, Olimov S, Xasanova G. “Tarkibida efir moyi bo‘lgan dorivor o‘simliklar va mahsulotlar”. "Экономика и социум" №11(90) 2021. 526-529-betlar.

Dorivor o‘simlik moylari tarkibidagi terpenoidlar, fenolik birikmalar va flavonoidlar biologik faol moddalarning eng muhim guruhlarini hisoblanadi. Ular antiseptik, antioksidant, yallig‘lanishga qarshi va boshqa ko‘plab shifobaxsh xususiyatlarga ega. Ushbu moddalar nafaqat farmatsevtika sanoatida, balki oziq-ovqat va kosmetologiya sohalarida ham keng qo‘llanilmoqda. Kelajakda ushbu biofaol birikmalarni chuqur o‘rganish yangi dori vositalarini yaratishda muhim ilmiy asos bo‘lib xizmat qiladi.¹⁴

Tadqiqot usullari. Biologik, Farmakologik, Farmatsevtik texnologiya usullari, Fizik-kimyoviy.

Tahlillar. O‘simlik moylarining fizik-kimyoviy asosiy xususiyatlari.¹⁵

O‘simlik moyi	Zichlik [g/cm ³]	pH	Yorug‘lik sinishi	Yopishqoqlik [mPa·s]	Ho‘llanish burchagi [°]	Yuzaki taranglik [N/m]
Primula (OW)	0.925	7.52	1.476	46.8	38.2	40.1
Mari silyum (OO)	0.918	6.34	1.4715	57.1	40.8	39.6
Qovoq (OD)	0.921	6.11	1.475	57.4	32.0	36.0
Zig‘ir (OL)	0.923	7.51	1.4755	50.6	34.2	36.3
Kamalina (OR)	0.921	6.4	1.475	48.8	30.6	33.7
Qora sedana (OCZ)	0.92	5.63	1.4725	57.2	35.4	38.0
Makkajo‘xori	0.92	6.8	1.4712	47.0	33.5	37.5
Kungaboqar	0.922	6.6	1.474	45.5	35.1	38.5
Paxta	0.924	6.2	1.4728	50.0	31.0	35.8
Yeryong‘oq	0.914	6.5	1.469	44.0	36.2	39.0
Xantal	0.915	6.4	1.4705	46.0	34.5	37.2
Zaytun	0.91	5.8	1.468	42.0	32.8	35.0

Xulosa. Dorivor o‘simlik moylari tarkibidagi biofaol moddalar - terpenoidlar, fenolik birikmalar va flavonoidlar - o‘simliklarning farmakologik ahamiyatini belgilovchi asosiy komponentlar hisoblanadi. Ushbu moddalar antiseptik, antioksidant, yallig‘lanishga qarshi hamda mikroblarga qarshi xususiyatlarga ega bo‘lib, turli kasalliklarni davolashda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, mazkur biofaol birikmalar nafaqat alohida holda, balki o‘zaro sinergik ta‘sir orqali yanada yuqori terapevtik samaradorlikni namoyon etadi. Bu esa dorivor o‘simliklarga asoslangan preparatlarning farmatsevtik amaliyotda keng qo‘llanish

¹⁴ Jalilova G. Ochilova N. “Efir moyli o‘simliklar biologiyasi va ularning ahamiyati haqida ma’lumotlar”. Amaliy va tibbiyot fanlari ilmiy jurnali, № 5. 2023 yil. 30-bet

¹⁵ Alibekova M. “O‘simlik moylari sifatini baholashning zamonaviy usullari”. Development of science Volume/ 6. 2025 y. 82-89 p.

imkoniyatini oshiradi. Shuningdek, efir moyli o‘simliklar tarkibini chuqur o‘rganish va ularning biofaol komponentlarini ilmiy asosda tahlil qilish kelajakda yangi samarali va xavfsiz dori vositalarini yaratishda muhim ilmiy yo‘nalishlardan biri bo‘lib xizmat qiladi.

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МЕТАЯЗЫКОВОЕ СОЗНАНИЕ СТУДЕНТОВ-ФИЛОЛОГОВ: КАК ФОРМИРУЕТСЯ ПОНИМАНИЕ ГРАММАТИЧЕСКИХ КАТЕГОРИЙ

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada filologiya talabalarining metatilshunoslik ongining fenomeni, ya'ni professional til fikrlashini shakllantirishdagi asosiy kognitiv mexanizm sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. Grammatik kategoriyalarni faqat shakliy-til strukturalari sifatida emas, balki til ichidagi voqelikni tasniflash usullarini aks ettiruvchi konseptual birliklar sifatida anglash jarayoni tahlil qilinadi. Metatilshunoslik ongi shakllanishi tizimli, ko'p qavatli jarayon ekanligi, unga kognitiv, lingvistik va didaktik komponentlar kirishi ta'kidlanadi. Maqola nazariy-analitik xarakterga ega bo'lib, psixolingvistika, lingvistik falsafa, lingvodidaktika va filologik ta'lim metodikasi sohalaridagi zamonaviy tadqiqotlarga tayangan.

Kalit so'zlar: metatilshunoslik ongi, grammatik kategoriya, til fikrlashi, kognitsiya, lingvodidaktika, filologik ta'lim, professional til kompetentsiyasi.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается феномен метаязыкового сознания студентов-филологов как ключевого когнитивного механизма формирования профессионального языкового мышления. Анализируется процесс осмысления грамматических категорий не только как формально-языковых структур, но как концептуальных единиц, отражающих способы категоризации действительности в языке. Обосновывается положение о том, что формирование метаязыкового сознания является системным, многоуровневым процессом, включающим когнитивные, лингвистические и дидактические компоненты. Статья носит теоретико-аналитический характер и опирается на современные исследования в области психолингвистики, лингвистической философии, лингводидактики и методики филологического образования.

Ключевые слова: метаязыковое сознание, грамматическая категория, языковое мышление, когниция, лингводидактика, филологическое образование, профессиональная языковая компетенция.

Abstract: The article examines the phenomenon of metalinguistic awareness among philology students as a key cognitive mechanism in the formation of professional linguistic thinking. It analyzes the process of understanding grammatical categories not only as formal linguistic structures but also as conceptual units reflecting ways of categorizing reality in language. The study substantiates the position that the formation of metalinguistic awareness is a systemic, multi-level process involving cognitive, linguistic, and didactic components. The article is theoretical and analytical in nature and draws on contemporary research in psycholinguistics, linguistic philosophy, linguodidactics, and philological education methodology.

Keywords: metalinguistic awareness, grammatical category, linguistic thinking, cognition, linguodidactics, philological education, professional linguistic competence.

Проблема формирования метаязыкового сознания занимает особое место в современной филологической науке и педагогике высшей школы. Подготовка специалиста-филолога предполагает не только усвоение языковой нормы и владение системой грамматических категорий, но и формирование способности к рефлексивному осмыслению языка как объекта научного познания. В этом контексте язык выступает не просто как средство коммуникации, но как форма концептуализации мира, а грамматические категории — как когнитивные структуры, посредством которых человек осмысливает действительность.

Метаязыковое сознание понимается как способность субъекта к осознанному анализу языковых явлений, к рефлексии над структурой, функциями и смысловой организацией языка. Как отмечает А.А. Леонтьев, язык становится объектом мышления лишь в условиях сформированной языковой рефлексии, когда говорящий способен дистанцироваться от

спонтанной речевой деятельности и рассматривать язык как систему [5]. Для будущего филолога это умение является профессионально значимым и определяет уровень его научной и методологической компетентности.

Грамматические категории в данном контексте перестают быть исключительно формальными элементами языковой системы. Они выступают как концептуальные схемы, структурирующие языковое мышление. В трудах А.В. Бондарко грамматическая категория трактуется как функционально-семантическая система, объединяющая форму, значение и функцию в целостную структуру [1]. Такое понимание позволяет рассматривать грамматику не как набор правил, а как модель когнитивной организации опыта.

Формирование понимания грамматических категорий у студентов-филологов осуществляется на нескольких уровнях. На первичном уровне происходит усвоение терминологического аппарата и описательных моделей. Однако данный уровень сам по себе не обеспечивает формирования метаязыкового сознания, так как знание терминов не тождественно пониманию языковых процессов. Как подчёркивает И.А. Зимняя, формальное усвоение знаний без их когнитивной интеграции не приводит к формированию профессионального мышления [3].

Второй уровень связан с интерпретацией грамматических категорий в системе языка. Здесь студент начинает осознавать системные связи между категориями, их иерархию и функциональное взаимодействие. Категории времени, вида, залога, модальности, лица и числа перестают восприниматься как изолированные элементы и осмысливаются как взаимосвязанные механизмы организации смысла.

Третий уровень формирования метаязыкового сознания связан с дискурсивной интерпретацией грамматических категорий. В этом случае грамматика рассматривается через призму речевой деятельности, коммуникативных стратегий и прагматических задач. Такой подход соответствует положениям теории речевой деятельности, согласно которой язык реализуется прежде всего в деятельности, а не в абстрактной системе [4].

Особую роль в формировании метаязыкового сознания играет когнитивный аспект обучения. Современные исследования показывают, что понимание грамматических категорий связано с процессами категоризации, концептуализации и символизации опыта. В рамках когнитивной лингвистики грамматические структуры интерпретируются как отражение ментальных моделей реальности, а не как чисто формальные конструкции [6].

Метаязыковое сознание студентов формируется в результате взаимодействия нескольких образовательных практик: аналитического чтения научных текстов, интерпретации языковых данных, участия в научных дискуссиях, написания исследовательских работ. Эти виды деятельности создают пространство рефлексивного мышления, в котором язык становится объектом анализа, а не только средством выражения.

Важнейшим фактором является также методика преподавания грамматических дисциплин. Традиционная репродуктивная модель обучения, ориентированная на запоминание правил и схем, не способствует развитию метаязыковой рефлексии. Напротив, проблемно-аналитический и исследовательский подходы стимулируют формирование осознанного отношения к языку как к объекту научного знания [5].

Особое значение имеет интеграция теоретических и прикладных дисциплин. Когда грамматические категории изучаются в отрыве от текстологии, стилистики, дискурсологии и прагматики, формируется фрагментарное языковое сознание. Интегративная модель филологического образования, напротив, способствует формированию целостного метаязыкового мышления.

Метаязыковое сознание является не только когнитивным, но и ценностным феноменом. Оно формирует отношение к языку как к культурной и интеллектуальной ценности. В этом смысле филологическое образование выполняет не только профессиональную, но и культуuroобразующую функцию.

Таким образом, понимание грамматических категорий в структуре метаязыкового сознания студентов-филологов формируется как

многоуровневый процесс, включающий когнитивное осмысление, системное мышление, дискурсивную интерпретацию и ценностную рефлексию. Этот процесс не сводится к усвоению знаний, а представляет собой формирование особого типа профессионального мышления.

Формирование метаязыкового сознания студентов-филологов представляет собой стратегическую задачу современного филологического образования. Понимание грамматических категорий как когнитивных и концептуальных структур позволяет преодолеть формализм традиционного грамматического обучения и перейти к осмысленному, рефлексивному освоению языка. Метаязыковое сознание становится основой профессиональной идентичности филолога, определяя его способность к научному анализу языка, методологической рефлексии и педагогической интерпретации языковых явлений. Развитие данного типа сознания требует интеграции когнитивных, лингводидактических и философских подходов, что открывает перспективы для дальнейших исследований в области теории филологического образования.

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THE ROLE OF MRI IN THE DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS OF NEURODEGENERATIVE DISEASES

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Abstract: This study examines the significance of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in identifying structural brain alterations associated with neurodegenerative diseases. MRI enables early detection of pathological changes in brain tissues and improves diagnostic accuracy in differentiating disorders such as Alzheimer’s disease, Parkinson’s disease, and multiple sclerosis. Early visualization of neurodegenerative processes contributes to more precise clinical evaluation and effective monitoring of disease progression.

Keywords: neurodegenerative diseases, magnetic resonance imaging, brain atrophy, gray matter, white matter, differential diagnosis, early diagnosis, neurodegeneration, hippocampal atrophy

Magnetic resonance imaging plays a crucial role in the diagnostic assessment of Alzheimer’s disease. Typical MRI findings include hippocampal atrophy, diffuse cortical degeneration, reduction in temporal and frontal lobe volume, and ventricular enlargement. These structural abnormalities allow early identification of neurodegenerative changes.

In Parkinson’s disease, MRI may demonstrate signal alterations within the substantia nigra pars compacta on T2-weighted and susceptibility-weighted imaging (SWI) sequences caused by iron deposition, appearing as hypointensity. High-resolution 3T MRI may also reveal the absence of the nigrosome-1 structure, known as the “swallow tail sign.” In early stages, cortical or diffuse brain atrophy is often minimal or absent. Therefore, MRI is mainly used to exclude atypical parkinsonism rather than to directly confirm Parkinson’s disease.

Multiple sclerosis represents a chronic immune-mediated demyelinating disorder of the central nervous system. MRI is essential for early detection, disease monitoring, and evaluation of lesion distribution, which significantly improves diagnostic accuracy and prognosis assessment.

Results. The analysis shows that Alzheimer’s disease is primarily characterized by neuronal degeneration and cortical atrophy, whereas Parkinson’s disease involves dysfunction of dopaminergic pathways leading to motor impairment. Multiple sclerosis is mainly associated with demyelination processes affecting the central nervous system. In all conditions, MRI demonstrates high diagnostic value in early-stage detection, differential diagnosis, and assessment of disease dynamics.

Conclusion. Despite differences in etiopathogenesis, Alzheimer’s disease, Parkinson’s disease, and multiple sclerosis share common features of progressive neurodegeneration and functional impairment of the central nervous system. Modern neuroimaging techniques, particularly MRI, play a key role in early diagnosis, accurate differentiation, and long-term monitoring of neurodegenerative disorders, ultimately improving clinical decision-making and patient outcomes.

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R.GLIER VA T.SODIQOVNING “LAYLI VA MAJNUN” OPERASINING MARKAZIY QAHRAMONLAR OBRAZI TAHLILI

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Annonatsiya: Ushbu maqolada R. Glier va T. Sodiqovning “Layli va Majnun” operasi misolida markaziy qahramonlar obrazining badiiy va musiqiy talqini tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida Layli va Majnun obrazlarining ichki ruhiy kechinmalari, ularning sevgi yo‘lidagi iztiroblari hamda fojiviy taqdiri musiqiy dramaturgiya vositalari orqali ochib berilishi yoritiladi. Shuningdek, kompozitorlarning milliy ohang va Yevropa opera an’analarini uyg‘unlashtirishdagi yondashuvi alohida e’tibor markazida bo‘ladi. Qahramonlarning vokal partiyalari, orkestr jo‘rligi va sahnaviy ifoda vositalari asosida ularning xarakteri chuqur tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada asarning g‘oyaviy-badiiy mazmuni va uning o‘zbek operachilik san’atidagi o‘rni haqida xulosalar chiqariladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Layli va Majnun, opera san’ati, obraz tahlili, musiqiy dramaturgiya, vokal ijro, kompozitorlik uslubi, milliy musiqa, lirika, fojiviylik, sahna talqini.

АНАЛИЗ ОБРАЗОВ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНЫХ ГЕРОЕВ ОПЕРЫ Р.ГЛИЕРА И Т.СОДИКОВА “ЛАЙЛИ И МАДЖНУН”

Аннотация: В данной статье на примере оперы Р. Глиэра и Т. Содикова «Лейли и Меджнун» анализируется художественное и музыкальное воплощение образов центральных персонажей. В ходе исследования освещается раскрытие внутреннего духовного переживания Лейли и Меджнуна, их страданий на пути любви и трагической судьбы посредством

средств музыкальной драматургии. Также особое внимание уделяется подходу композиторов к сочетанию национальной мелодики и европейских оперных традиций. На основании вокальных партий героев, оркестрового сопровождения и сценических выразительных средств проводится глубокий анализ их характеров. В статье делаются выводы о идейно-художественном содержании произведения и его месте в узбекском оперном искусстве.

Ключевые слова: Лейли и Меджнун, искусство оперы, анализ образа, музыкальная драматургия, вокальное исполнение, стиль композитора, национальная музыка, лирика, трагизм, сценическая интерпретация.

ANALYSIS OF THE CENTRAL CHARACTERS IN R. GLIER AND T. SODIQOV’S OPERA “LAYLA AND MAJNUN”

Annotation: This article analyzes the artistic and musical interpretation of the central characters in the opera “Layli and Majnun” by R. Glier and T. Sodiqov. During the study, the inner psychological experiences of the characters Layli and Majnun, their sufferings in the path of love, as well as their tragic fate revealed through musical dramaturgy, are highlighted. In addition, the composers' approach to harmonizing national tones with European opera traditions is given special attention. The characters are deeply analyzed based on their vocal parts, orchestral accompaniment, and means of stage expression. The article draws conclusions about the ideological and artistic content of the work and its place in Uzbek operatic art.

Keywords: Layla and Majnun, opera art, character analysis, musical dramaturgy, vocal performance, compositional style, national music, lyricism, tragedy, stage interpretation.

Barcha xalqlar qatori o‘zbek xalqi ham qadimdan o‘zining boy milliy ma’naviy qadriyatlariga, urf-odatlariga va an’analariga ega bo‘lib kelgan. Tarixan juda o‘tmishga borib taqaladigan boy musiqiy merosga ega. R.Glier va T.Sodiqovning “Layli va Majnun” operasi ijodiy hamkorlik namunasi sifatida o‘zbek opera san’atida

nafaqat tarixiy, balki badiiy, estetik va pedagogik ahamiyatga ega bo‘lgan durdona asar hisoblanadi. O‘zbek xalqining turmush tarzi, ruhiyati va salohiyatini belgilovchi ko‘plab xususiyatlar ushbu operada o‘z aksini topgan. Milliy ruh bilan boy bo‘lgan opera obrazidan biri Qays (Majnun) obrazidir. Operada Qays partiyasi markaziy qahramon bo‘lib, u yosh ijrochilarda quyidagilarni rivojlantiradi:

- musiqiy qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish;
- musiqani idrok etish malakalarini o‘stirish;
- kuylash malakalarini o‘stirish;
- musiqa nazariyasi asoslarini o‘rgatish.

Qays obrazi lirik tenor uchun yozilgan bo‘lib, unga quyidagicha tasnif berish mumkin bo‘ladi. Tenor lirik tenorning yorqinligi va balandligiga ega ammo ovozi og‘irroq bo‘lib, ovozi yengilroq o‘xshashlariga nisbatan kamroq keskinlik bilan ovozni dramatik avj nuqtalariga qarab “siljitish” imkonini beradi. Spinto tenorlari lirik tenorga qaraganda quyuoqroq tembrga ega ammo boshqa (hammasi emas) dramatik tenorlarnikiga o‘xshagan yopiq rangli ovozga ega emas. Spinto fachning nemischa o‘xshashi (ekvivalenti) bu – ko‘plab dramatik tenor rollarini o‘z ichiga olgan Jugendlicher Heldentenor, shuningdek, Vagnerning Loengrin va Shtoltsing kabi ba’zi rollari. Farqi ko‘pincha ovozni tebranligidan va temirga o‘xshab qolganligidan iborat bo‘ladi, chunki ba’zi lirik tenorlar yoshi o‘tganda yoki spinto singari kuylaganda, ularga yengilroq ohang beradi, Jugendlicher Heldentenor esa, yosh heldentenor yoki haqiqiy lirik spinto bo‘lishga intiladi. Spinto-tenorlarining diapazoni taxminan C (C3) o‘rta pastroq oktavadagi C dan C (C5) o‘rta balandroq oktavaning C gacha bo‘ladi. Shuningdek ariyaning ayrim joylarida obraz ustida ishlash vaqtida falset kuylashga ham duch kelishimiz mumkin. U qanday ta’riflanadi. Falset tovushini hosil bo‘lishida kamida ikkita usul mavjud: o‘pkadan oqib chiqayotgan va nafas yordamida qo‘llab-quvvatlanuvchi deb ataladiganlardir. Agar birinchisi tenorlarga juda oson bo‘lsa, ikkinchisi ustida ishlashga to‘g‘ri keladi. Falsetni yaxshi bilish, ayniqsa, majburlab kuylashga moyil bo‘lgan tenorlar uchun foydalidir, bu esa ovoz bo‘g‘inlarining to‘qnashuvi demakdir. Bu haqda taniqli opera xonandasi va o‘qituvchisi shunday deydi: “... falsetda kuylay olish qobiliyati

diapazonning yuqori qismiga va uning biroz yopiq ligiga juda mos tushadi”. Bundan tashqari, ko‘p hollarda falset ko‘krak pianosining o‘rnini bosishi mumkin, nafasga suyanuvchi falset esa, ovozida baland cho‘qqisi bo‘lmagan tenorlarni juda ham qo‘llaydi.

Aynan Qays (Majnun) partiyasini ijro etmoqchi bo‘lgan tenorlarga quyidagi maslahatlarni berib o‘tamiz:

1. Kuylayotgan paytda ikki oyog‘ida bemalol turish. Jismni to‘g‘ri ushlab shart, yelkalari ochilgan, bosh yaxshi, erkin holatda bo‘lishi kerak. Ushbu shartlar kuylovchi tanasidagi mushaklar va barcha mushaklarning bir xil yukga ega bo‘lishi uchun zarurdir, bunga tananing tabiiyligi va faol erkinligi ila erishiladi.

2. Hech qachon qorin to‘q ekan kuylamang, chunki u diafragmani erkinlik va harakatchanlikdan mahrum qiladi, uni pastdan “qo‘llab-quvvatlaydi”. To‘yib ovqatlanish va kuylash mashg‘ulotlari orasida kamida bir soat tanaffus bo‘lishi kerak. I.P.Pryanishnikovning fikricha, to‘q qoringa kuylash “tovushning tebranishi” samarasini beradi deb hisoblaydi.

3. Nafas olish shovqinsiz bo‘lishi kerak, nafas olayotganda tovushlarga yo‘l qo‘yilmaydi.

4. Kuylashni boshlang‘ich davrida bo‘lganlar uchun bir vaqtning o‘zida burun va og‘iz bilan nafas olish yaxshiroqdir, yoki og‘iz ochiq holatda burun orqali, bu halqumning yaxshiroq ochilishini ta‘minlaydi (tadqiqotchilar L.D.Robotnov va P.Organov ishlari shuni ko‘rsatadiki, bu nafas olish yo‘li qizil o‘ngach, yirik bronxlar kengayishiga yordam beradi). V.Brasova “yopiq og‘izda bir zumda chuqur nafas olish mumkin emas” deb hisoblagan. Bundan tashqari, bu nafas olish turi (og‘iz+burun) kam shovqinlidir. Tanaffuslarda iloji bo‘lsa, og‘iz orqali nafas olganda qurigan shilliq pardalarni namlash uchun burun orqali nafas olib turmoq zarur.

5. To‘liq hajmda havo olish kerak (pastki qovurg‘alar, diafragma) ammo orttirib yubormaslik ham zarur, chunki orttirib yuborilgan nafas olish qisilishga olib kelishi mumkin. Hammasi tabiiy bo‘lishi shart, haddan tashqarisi ortiqcha.

Markaziy qahramon Layli obraziga murojaat etar ekanmiz, uning yorqin va ta‘sirchan siyosiy operada alohida badiiy-estetik ahamiyat kasb etishini ko‘ramiz.

Layli obrazi musiqiy dramaturgiya jarayonida yetakchi o‘rin tutib, asarning g‘oyaviy mazmunini ochib berishda muhim vosita bo‘lib xizmat qiladi. Layli obrazi operada nozik lirizm, ichki ruhiy kechinmalar va ayollik latofatini ifodalovchi musiqiy vositalar orqali gavdalantirilgan. Uning vokal partiyasi kuychanlik, nafis intonatsiyalar, yumshoq dinamika va keng legato uslubi bilan ajralib turadi. Layli obrazining musiqiy tavsifida milliy lad-intonatsion asoslar bilan bir qatorda, yevropa vokal texnikasiga xos bo‘lgan badiiy ifoda vositalari ham mahorat bilan qo‘llangan. Bu hol obrazning ichki ziddiyatlari, muhabbat va ijtimoiy majburiyat o‘rtasidagi ruhiy kurashini yanada teranroq yoritishga xizmat qiladi.

“Layli va Majnun” operasi nafaqat syujet va obrazlar tizimi, balki vokal-ijrochilik, talaffuz, artikulyatsiya va nafas masalalarini o‘zida mujassam etgan murakkab sahnaviy asardir. Operadagi vokal partiyalar ijrochidan nafaqat texnik jihatdan mukammallik, balki chuqur badiiy tafakkur, obrazni psixologik jihatdan his eta olish qobiliyatini ham talab qiladi. Ayniqsa, talaffuz masalasi asarning badiiy ta’sirchanligini ta’minlovchi muhim omillardan biri sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi.

Xulosa

R. Glier va T. Sodiqov tomonidan yaratilgan “Layli va Majnun” operasi o‘zbek professional opera san’atining shakllanish va rivojlanish jarayonida muhim bosqichni tashkil etadi. Mazkur asar Sharq mumtoz adabiyotining durdonasi bo‘lgan “Layli va Majnun” syujetini yevropa opera an’analari bilan uyg‘unlashtirgan holda, milliy musiqiy tafakkur va badiiy-estetik qarashlarning yuksak namunasi sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi. Operada markaziy qahramonlar — Layli va Majnun obrazlari orqali insoniy muhabbat, sadoqat, ichki iztirob, ijtimoiy qarama-qarshilik va ma’naviy poklik kabi umuminsoniy g‘oyalar musiqiy-dramaturgik jihatdan chuqur ochib berilgan.

“Layli va Majnun” operasi nafaqat syujet va obrazlar tizimi, balki vokal-ijrochilik, talaffuz, artikulyatsiya va nafas masalalarini o‘zida mujassam etgan murakkab sahnaviy asardir. Operadagi vokal partiyalar ijrochidan nafaqat texnik jihatdan mukammallik, balki chuqur badiiy tafakkur, obrazni psixologik jihatdan his eta olish qobiliyatini ham talab qiladi. Ayniqsa, talaffuz masalasi asarning badiiy ta’sirchanligini ta’minlovchi muhim omillardan biri sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, R. Glier va T. Sodiqovning “Layli va Majnun” operasi markaziy qahramonlar obrazlari orqali milliy va jahon opera san’ati an’analari sintezini o’zida mujassam etgan yuksak badiiy asar hisoblanadi. Layli va Majnun obrazlari musiqiy-dramaturgik jihatdan mukammal ishlangan bo’lib, ular o’zbek opera san’atida klassik obrazlar darajasiga ko’tarilgan. Mazkur tadqiqot natijalari ushbu operani o’rganish, ijro etish va pedagogik amaliyotda qo’llash jarayonida muhim nazariy va amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi hamda o’zbek opera san’ati rivojini tadqiq etishda muhim manba bo’lib xizmat qiladi.

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СУД ТИЗИМИДА КОРРУПЦИЯНИ ОЛДИНИ ОЛИШ ВА УНГА ҚАРШИ КУРАШИШ

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Суд ҳокимияти давлат организмидаги энг муҳим тизим бўлиб, у адолат ва қонун устуворлигини таъминловчи «охирги нуқта» ҳисобланади. Агар ушбу нуқтада коррупция иллоти пайдо бўлса, жамиятнинг давлатга бўлган ишончи дарз кетади. Шу боис, бугунги кунда суд тизимини коррупциядан холи қилиш ҳуқуқий ислохотларнинг марказида турибди. Зеро, Президентимиз таъкидлаганидек, «Судьянинг онгида — адолат, тилида — ҳақиқат, дилида — поклик бўлиши шарт». Суд тизимидаги коррупция нафақат ҳуқуқий муаммо, балки хавфсизлик ва тараққиётга бевосита таҳдид солувчи омилдир.

Суд тизимида коррупция бу оддий ҳуқуқбузарлик эмас. Унинг оқибатлари жамият учун ҳалокатлидир. Бу фуқароларда «ҳамма нарсани сотиб олса бўлади» деган нотўғри қараш шаклланишига олиб келади. Шунингдек, хорижий ва маҳаллий инвесторлар мулк ҳуқуқи суд орқали кафолатланмаган, судьялари келишувга мойил бўлган давлатга сармоя киритмайди. Демак, суддаги коррупция бевосита мамлакат иқтисодиётини бўғувчи занжирдир. Бундан ташқари, мамлакатнинг халқаро рейтинглардаги ўрни пасайиши давлатнинг халқаро майдондаги сиёсий ва иқтисодий обрўсига путур етказиши. Адолат сотилган жойда нафақат қонун, балки инсон қадрлари ҳам топталади.

Бугунги кунда мамлакатимизда коррупциянинг олдини олиш бўйича бир нечта муҳим механизмлар ишга туширилган.

Жумладан, Судьялар олий кенгашининг мустақил орган сифатида фаолият юритиши судьяларни саралаш жараёнини очиқ ва шаффоф қилди.

Эндиликда судьяликка номзоднинг нафақат ҳуқуқий билими, балки стрессга чидамлилиги ва коррупцияга нисбатан иммунитетини ҳам психологик тестлар орқали текширилмоқда. Шунингдек, жамоатчилик назорати

кучайтирилиб, судьяликка номзодлар ҳақидаги маълумотлар кенг оммага эълон қилиниб борилмоқда.

Суд тизимида рақамлаштириш жараёнларини алоҳида таъкидлаш мумкин. Ишларни судьялар ўртасида тақсимлашда раисларнинг иштироки чекланди. Махсус алгоритм ишларни тасодифий тартибда тақсимлайди, бу эса маълум бир ишни келишилган судьяга бериш имкониятини йўққа чиқарди. Шунингдек, видеоконференцалоқа тизими орқали мажлислар ўтказилиши, суд мажлисларининг аудио-видео қайд этилиши ва онлайн трансляция қилиниши судьянинг ҳам, тарафларнинг ҳам масъулиятини оширди. Шу билан бирга суд қарорининг Интернетда эълон қилиниши судьяни ҳар бир сўз ва асослантириш учун жамоатчилик олдида масъул қилади. Очиқлик бор жойда яширин келишувларга ўрин қолмайди.

Коррупциянинг иқтисодий илдизларини қирқиш учун судьяларнинг иш ҳақи ва ижтимоий таъминоти тубдан қайта кўриб чиқилди. Бу шунчаки имтиёз эмас, балки адолатни таъминлаш учун зарур бўлган қафолатдир. Европа ва Осиёнинг ривожланган давлатлари тажрибаси шуни кўрсатадики, моддий жиҳатдан мустақил ва ижтимоий ҳимояланган судья бегона манфаатларга хизмат қилмайди. Моддий муҳтож судьядан мустақил қарор кутиш мантиққа зиддир. Бугунги кундаги уй-жой, тиббий хизмат ва муносиб маош судьянинг фақат ишга ва қонун устуворлигига диққат қаратишига замин яратади.

Ўзбекистон суд тизимидаги ислохотлар халқаро миқёсда тан олинган халқаро стандартлар ва Бангалор тамойиллари асосига қурилган. Бангалор тамойилларнинг ҳар бири коррупцияга қарши курашда мустаҳкам ҳуқуқий замин бўлиб хизмат қилмоқда. Биз нафақат миллий қонунчиликни, балки жаҳон адолат мезонларини ҳам тизимга сингдирмоқдамиз.

Коррупциянинг олдини олишда судьянинг ўз келажагига бўлган ишончи марказий ўрин тутади. Илгари судьялар муайян муддатга (5 ёки 10 йилга) тайинланар эди, бу эса уларнинг фаолиятига билвосита ташқи таъсир ўтказиш имконини берарди. Чунки муддат тугаши арафасида судья қайта тайинланиши ўйлаб, мустақил қарор қабул қилишда иккиланиши мумкин эди. Судьялик

лавозимида бўлишнинг муддатсиз даври жорий этилиши судьяни ижроия ҳокимияти ва бошқа сиёсий кучлардан мустақил қилди.

Венеция комиссияси ва БМТнинг судьялар мустақиллигига оид тамойилларида судьяларни муддатсиз тайинлаш (ёки пенсия ёшигача) коррупцияга қарши курашнинг энг самарали ҳуқуқий ҳимояси эканлиги эътироф этилган. Бу тизим судьянинг «касбий хавфсизлиги»ни таъминлайди.

Масалан, Сингапур давлатида судьяларнинг маоши дунёдаги энг юқори кўрсаткичлардан бири ҳисобланади. Сингапурнинг асосий фалсафаси судьяга шундай маош бериш керакки, у нафақат пора олишдан қўрқсин, балки бунга эҳтиёжи ҳам қолмасин деган мазмунда. Шу билан бирга, коррупция учун жазо муқаррар ва ўта оғирдир.

Америка Қўшма Штатлари тажрибаси шуни кўрсатадики, у ерда судьяларнинг муддатсиз тайинланиши (федерал даражада) ва уларнинг шахсий обрўси энг катта бойлик ҳисобланади. Коррупцияга аралашиб судья учун нафақат қамок, балки умрбод хизмат қилган касбидан ва обрўсидан маҳрум бўлиш демакдир.

Коррупцияга қарши кураш фақат суд бинотида бўлмайди. Бу жамиятнинг судга бўлган муносабати билан ҳам боғлиқ. Фуқароларнинг роли алоҳида аҳамиятга эга. Агар фуқаролар адолатга эришишнинг ягона йўли бу қонуний асос ва кучли адвокат эканини англаб етсалар, коррупция таклиф қилувчилар сони кескин камаяди. Шунингдек, судларнинг матбуот хизматлари фаоллиги, чиқарилган қарорларнинг моҳиятини халқчил тилда тушунтириб бериш судга бўлган ишончни мустаҳкамлайди. Ишонч бор жойда эса шубҳа ва порага ўрин қолмайди.

Хулоса ўрнида шуни айтиш мумкинки, суд тизимида коррупцияга қарши кураш бу бир марталик тадбир эмас, балки узлуксиз жараёндир. Қолаверса, бу комплекс ёндашувни талаб этади. Бунда судьянинг муддатсиз тайинланиши унинг эркинлигини, рақамлаштириш жараёнининг тозаллигини, муносиб иш ҳақи иқтисодий хавфсизлигини, жамоатчилик назорати эса тизимнинг шаффофлигини таъминлайди.

Адолат сотилмайдиган, қонун устувор бўлган жамиятни қуриш бу фақат судьяларнинг эмас, балки бутун давлат ва жамиятнинг умумий мақсадидир. Биз, судьялар, бу масъулиятли йўлда нафақат қонун ҳимоячиси, балки маънавий поклик намунаси бўлиб қолишимиз шарт.

PEDAGOGIK TEXNIKANING TARKIBIY QISMLARI: O‘QITUVCHINING O‘Z XULQINI, XATTI-HARAKATLARI, FE‘L-ATVORINI BOSHQARA OLISH QOBILIYATI BILAN BOG‘LIQ BO‘LGAN KO‘NIKMANI SHAKLLANTIRISH

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada pedagogik texnikaning muhim tarkibiy qismlaridan biri — o‘qituvchining o‘z xulqi, xatti-harakatlari va fe‘l-atvorini boshqara olish qobiliyati hamda ushbu ko‘nikmani shakllantirish masalalari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Pedagogik texnika, o‘qituvchi shaxsi, o‘zini boshqarish, xulq-atvor, pedagogik mahorat, emotsional barqarorlik,

Kirish. Zamonaviy ta‘lim tizimida o‘qituvchining kasbiy mahorati nafaqat uning bilim darajasi, balki o‘z xulqi va xatti-harakatlarini boshqara olish qobiliyati bilan ham belgilanadi. Pedagogik faoliyat insonlar bilan bevosita muloqotga asoslangan bo‘lib, unda o‘qituvchining psixologik holati, emotsional muvozanati va fe‘l-atvori muhim o‘rin tutadi. Shu bois pedagogik texnika tushunchasi ta‘lim jarayonining ajralmas qismi sifatida qaraladi. Tadqiqot davomida mazkur ko‘nikmaning pedagogik jarayon samaradorligiga ta‘siri ham atroflicha tahlil qilinadi.

Asosiy qism. Pedagogik texnologiya usulining o‘ziga xos xususiyati shundaki, unda ta‘limning rejalashtirilgan maqsadiga erishishni kafolatlaydigan o‘qib – bilish (o‘zlashtirish) jarayoni loyhalashtiriladi. Maqsadni ko‘zlash, joriy natijalarni tekshirib borish, o‘quv materialini ayrim bo‘laklarga ajratib – o‘quv jarayonini tashkil

etishning bu belgilari – qayta ishlab chiqiladigan (takrorlanadigan) ta’lim sikliga xos xususiyatlaridir. Boshqacha aytganda, takrorlanadigan ta’lim siklining asosiy qismlari quyidagilar:

- ta’lim maqsadlarini umumiy belgalash;
- umumiy maqsadni oydinlashtirib o‘quv maqsadlariga aylantirish;
- o‘quv amallari majmui;
- ta’lim natijasini baholash.

O‘quv jarayoni bunday takrorlanadigan shaklga ega bo‘lgani uchun modul xarakterini kasb etadi, alohida blok (qism)larga ajratiladi, ular turli mazmunga, lekin umumiy tuzilishga ega bo‘ladi [1].

O‘quv jarayonining hamma bosqichlarida asosiy e’tibor ta’lim natijasiga erishishga qaratiladi. Pedagogik texnologiya usuli tarkibiga umumlashtirib aytganda quyidagilar kiradi:

1. Ta’limning umumiy maqsadlari, muhim masalalari tasnifi.
2. Oddiylashtirilgan maqsad (o‘quv vazifa)larini ishlab chiqish.
3. Ta’limning maqsadlarini nazorat (test) topshiriqlariga aylantirish.
4. maqsadlarga erishish usullari.

Ta’lim maqsadining aniq ifodalanishi, o‘qish davomida o‘quvchi bilimni qanchalik o‘zlashtirganidan xabardorlik, o‘quvchi (talaba) ning harakatlari (faoliyati)ga asoslanib o‘qitish - pedagogik texnologiyaning muhim jihatidi [2].

Yangi pedagogik texnologiyaga binoan o‘quv jarayonidagi muhim o‘zgarishlarning yo‘nalishlari quyidagilar: diagnostik maqsadlar asosida o‘quv maqsadlarini oydinlashtirish; joriy va yakuniy baholashlarni aniq ajratish; rejalashtirilgan ta’lim natijasiga erishishni kafolatlash; o‘quv faoliyati ko‘rinishlarini hamda o‘qituvchi va talabaning o‘zaro ta’siri vositalarini sharoitga qarab tanlash; o‘quv materialini reproduktiv topshiriqlarni bajarish orqali ishlab chiqish; etalon – natijani o‘zlashtirish uchun o‘z – o‘zini tekshirib boruvchi kichik – kichik guruhlarda ishlash kabilar [3].

O‘qituvchi pedagogik texnikasining muhim malakalaridan biri uning nutq texnikasi. (Nutq tempi, diksiyasi, (tovushning baland, o‘rta, past qila olishi) nutq

tembridir. Ma'lumki, insonlar hayotida nutq katta ahamiyatga ega. Buni barcha biladi va u har bir kishiga aloqa uchun zarur. Nutq kishilarning bir-birlariga ta'sir etishning qudratli vositasi sifatida insonni ishontirishi, mehnatga, g'alabaga chorlashi, yomon yo'ldan qaytarishi, quvontirishi yoki jahlini chiqarish va hatto o'ldirishi ham mumkin. O'qituvchi faoliyatida ham nutq juda muhim ahamiyat kasb etib, u ta'limiy – tarbiyaviy funksiyalarni bajaradi. O'quvchilar o'qituvchi nutqi orqali bilim, fikr, ishonchga ega bo'ladilar. Muayyan his –tuyg'ularni tushunib, o'z faoliyatlarini shu nutqda bayon ettirganlari asosida tashkil etadilar. Nutqning fiziologik asoslari I.P.Pavlov tomonidan izohlab berilganligi sababli ham biz sezgilarimiz, idrokimiz va tasavvurimizni atrofimizdagi tashqi dunyoning birinchi signallari deb bilamiz; nutq va tafakkur esa, ikkinchi signal sistemasini tashkil etadi. So'z voqelikdagi narsa va hodisalarni idrok qilish, ular to'g'risida tasavvurlar hosil qilishdan iborat bo'lgan bevosita signallarning signalidir [4].

Xulosa. Xulosa qilib aytganda, pedagogik texnika o'qituvchi kasbiy mahoratining ajralmas tarkibiy qismi bo'lib, unda o'z xulqi, xatti-harakatlari va fe'l-atvorini boshqara olish ko'nikmasi alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. O'qituvchining o'zini boshqarish qobiliyati pedagogik jarayonning samaradorligini ta'minlash, o'quvchilar bilan ijobiy psixologik muhitni shakllantirish hamda ta'lim sifatini oshirishda muhim omil hisoblanadi.

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THE LINGUISTIC ENCODING OF VALUE: AN AXIOLOGICAL APPROACH TO MEANING

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Annotation: This work explores the axiological dimension of language, focusing on how evaluation is encoded in conceptual meaning. It argues that concepts are not value-neutral but are shaped by culturally and socially determined systems of values. The study examines how speakers of different linguistic and cultural backgrounds assign positive or negative evaluations to the same phenomena, reflecting collective worldviews and moral norms.

Key words: Axiology, evaluation, linguistic meaning, conceptual structure, value systems, cultural semantics, worldview, proverbs, intercultural communication

Annotatsiya: Mazkur ish tilning aksiologik jihatini, ya’ni baholashning konseptual ma’noda qanday ifodalanishini o’rganishga bag’ishlangan. Unda tushunchalar qiymatdan xoli emasligi, balki ijtimoiy va madaniy jihatdan shakllangan qadriyatlar tizimi asosida yuzaga kelishi asoslab beriladi. Tadqiqot turli til va madaniyat vakillari bir xil hodisalarni turlicha – ijobiy yoki salbiy – baholashini ko’rsatadi, bu esa ularning jamoaviy dunyoqarashi va axloqiy me’yorlari bilan bog’liq.

Kalit so‘zlar: Aksiologiya, baholash, lingvistik ma’no, konseptual tuzilma, qadriyatlar tizimi, madaniy semantika, dunyoqarash, maqollar, madaniyatlararo muloqot.

Almost every concept possesses a distinct evaluative dimension. Speakers of different languages and members of different cultures may assign varying value judgments to the same concept, depending on their social experience, moral norms, and cultural traditions. As a result, evaluation in language reflects not only individual perception but also collective axiological systems that shape how concepts are

interpreted as positive or negative.[2, p. 15] These evaluative differences are linguistically encoded and become an integral part of conceptual meaning. Through language, societies fix their value orientations, allowing evaluation to function as a mechanism for interpreting reality rather than merely describing it.[4, p. 78] Consequently, concepts are not value-neutral: they are embedded in axiological frameworks that determine whether a phenomenon is perceived as good or bad, acceptable or unacceptable. This evaluative component plays a crucial role in shaping collective worldview and is especially evident in stable linguistic units, such as proverbs, where culturally significant judgments are condensed and transmitted across generations.[5, p. 156]

Axiology is a field of study concerned with the notion of value. Values are frequently conflated with the objects to which they are assigned, that is, with entities considered valuable. Statements such as *health is a great value, friendship is a great value, or peace is a great value* illustrate this tendency. However, such formulations do not imply that these phenomena are values in themselves. Rather, they indicate that a speaker assigns a high degree of value to them. In other words, these statements represent condensed expressions of a more explicit judgment, namely that an individual attributes significant value to health, friendship, or peace.[2, p. 25] This implies that different entities may possess different degrees of value and that certain values are considered higher than others.

Hartman distinguishes three levels at which axiology may be examined: the axiological system itself, the application of this system, and the concrete situations explained through its application. These levels are identified as **formal axiology, theoretical (or pure) axiology, and applied axiology**. [1, p. 155]

Formal axiology represents the most abstract level and constitutes the domain of the logic of value. At this level, value is defined both in general terms and through specific evaluative concepts. Formal axiology establishes the meanings and logical interrelations of axiological notions such as *good, bad, perfect, fair, unique, and worthless*. It also accounts for evaluative relations including *better, worse, good for, bad for*, and modal constructions such as *it is good that* or *ought*. In addition, this

level addresses the structure of axiological propositions, dimensions and hierarchies of value, rules and calculus of valuation, types of value languages, and fundamental issues such as the universality or particularity of values, their absoluteness or relativity, rationality or irrationality, and objectivity or subjectivity, as well as the general nature of the value domain and moral law.

Applied axiology functions at the phenomenal level of valuation and concerns concrete, singular values as they appear within specific fields of human activity, including ethics, aesthetics, economics, and theology. These domains represent material or empirical manifestations of valuation. However, the logic of value cannot be applied directly to concrete evaluative acts, just as mathematical logic cannot be directly equated with the act of counting. This limitation stems from the formal character of axiological logic, which applies to abstract propositions of pure axiology rather than to their empirical referents.

Theoretical axiology focuses on defining particular types of values such as aesthetic, ethical, economic, psychological, metaphysical, and technological values and on establishing their interrelations. It also examines the relationships between different value-oriented disciplines, as well as the value dimensions present in the natural sciences. This includes historically and conceptually significant intersections, such as the connection between music and astronomy in Pythagorean thought, astronomy and theology in Plato’s philosophy, or theology and chemistry in alchemy. Theoretical axiology further addresses conceptual confusions between ethics and other sciences, between scientific disciplines and their subject matter, and between value definitions expressed in statements such as *to be good is to do God’s will*, *to be good is to be preferred*, or *to be good is to be proletarian*.

Taken together, these three levels represent distinct modes of the existence of value, each characterized by its own analytical focus. Their differentiation allows axiology to address a wide range of theoretical problems, including the nature of value and disvalue, the foundations of moral norms, and the conditions under which axiological agreement or disagreement arises.[6, p. 112]

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IKKILAMCHI RESURLAR VA CHIQUINDILARNI QOPLASHGA QAYTA ISHLASH IMKONIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada bitum-piroliz qoplamalarini ishlab chiqishni yuqori resurs tejankor va energiya samaradorligiga ega usuli taklif etilgan bo'lib, ularni ishlab chiqarishda texnologik jarayonida energiya va xomashyo xarajatlarini kamaytirish hisobiga piroliz, bentonit va PET kabi ikkilamchi materiallar qo'llangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Bitum, piroliz, kompozitsiya, tabiiy resurs, polimer, organik chiqindilar, termik parchalanish, piroliz distillati, modifikator, qoplama, chiqindilar, utilizatsiya qilish, ekologik.

Zamonaviy barqaror rivojlanish sharoitida ikkilamchi resurslar va sanoat chiqindilaridan samarali foydalanish imkonini beruvchi texnologiyalarni joriy etish muhim yo'nalishdir. Ishlab chiqilgan bitum-piroliz kompozitsiyalari bunday materiallardan faol foydalanishni nazarda tutadi, bu esa atrof-muhitga salbiy ta'sirni kamaytiradi va tabiiy resurslarni tejaydi [1, 150-161 bb].

Polimer va organik chiqindilarning termik parchalanishida olinadigan piroliz distillatidan bitum modifikatori sifatida foydalaniladi. Bu an'anaviy neft komponentlari iste'molini kamaytirish va qoplamaning foydalanish xususiyatlarini oshirish imkonini beradi. Polimer chiqindilarni utilizatsiya qilish, ko'mish hajmini kamaytirish va ekologik ifloslanishning oldini olish imkonini beradi[2,B. 27].

Neft bitumi, mikrokremnezem, bentonit kabi to'ldirgichlar sanoat chiqindilaridan kelib chiqishi mumkin. Ularni qo'llash nafaqat qoplamaning tarkibiy-mexanik xususiyatlarini yaxshilaydi, balki mahsulot tannarxini ham pasaytiradi.

Ekologik xavfsizlik korroziyaga qarshi qoplamalarni ishlab chiqish va qo'llashda, ayniqsa, sanoat materiallarining atrof-muhit va inson salomatligiga ta'siri ustidan zamonaviy qattiq nazorat sharoitida muhim omillardan biridir. Bitum va piroliz distillati asosida ishlab chiqilgan bitum-piroliz qoplamalari bir qator ekologik jihatdan muhim afzalliklar bilan ajralib turadi[3, 12-24 bb].

Kompozitsiyada ishlatiladigan piroliz distillati tozalash va barqarorlashtirishdan o'tgan organik materiallarning termik parchalanishi mahsuloti bo'lib, zararli organik birikmalar (ZOB) tarkibini kamaytiradi. Qoplamalar tarkibiga og'ir metallar va normativ chegaralardan ortiq konsentratsiyadagi kanserogen moddalar kirmaydi, bu laboratoriya tahlillari bilan tasdiqlangan [4, 12-13 bb].

Foydalaniladigan polimer qo'shimchalar va sirt-aktiv moddalar minimal toksiklik va biologik parchalanuvchanlikni hisobga olgan holda tanlangan. O'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, qizdirish va qoplamalarni qo'llash chog'ida LOS ajratish me'yoriy normalar doirasida bo'lib, bu ishlab chiqarish ishchilari va atrof-muhit uchun xavfni kamaytiradi. Foydalanish jarayonida qoplamalar yuvilish va fotodegradatsiyaga yuqori chidamli bo'lib, tarkibiy qismlarning atrof-muhitga ko'chishini kamaytiradi [5, 67-68 bb].

Ishlab chiqilgan qoplamalar ekologik xavfsizlik bo'yicha milliy va xalqaro standartlar talablariga javob beradi. Suvni tejash va zaif ekotizimli hududlar kabi ekologik talablar yuqori bo'lgan zonalarda qo'llash uchun ularning yaroqliligi hujjatlar bilan tasdiqlangan.

Qoplama po'lat quvurlarning turli turlariga yuqori darajada adgeziya ko'rsatadi, agressiv muhitlarda korroziyadan uzoq muddatli himoyani ta'minlaydi, bu esa ularni yangi ob'ektlarni qurishda ham, mavjud quvurlarni ta'mirlash va rekonstruksiya qilishda ham qo'llash imkonini beradi. Qoplamanı surtish texnologiyasi mavjud sanoat uskunalariğa mos keladi, bu esa ishlab chiqarish liniyalarini modernizatsiya qilish va xodimlarni o'qitish xarajatlarini kamaytiradi.

Qoplamalar tarkibining moslashuvchanligi ularni maxsus foydalanish sharoitlariga (harorat rejimi, muhitning kimyoviy tarkibi) moslashtirish, qo'llanish sohasini kengaytirish imkonini beradi.

Piroliz distillati va ikkilamchi to‘ldirgichlardan foydalanish hisobiga qoplamalarning tannarxi sifati va chidamliligi ko‘rsatkichlariga salbiy ko‘rsatmagan holda arzonlashadi. Quvurlarning xizmat muddatini uzaytirish xizmat ko‘rsatish va kapital ta‘mirlash xarajatlarini kamaytiradi. Ishlab chiqarish jarayonining energiya samaradorligi umumiy foydalanish xarajatlarini qo‘shimcha ravishda kamaytiradi.

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O‘QUVCHILARNI BUYUK AJDODLARIMIZ MEROSI ASOSIDA MAFKURAVIY TARBIYALASH VA G‘OYAVIY IMMUNITETINI KUCHAYTIRISH ZARURIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Quyidagi maqolada o‘quvchilarni buyuk ajdodlarimiz merosi asosida mafkuraviy qurollantirish va g‘oyaviy immunitetini kuchaytirish zaruriyati o‘quvchilarda tarix ta‘limida buyuk ajdodlarimizning ilmiy merosi orqali dunyoqarashni shakllantirishda va ularni g‘oyaviy immunitetini kuchaytirish zarurligi haqida fikr-muloxozalar keltirilgan.

Annatation: In the following article, the need to ideologically arm students and strengthen their ideological immunity based on the legacy of our great ancestors is presented.

Аннотация: В статье представлена необходимость идеологического вооружения студентов и укрепления их идеологического иммунитета на основе наследия наших великих предков.

Ключевые слова: идея, идеология, иммунитет, история, общее среднее образование, научное мировоззрение, наука, энциклопедист, великие мыслители.

Key words: idea, ideology, immunity, history, general secondary education, scientific outlook, science, encyclopedist, great thinkers

Kalit so‘zlar: g‘oya, mafkura, immunitet, tarix, umumiy o‘rta ta‘lim, ilmiy dunyoqarash, ilm-fan, qomusiy olim, buyuk mutafakkirlar.

**НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ ИДЕОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ
СТУДЕНТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ НАСЛЕДИЯ НАШИХ ВЕЛИКИХ ПРЕДКОВ
И УКРЕПЛЕНИЯ ИХ ИДЕОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ НЕВОСПРИИМЧИВОСТИ**

Аннотация: В статье необходимо изменить подход и информационную систему в формировании научного мировоззрения через научное наследие наших великих предков в историческом образовании студентов, рассмотреть конкретные аспекты научной деятельности великих мыслителей в России. школьного образования в формировании научного мировоззрения учащихся, достигнутых ими результатов, их возможностей и трудностей в обучении, исходя из менталитета того времени, говорится, что важны объяснение и демонстрация.

Ключевые слова: история, общее среднее образование, научное мировоззрение, наука, великие мыслители.

THE NEED TO IDEOLOGICALLY EDUCATE STUDENTS BASED ON THE HERITAGE OF OUR GREAT ANCESTORS AND STRENGTHEN THEIR IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY

Annotation: In the article, it is necessary to change the approach and information system in the formation of the scientific worldview through the scientific heritage of our great ancestors in the history education of students, the specific aspects of the scientific activity of the great thinkers in school education in the formation of the scientific worldview of the students, the results they achieved, their opportunities and difficulties in learning from the mentality of that time it is said that explanation and demonstration are important.

Key words: history, general secondary education, scientific outlook, science, great thinkers.

Buyuk ajdodlarimizning ilmiy faoliyatini jamlagan ilmiy asarlarini o‘rganish, ularni tahlil qili bilish va ijtimoiy ahamiyatini baholay olish. Mazkur talablar asosida tarix darslarini tashkil etish, innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar – buyuk ajdodlari ilmiy merosi vositasida o‘quvchilarda bilim, ko‘nikma va malakalarni oshirishga

yo‘naltirilgan vazifalarni bajarish omili bo‘lib xizmat qiladi. Shu bilan birga o‘quvchilarni ilmiy dunyoqarashi shakllanib boradi.

Tarix darslarida buyuk ajdodlarimizning ilmiy merosi va tarixiy asarlaridan foydalanishda o‘qituvchi ham ma’lum tartiblarga amal qilishi lozim:

– dastur va o‘quv qo‘llanma bo‘yicha o‘rganish ko‘zda tutilgan tarixiy voqealarni jonli tarzda bayon etish;

– tarixiy arboblarni, buyuk ajdodlarimizning tarixiy portretini va ijtimoiy rolini ko‘rsatish;

– ilmiy dunyoqarashni shakllantirishda xizmat qiladigan Sharq mutafakkirlarining asarlari va ilmiy izlanishlarini to‘g‘ri tanlab olishi;

– mavzuga oid qo‘shimcha detallar va ma’lumotlar berish va boshqalar.

O‘quvchilarda ilmiy dunyoqarashni shakllantirishda buyuk ajdodlarimizning ilmiy merosidan foydalanib dars o‘tishda darsning “didaktik qurilishi”ni quyidagicha bo‘lishi maqsadga muvofiq:

– o‘qituvchi mutafakkirlarning asarlarini yoritish bilan birga ularning ijtimoiy ahamiyatini obyektiv yoritishiga doir shaxsiy yondashuvini ham keltirib o‘tadi.

– ilmiy dunyoqarashni shakllantirishda o‘sha davrga xos ilmiy faoliyatga ta’sir ko‘rsatgan omillarni tahlil qiladi.

– buyuk ajdodlarimizning ilmiy merosi vositasida ilmiy faoliyatga qiziqishni o‘stirish talab etiladi;

– buyuk ajdodlarimizning ilmiy merosi, ilm-fanning turli sohalariga qo‘shgan hissalarini induktiv va deduktiv metodlardan foydalangan holda tushuntiradi, ya’ni darsining yakunida umumlashtirib xulosa chiqaradi va bunga dalillar keltiradi.

1. Mavzuga yoki sinfdagi o‘tiladigan darslarga tegishli tarixiy asarlar ro‘yxatini tuzish va ular orasidan o‘quvchilarning ilmiy dunyoqarashini oshirishga kuchli ta’sir ko‘rsatadiganlarini alohida ajratib olish.

2. Iloji boricha mutafakkirlarning ilmiy asarlarni tanlab olish.

3. Tanlab olingan asarlarni qisqacha tushuntirish orqali o‘quvchilarni qiziqtirish va o‘rganishga yo‘naltirish, o‘quvchilarning o‘rgangan ma’lumotlarini, olgan bilimlarini tahlil qilish, baholab borish.

4. O‘quvchilarga ilmiy dunyoqarashni shakllantirish yo‘llari va buning uchun mutafakkirlarning asarlarini o‘rganishda e‘tibor qaratish lozim bo‘lgan jihatlar haqida tushuncha berish.

5. Buyuk ajdodlarimiz Mahmud Qoshg‘ariy, Abu Nasr Farobiy, Al-Xorazmiy, Abu Rayhon Beruniy, Abu Ali Ibn Sinoning ilmiy faoliyati to‘g‘risida alohida ma‘lumotlar berib borish.

6. O‘zbekistonda saqlanayotgan qo‘lyozmalar, tarixiy-ilmiy asarlar haqida ma‘lumot berish.

7. O‘zbekistonda yaratilgan buyuk mutafakkirlarning ilmiy merosi, asarlari, ilm-fanga qo‘shga hissalarini to‘g‘risidagi to‘plamlar, o‘tkaziladigan anjumanlar va xalqaro konferensiyalar haqida tushuncha berish, ularda qilingna ma‘ruzalar bilan tanishish imkoniyatini yaratish.

Umumiy o‘rta ta‘lim tizimida o‘tiladigan tarix talimida buyuk ajdodlarimizning ilmiy merosini innovatsion yondashuvlar asosida o‘rgatish tizimini takomillashtirish va bu orqali o‘quvchilarning ilmiy dunyoqarashini shakllantirish muhim vazifa hisoblanadi. Shu ma‘noda tanlab olingan buyuk mutafakkirlarning ilmiy merosini o‘rgatishga qraatilgan pedagogik jarayon quyidagi parametrlarga ega bo‘lishi lozim.

- ilmiy bilimlarning yetakchi roli;
- umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni bilib olish;
- tarbiyalanuvchi shaxsni ilmiy dunyoqarashini shakllantirish;
- tarixni jamiyat qurilishi tajribasi bilan bog‘liqligi;
- ta‘limning bir maqsadga qaratilganligi;
- ta‘lim sohasidagi davlat siyosatining asosiy yo‘nalishlariga muvofiqligi tamoyillari;
- didaktik prinsiplariga amal qilinishi va h.k.

Umumiy o‘rta ta‘limda tarix fani darslarida o‘quvchilarning ilmiy dunyoqarashini shakllantirishga nisbatan qo‘yiladigan didaktik talablarga ko‘ra buyuk ajdodlarimizning ilmiy merosi, asarlarini tanlashda va ulardan foydalanishda quyidagilarga e‘tibor berish lozim:

– o‘quvchilarning yoshi, bilimi va malakalari o‘tib borgan sari ularning ilmiy asarlarni o‘rganishga va ilmiy bilimlarni o‘zlashtirishga nisbatan qiziqishi ortib borish dinamikasi;

– har bir dars uchun tanlangan buyuk ajdodlarimizning asarlari ilmiyligi jihatdan talabga javob berishi;

– muayyan sinf o‘quvchilarining ilmiy dunyoqarashi, bilim darajasi, qiziqishi va ehtiyojlariga mos bo‘lishi;

Aks holda o‘quvchining diqqat-e’tibori asosiy obyekt bo‘lgan tarixiy mavzuni o‘zlashtirishdan chalg‘ishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

Ayni paytda didaktik imkoniyat hamda “ta’limiy yuk” nuqtayi nazaridan tarix darslarida foydalaniladigan buyuk ajdodlarimizning ilmiy merosini o‘rganish, asarlari bilan tanishish jarayonida mustaqil ishlay olishlari uchun o‘quvchilar:

– fan sohalari bo‘yicha ilmiy yondashuvlarni to‘g‘ri tahlil qilishlari va tushunishlari;

– undan tarixiy bilim o‘rganishlari va ilmiy dunyoqarashni yuksaltirishlari;

– so‘zlaganda yuksak ilmiy dunyoqarashni namoyon qila bilishlari va turli mutafakkirlarning ilmiy xulosalarini tushuntirib bera bilishlari;

Tarix darslarida buyuk ajdodlarning ilmiy merosi vositasida o‘quvchilarning ilmiy dunyoqarashini rivojlantirishda o‘qituvchi rahbarligida jamoa bo‘lib ishlashni tashkil etish samarali yo‘llardan biridir. Darsda buyuk mutafakkirlarning asarlaridagi ilmiy g‘oyalar va yondashuvlarni tahliliga qaratilgan pedagogik jarayon o‘quvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlashlarini rivojlantirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Mutafakkirlarning ilmiy g‘oya va qarashlarini munozaralar asosida tahlil qilish, har bir o‘quvchiga o‘z munosabatini bildirishga imkon berish, ilmiy izlanishlarning bugungi kundagi ahamiyati to‘g‘risida xulosalari bilan erkin o‘rtoqlashishlariga sharoit yaratish o‘quvchilarda ilmiy dunyoqarashni shakllanishini tezlashtirib yuboradi.

WHY DIDN'T AMIR TEMUR EVER LOSE? (HISTORICAL ANALYSIS)

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Annotation: the article covers the peculiarities of the Military Art of Amir Temur, his methods of innovating in the organization, maneuvering, supplying and communication of the combat situation of troops on a scientific basis. It also examined Amir Temur's contributions to military theory, the importance of the "Temur traps", its influence on the next generation of warlords, and its role in modern military education.

Keywords: " Temur traps", military theory, commander, Empire, military art, strategy, tactics, troop, military march, supply, troop organization.

Amir Temür (1336-1405) is regarded as one of the most prominent captains in world history. His military campaigns not only led to the conquest of vast territories, but also greatly influenced the development of military art. Amir Temur's military strategy and tactics were innovative for the time, and they were also used by the next generation of commanders.

This is how Ibn Arabshah defines the person of Timur. "Timur was a man of unrivaled character, of deep contemplation, and there was no floor of his sea of contemplation, and a path was found to the mountain of (his) event, neither flat nor humbled." [6, p.64].

Amir Temür's military strategy was based on the rational use of military power to achieve his political goals. Amir Temur set a specific goal before each military campaign. This purpose could have had political, economic or military significance. For example, the purpose of the march against the Golden Horde was to break its power and make the borders of Central Asia safe.

Temür's military art, his ability as a commander, was evident in the structure of the armies and in the “savkuljaysh”(strategy) and fighting styles he employed in the major battles next to Terek, Qunduzcha, Ankara, namely the “ta'biyatuljaysh” (tactics). His army consisted of soldiers formed on the basis of ten soldier compounds. On minglik – ” district“, miglik – ” khazora“, hundred - ” khoshun“, tithe - ” ayl”.

The army units were separated by signs. The red flag, for example amiralumaro, was a sign of a long blunt mist mouth with a beak connected by a horse's Mane, a round face head with coquils hanging on both sides. At the forefront of the journey were the “khabargiri”- spies, who marched with each of their armies, who would be in front of the ranks. Spies were selected from the most advanced, powerful and courageous soldiers. The messengers were followed by the “yasovuls”, and in the center by the “manglay”-Vanguard. A commander's residence was placed between manglai and the army, with an “izova”- reserve around their flank. On the right side of the detachment, the “burongor” troops were deployed, and on the left-the “juvongor” troops were deployed. The army was divided into seven sections, with the arrangement as outlined above being introduced by Amir Temur. It was mentioned by Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi in his work “The Triumph”.

Amir Temur studied in depth the strengths and weaknesses of the opponent, his military potential, his economic situation and his political situation. This information was instrumental in establishing a walking plan. Timur correctly distributed the forces for each March. It concentrated forces on the main strike direction and left enough force on the secondary directions. Amir Temur attached great importance to agility and suspense. He used a variety of military tricks to distract the opponent and carried out the attack at an unexpected time and place.

Amir Temur was trying to get along well with the inhabitants of the conquered territories. He respected the religion, customs and traditions of the population and treated them fairly. This helped ensure peace and tranquility in the conquered territories. “If I wanted to draw a army over my Ghanim, I would like to speak out in the midst of war and find out which of these two of my emirs is inclined. When

Arash spoke of the wound, I used to compare the benefits of it to the detriment of the war. If they were prone to war, I would compare its usefulness and usefulness to the harm of the race”. [1, B. 17]. This interpretation of Amir Temur shows that before the military campaign he conducted a council. As peacefully as possible, he tried to resolve the differences through the mashwarat.

Amir Temur's military theory is fully reflected in his work "the Temur traps". The great warlord draws attention to the importance of this work, quoting such sentences. "In my experience, I saw that if the state was not built on the basis of religion-it was not built on the rule, and tola was not tied to the structure, then the shukuhi, power and order of the kingdom would disappear." [1, B. 73]. Amir Temur's military strategy played an important role in the success of his campaigns. He achieved victory by reconciling political goals with military might by studying the opponent in depth, properly distributing forces, attaching importance to agility and unpredictability.

Amir Temur was also an innovator in military tactics. The organizational structures of his troops and each unit had its own leader and was completely subordinate to him. The troops included cavalry, infantry, archers, and skilled warriors who used manjaniqs (stone throwing weapons).

About the composition of the Temur soldiers A. Choriyev says in his work "The Divine spirituality". "To the surprise of ibn Arabshah, that sahibqiran was so tolerant and therefore faithfully served him, in addition to Muslims, Christians, Zoroastrians, Buddhists and other religions." [3, B. 159].

The main force of the Emir Temür army was Cavalry soldiers. Cavalry soldiers had the characteristics of agility, maneuverability, and aggressiveness. They were used to surround the opponent's Wings, attack from the rear, and launch quick raids.

Archers also played an important role in the Temür Army. Archers were used to damage an opponent at long range, break their ranks, and prepare them for attack. In the army of Amir Temur, engineers carried out siege of forts, construction of bridges, repair of roads and other engineering tasks. They used mandibles and other siege weapons to help break through the opponent's defenses.

Sahibqiron used a variety of military tricks to distract the opponent and achieve victory. Methods such as false withdrawal, troop displacement, night attacks, and rumor spreading helped to deorient the opponent and gain the upper hand. Amir Temur's military tactics were instrumental in securing the victories of his troops. He gained an advantage against the opponent by organizing troops, increasing the role of Cavalry soldiers, making the most of the Archers, clearly defining the task of engineers, and successfully applying military tricks.

The following work was carried out on the supply system. Amir Temur had created an effective system to supply his troops with food, weapons and other necessities. Supplies were made at the expense of territorial reserves, merchants and supplies from the local population.

Special attention was paid to the construction and repair of roads and bridges to ensure the rapid movement of his troops. These works were carried out by engineers and soldiers. Amir Temur had created a special communication system to ensure communication between his troops. Messages were delivered through messengers, chopsticks, and gestures. This helped coordinate troop movements and make quick decisions.

A specialist medical service has been established to provide medical care to wounded and infected soldiers. Field hospitals, surgeons, and medicines have been credited with helping to maintain the health of soldiers and their quick return to the line.

The military art of Amir Temur has left an important mark on World Military History. His strategy, tactics were an example for the next generation of captains. His experience of military marching was reflected in his work "the Temür traps", which made important recommendations for Public Administration, troop organization, and military marching planning. Of this, in his arrangements, sarkarda says: "those who use these arrangements as a guide in the management of their dynastic affairs, so that the state and Kingdom that reach them from me is harm-that he may survive the decline." [1, PG. 68]. The work was translated and printed in many world languages, including English, Persian, Russian, and the present Uzbek language. [3-182]

Timur's military art had a great influence on the next generation of captains, including Beaver, Napoleon, and others. They used Amir Temur's strategy, tactics and logistics to succeed in their march. His military art continues to be studied in modern military educational institutions. His walking experience, strategic thinking and tactical methods are important in the training of future captains.

The military art of Amir Temur is an important example for the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Uzbek national army continues the military tradition of Amir Temur, serving to protect the homeland and ensure the safety of the people.

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FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLARNING SINONIMIK QATORLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada frazeologik birliklarning sinonimik qatorlari, ularning semantik, stilistik va obrazli xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Sinonimiya hodisasining til taraqqiyotidagi o‘rni, frazeologik sinonimlarning tasnifi hamda ingliz va o‘zbek tillari misolida ularning qo‘llanishi yoritiladi. Tadqiqot natijasida frazeologik sinonimlarning nutq boyligini oshirishdagi ahamiyati asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: frazeologiya, sinonimiya, frazeologik birlik, sinonimik qator, stilistik bo‘yoq, dominanta, obrazlilik.

Frazeologik birliklar tilning muhim qatlamlaridan biri bo‘lib, ular ko‘pincha ikki yoki undan ortiq so‘zlardan tashkil topadi va ko‘chma, obrazli ma‘noni ifodalaydi. Bunday birliklar nafaqat nominativ, balki stilistik vazifani ham bajaradi. Ayniqsa, frazeologik sinonimiya tilning boyligi va rivojlanganlik darajasini ko‘rsatadigan muhim hodisalardan biridir.

Tilshunos olim Shavkat Rahmatullayev ta’kidlaganidek, frazeologik birliklarning aksariyati stilistik jihatdan neytralga yaqin bo‘lsa-da, ular sinonim so‘zlarga nisbatan kuchliroq ifoda imkoniyatiga ega (Rahmatullayev, 1966).

Sinonimiya kamida ikki yoki undan ortiq til birliklari o‘rtasidagi ma‘no yaqinligiga asoslanadi. Bu birliklar o‘zaro bog‘lanib, sinonimik qatorni hosil qiladi. Sinonimik qator tarkibidagi birliklar bir umumiy ma‘noga ega bo‘lsa-da, ular o‘zaro nozik semantik va stilistik farqlarga ega bo‘ladi.

Sinonimik qatorda odatda bitta asosiy birlik — **dominanta** ajralib turadi. Dominanta boshqa sinonimlarga nisbatan umumiyroq va kengroq ma‘noni ifodalaydi.

Shavkat Rahmatullayev frazeologik sinonimlarni quyidagi mezonlar asosida tasniflaydi:

1. Frazeologik birliklarning leksik tarkibi
2. Ularning asosida yotgan obraz
3. Ma’nodagi farqlanish darajasi

Bundan tashqari, ingliz tilshunosi N. L. Kamenetskaya frazeologik sinonimlarga bag‘ishlangan maxsus lug‘at tuzgan bo‘lib, unda sinonimik qatorlar stilistik bo‘yoqdorlik va ko‘chma ma’no asosida ajratiladi.

1. “Juda uzoq vaqt” ma’nosini bildiruvchi iboralar

Quyidagi sinonimik qatorda dominanta sifatida “**a month of Sundays**” iborasi ajralib turadi:

- *a month of Sundays* — juda uzoq vaqt (umumiy, neytralroq)
- *donkey’s years* — juda uzoq vaqt (so‘zlashuv uslubida)
- *till the cows come home* — cheksiz uzoq vaqt (emotsional bo‘yoqli)

Bu iboralar umumiy ma’noda bir-biriga yaqin bo‘lsa-da, ularning stilistik ranglari farq qiladi. Masalan, *donkey’s years* ko‘proq so‘zlashuv nutqida ishlatiladi, *till the cows come home* esa obrazlilik jihatdan kuchliroqdir.

O‘zbek tilida ushbu ma’noga mos iboralar:

- “tuyaning dumi yerga tekkanda”
- “qizil qor yoqqanda”

2. “Pulga muhtoj bo‘lmoq” ma’nosini bildiruvchi iboralar

Quyidagi frazeologik sinonimlar bir sinonimik qatorni tashkil etadi:

- *be hard up* — pulga muhtoj bo‘lmoq (dominanta)
- *be as poor as a church mouse* — juda kambag‘al bo‘lmoq
- *be as poor as Job’s turkey* — nihoyatda qashshoq bo‘lmoq

Bu iboralarning barchasi moddiy yetishmovchilikni ifodalaydi, ammo ularning obrazlilik darajasi va stilistik bo‘yoqlari turlicha.

Frazeologik sinonimlar nutqda muhim stilistik vosita hisoblanadi. Ular yordamida takrorlardan qochiladi, nutq ravonligi ta’minlanadi, fikrning nozik qirralari ifodalanadi, emotsional-ekspressiv ta’sir kuchaytiriladi. Sinonimik

qatorlardan to‘g‘ri foydalanish nutq madaniyatining muhim ko‘rsatkichidir. Har bir vaziyatda eng mos iborani tanlash til egasidan yuqori darajadagi lingvistik sezgirlikni talab qiladi.

Xulosa

Frazeologik sinonimiya tilning boyligi va ifoda imkoniyatlarining kengligini ko‘rsatadi. Sinonimik qatorlar orqali bir xil ma’no turli stilistik va obrazli vositalar yordamida ifodalanadi. Dominanta tushunchasi esa sinonimik tizimni tartibga solishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Frazeologik sinonimlarni chuqur o‘rganish tilshunoslikda ham nazariy, ham amaliy jihatdan muhimdir.

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O‘SMIRLAR PSIXOLOGIK HIMOYA MEXANIZMLARINI O‘RGANISHGA DOIR NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR

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Zamonaviy psixologiyada psixologik himoya mexanizmlarini o‘rganishga katta e‘tibor beriladi. Olimlarning ta’kidlashicha, psixologik himoya tushunchasi psixoanalizning shaxsiyat nazariyasi va aqliy moslashuv nazariyasiga qo‘shgan eng muhim hissalaridan biri bo‘lgan va shunday bo‘lib qoladi. Psixologik himoya mexanizmlarini shaxsiyatni barqarorlashtirish uchun tartibga solish tizimi sifatida ko‘rish mumkin. Keng psixologik kontekstda psixologik himoya u yoki bu tarzda salbiy, psixotravmatik kechinmalar yuzaga kelganda va asosan shaxsning xulq-atvorini belgilab, ruhiy noqulaylik va tashvishli taranglikni bartaraf etganda qo‘zg‘atiladi. Ko‘pgina zamonaviy psixologik tushunchalarda psixologik himoya o‘z-o‘zidan shubha va pastlik tuyg‘ularini yengish, qadriyat ongini himoya qilish va barqaror o‘zini o‘zi hurmat qilish funksiyasini bajaradi.

O‘smirlik inson rivojlanishining eng murakkab va o‘ziga xos bosqichidir. Bu davrda jismoniy, hissiy va ijtimoiy o‘zgarishlar jadallashadi, o‘zini anglash va shaxsiy identifikatsiya jarayoni chuqurlashadi. O‘smirlar tashqi muhit ta’siriga nisbatan sezuvchan bo‘lib, bu davrda stressli holatlar va ichki ziddiyatlar ko‘payadi. Bunday holatlarda shaxs o‘z ruhiy holatini saqlab qolish uchun turli psixologik himoya mexanizmlarini ishga soladi. Ushbu mexanizmlar inson ong osti tomonidan avtomatik tarzda faollashadi va psixik muvozanatni saqlashga xizmat qiladi. O‘smirlarning psixologik himoya mexanizmlarini tizimli o‘rganish hozirgi kunda zamonaviy psixologiyaning dolzarb tadqiqot muammosi sifatida e‘tirof etilgan. Adabiyotlarning nazariy tahlili shuni ko‘rsatadiki, ko‘pchilik mualliflar o‘smirlik davriga xos bo‘lgan himoya mexanizmlarini o‘rganadilar.

Himoya mexanizmlari—inson ruhiyatida yuzaga keladigan xavfli, yoqimsiz hissiyot yoki fikrlardan o‘zini ong osti darajasida himoya qilish tizimidir. Bu

tushuncha ilk bor Zigmund Freyd tomonidan joriy qilingan va keyinchalik Anna Freyd, E.Erikson, K.Xorni kabi psixoanalitiklar tomonidan rivojlantirilgan. Himoya mexanizmlarining asosiy funksiyasi shaxsni ichki ziddiyatlar va tashqi tahdidlardan asrash, ruhiy barqarorlikni saqlab qolishdir. Ular ong osti faoliyatining bir ko‘rinishi bo‘lib, aksariyat hollarda inson bu jarayonni anglab yetmaydi.

E. Erikson nazariyasiga ko‘ra, o‘smirlik — bu identitet inqirozi davri, unda shaxs “men kimman?”, “hayotdagi o‘rnim qanday?” degan savollarga javob izlaydi. Bu jarayon ko‘plab ichki ziddiyatlar va tashqi bosimlar bilan kechadi. Masalan:

- o‘z tengdoshlariga moslashish ehtiyoji;
- ota-onalar bilan avtonomiya (mustaqillik) uchun kurash;
- tananing jismoniy o‘zgarishlariga nisbatan noaniq munosabat;
- kelajak uchun qarorlar qabul qilishdagi ishonchsizlik.

Bunday murakkab holatlarda himoya mexanizmlari o‘smirga psixologik xavfsizlikni saqlash imkonini beradi.

Psixologik himoya mexanizmlarini o‘rganishda Anna Freyd bolalik davriga alohida e‘tibor qaratadi. Uning fikriga ko‘ra, aynan bolalar misolida bu mexanizmlarning faoliyatini yanada aniqroq kuzatish mumkin, chunki bolalarning hissiy hayoti kattalarnikiga nisbatan sodda va shaffofroq bo‘ladi. Bu esa kattalarga bolalarning turli hodisalarga bo‘lgan reaksiyalarini oldindan taxmin qilish imkonini beradi. Agar kutilgan emotsional yoki xulqiy javob sodir bo‘lmasa, bu psixologik jarayonda ma’lum bir buzilish yoki o‘zgarish mavjudligini anglatadi.

Anna Freyd bunday holatlarda aynan affekt (hissiy holat) transformatsiyasining sababini psixologik himoya mexanizmlarining ta’sirida izohlaydi. U himoya mexanizmlarini kuzatish orqali ularning asosiy funksiyasi shaxs ruhiyatining barqarorligini saqlashdan iborat ekanligini ta’kidlaydi. Ya’ni, bu mexanizmlar tartibsizlikka va psixik parchalanishga qarshi kurashuvchi, shaxsni ruhiy muvozanatda ushlab turuvchi vositalar sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi. Biroq, Anna Freyd himoya mexanizmlaridan foydalanishning o‘zi psixik muammolarni butunlay hal etmaydi, deb hisoblaydi. Aksincha, himoya vaqtincha yechim bo‘lishi mumkin, lekin ichki konfliktlar — xususan, qo‘rquv, xavotir va noaniqlik hissi ong ostida saqlanib

qoladi. Bu esa uzoq muddatda psixologik muammolarning chuqurlashishiga, hattoki nevrotik buzilishlarning yuzaga kelishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

A. Freyd ayrim psixik himoya mexanizmlarining muayyan psixologik kasalliklar bilan bog‘liq bo‘lishini aniqlaydi. U o‘z tadqiqotlarida har bir psixik patologiyaga mos keluvchi, o‘ziga xos himoya strategiyalarini ko‘rsatib o‘tadi. Masalan:

- Isteriya holatida ko‘pincha repressiya (bostirish) — ya’ni og‘riqli fikrlar va xotiralarni ongdan siqib chiqarish — ustuvor rol o‘ynaydi;

- Obsessiv-kompulsiv nevroz esa odatda izolyatsiya va bostirish mexanizmlarining ko‘p qo‘llanilishi bilan tavsiflanadi.

Bu kuzatishlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, psixologik himoya mexanizmlari nafaqat shaxsning ruhiy holatini vaqtincha barqarorlashtirishga xizmat qiladi, balki ularning noto‘g‘ri va haddan ortiq qo‘llanilishi ayrim ruhiy buzilishlar rivojlanishida muhim rol o‘ynaydi.

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TEACHING ENGLISH IN MIXED-ABILITY CLASSES

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Abstract: The presence of mixed-ability classes has become increasingly common in English language teaching (ELT) due to diverse educational backgrounds, varying proficiency levels, and inclusive education policies. This study examines the challenges and effective pedagogical strategies associated with teaching English in mixed-ability classrooms. The research aims to explore how teachers can address learner diversity while maintaining engagement and achieving instructional goals. A qualitative research design was employed, utilizing classroom observations, teacher interviews, and document analysis. The findings reveal that differentiated instruction, scaffolding, flexible grouping, and formative assessment are essential strategies for managing heterogeneous classrooms. These approaches contribute to improved student participation, confidence, and overall learning outcomes.

Keywords: Mixed-ability classes, English language teaching, differentiated instruction, inclusive education, scaffolding, classroom management, learner diversity.

In contemporary educational contexts, classrooms are increasingly characterized by heterogeneity in student abilities, prior knowledge, learning styles, and socio-cultural backgrounds. This is particularly evident in English language teaching (ELT), where learners' proficiency levels often range from beginner to advanced within a single classroom. Mixed-ability classrooms are therefore a common reality in secondary and higher education institutions, as well as in adult and community language programs. The heterogeneity in these classrooms presents a multifaceted challenge for teachers, as they must simultaneously address the diverse learning needs of all students while maintaining engagement, ensuring effective instruction, and achieving curricular goals. Traditional pedagogical models, which tend to assume

a relatively uniform level of student ability, are often inadequate for mixed-ability settings. Teachers frequently face dilemmas such as managing students who complete tasks at different speeds, balancing attention between advanced learners and those struggling, and designing lesson plans that are both challenging and accessible. If not addressed effectively, these challenges can lead to unequal participation, reduced motivation among weaker students, and frustration among stronger students who are under-challenged. From a theoretical perspective, mixed-ability classrooms intersect with multiple principles in educational psychology and second language acquisition. Vygotsky’s concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) emphasizes the importance of scaffolded support, where learners can progress beyond their current competence with appropriate guidance (Vygotsky, 1978). Similarly, Gardner’s theory of multiple intelligences highlights that students possess different strengths and learning preferences, requiring teachers to adopt varied instructional strategies. In addition, contemporary approaches in ELT, including communicative language teaching (CLT) and task-based language teaching (TBLT), emphasize interaction, learner-centeredness, and differentiated tasks—principles that are particularly relevant in heterogeneous classrooms.

The importance of inclusive education policies further accentuates the need for effective teaching strategies in mixed-ability classes. Educational systems worldwide increasingly aim to provide equitable learning opportunities, ensuring that all students, regardless of their proficiency or prior achievement, can participate meaningfully and achieve their learning objectives. Mixed-ability classrooms, therefore, are not only a pedagogical challenge but also an opportunity to foster collaborative learning, peer support, and social cohesion among students. This study aims to investigate effective instructional strategies for teaching English in mixed-ability classrooms, with a focus on understanding both the challenges and practical solutions that teachers employ. The research seeks to answer the following questions:

- What are the primary challenges faced by teachers in mixed-ability English classrooms?

- Which instructional strategies are most effective in accommodating learner diversity?

- How do these strategies influence student engagement, participation, and learning outcomes?

By exploring these questions, the study contributes to the growing body of literature on inclusive education and provides practical insights for ELT practitioners working in heterogeneous learning environments.

This study adopts a qualitative-descriptive research design, which is particularly suitable for investigating complex educational phenomena such as mixed-ability classrooms. Unlike quantitative approaches that focus primarily on measurable outcomes, qualitative research allows for a detailed exploration of teaching practices, student-teacher interactions, and classroom dynamics. The descriptive aspect ensures that the study captures a comprehensive view of the strategies teachers use, the challenges they encounter, and the responses of learners. The research is guided by an interpretivist paradigm, which emphasizes understanding human behavior within its social and cultural context. In mixed-ability classrooms, student behavior, participation, and engagement are influenced not only by individual ability but also by peer interactions, classroom culture, and instructional methods. A qualitative-descriptive design enables the researcher to capture these nuanced factors and their interrelationships.

The participants of this study included English language teachers and students from several secondary schools and higher education institutions. The teachers were selected based on their experience teaching mixed-ability classes, ranging from three to fifteen years of professional practice. Student participants represented a broad spectrum of English proficiency, from beginner to advanced levels, and included individuals with diverse learning styles, motivations, and socio-cultural backgrounds. Participation was voluntary, and ethical approval and consent were obtained from all participants.

Data were collected using a triangulated approach to enhance reliability and provide a holistic understanding of classroom dynamics. The methods included:

Lessons were observed over multiple sessions to capture teaching strategies, student engagement, and interaction patterns. Field notes focused on how teachers adapted tasks for different ability levels, classroom management techniques, and the responses of students to various instructional methods.

Teachers were interviewed to provide insight into the challenges they encounter, their pedagogical beliefs, and the strategies they employ to address learner diversity.

The semi-structured format allowed for guided discussion while providing flexibility for teachers to share experiences in depth.

The analysis of classroom observations, teacher interviews, and lesson plan documents revealed multiple insights regarding the challenges and effective strategies in teaching English in mixed-ability classrooms. The findings are organized into three main themes: challenges, instructional strategies, and student outcomes.

Challenges in Mixed-Ability Classrooms

a) Variation in Language Proficiency

A primary challenge observed across all classrooms was the significant disparity in English proficiency levels. While some students demonstrated advanced grammatical knowledge and fluency, others struggled with basic vocabulary and sentence construction. Teachers noted that designing lessons suitable for the entire class was difficult, as tasks that were accessible to lower-level learners often under-challenged more advanced students.

b) Unequal Participation

Observation data revealed that stronger students tended to dominate oral activities, group discussions, and classroom interactions. Conversely, students with lower proficiency levels often remained passive, avoided speaking, or relied on peers for answers. Interviews indicated that teachers struggled to ensure equitable participation without discouraging stronger learners.

c) Time Constraints

Teachers highlighted that individualized attention and differentiated tasks require additional time, which was often limited within standard lesson periods.

Planning activities that simultaneously cater to multiple proficiency levels was identified as a major time-intensive task.

d) Classroom Management

Mixed-ability classrooms presented challenges in maintaining order and focus. In some observed sessions, students became disengaged if tasks were too easy or too difficult. Teachers noted that balancing engagement while preventing off-task behavior required constant monitoring and adaptive instruction.

The findings indicate that mixed-ability classrooms present both pedagogical challenges and opportunities for enhancing English learning. The challenges identified—variation in proficiency, unequal participation, time constraints, and classroom management—are consistent with previous research (Tomlinson, 2014; Harmer, 2007). These challenges highlight the need for adaptive and learner-centered teaching approaches.

Differentiated instruction emerged as a key strategy for addressing learner diversity. By tailoring tasks to individual abilities, teachers were able to maintain engagement, challenge advanced students, and support lower-level learners. This aligns with Tomlinson’s (2014) framework, which emphasizes content, process, and product differentiation as essential tools for inclusive classrooms.

Scaffolding allowed learners to bridge the gap between current competence and target skills, reflecting Vygotsky’s (1978) Zone of Proximal Development. The use of mixed-ability groups further enhanced peer-assisted learning, enabling advanced learners to reinforce their knowledge while supporting their peers. This approach fosters not only cognitive development but also social and communicative competence.

Communicative and interactive activities proved effective in engaging students across proficiency levels. Activities such as role-plays and discussions provided meaningful contexts for language use, increasing intrinsic motivation and active participation. This supports principles of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), which prioritize meaningful interaction over rote memorization (Ur, 2012).

Teaching English in mixed-ability classrooms is both a challenge and an opportunity for language educators. This study has highlighted that learner diversity—manifested in varying proficiency levels, cognitive abilities, and learning styles—requires adaptive and inclusive pedagogical approaches. Mixed-ability classes challenge teachers to balance engagement, provide appropriate support for weaker learners, and simultaneously offer meaningful challenges to more advanced students. Differentiation ensures that all learners are appropriately challenged, scaffolding supports skill development within the learners’ zone of proximal development, and flexible grouping promotes peer-assisted learning and collaboration. Communicative and interactive activities enhance engagement and intrinsic motivation, while formative assessment allows teachers to continuously monitor progress and adjust instruction.

Moreover, mixed-ability classrooms offer significant pedagogical advantages. Peer learning encourages collaboration, fosters social skills, and allows stronger learners to reinforce knowledge while supporting their peers. Inclusive practices in such settings contribute to equitable learning opportunities, enhance learner confidence, and promote a positive classroom environment.

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ЯЗЫКОВАЯ КАРТИНА МИРА НАРОДОВ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ

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Аннотация: В статье исследуется языковая картина мира народов Центральной Азии как комплексный лингвокультурный феномен, отражающий специфику этнического сознания, исторического развития и когнитивных моделей восприятия действительности. Анализируются ключевые концепты, формирующие национально-культурную семантику, выявляются особенности репрезентации времени, пространства и социальных отношений. Особое внимание уделяется влиянию многоязычия и языковых контактов на формирование и трансформацию языковой картины мира в регионе.

Ключевые слова: языковая картина мира, Центральная Азия, концепт, лингвокультура, когнитивная лингвистика, билингвизм, языковые контакты, культурный код.

Языковая картина мира представляет собой одну из ключевых категорий современной лингвистики, находящуюся на пересечении когнитивного и культурологического подходов. Она понимается как совокупность представлений о мире, закреплённых в языке и отражающих результаты познавательной деятельности человека. Согласно Ю.Д. Апресяну, язык фиксирует «наивную картину мира», отличную от научной, но обладающую внутренней системностью [1, с. 38]. В свою очередь, А. Вежбицкая подчёркивает универсальность базовых семантических примитивов при их национально-культурной специфике [2, с. 115].

Центральная Азия как историко-культурный регион характеризуется сложной этнолингвистической структурой, сформированной в результате длительного взаимодействия различных языковых и культурных традиций.

Здесь сосуществуют тюркские, иранские и славянские языки, что обуславливает многоуровневую организацию языковой картины мира. Многоязычие выступает не только социолингвистическим фактом, но и когнитивным механизмом, влияющим на способы концептуализации действительности.

Одной из определяющих характеристик языковой картины мира народов Центральной Азии является её ценностно-ориентированная структура. В центре данной системы находятся концепты, отражающие базовые социальные и культурные установки: «семья», «род», «уважение», «гостеприимство», «честь». Эти концепты репрезентируются через лексико-фразеологические средства, паремиологический фонд, а также коммуникативные нормы. Их устойчивость свидетельствует о глубокой укоренённости традиционных ценностей в языковом сознании.

Существенным элементом языковой картины мира является концептуализация пространства. Для народов Центральной Азии характерна тесная связь пространственных представлений с традиционным образом жизни. Пространство осмысливается через бинарные оппозиции «свой – чужой», «дом – внешний мир», «центр – периферия». Эти оппозиции отражают не только географическую, но и социальную организацию общества. Лексика, связанная с обозначением природных объектов, отличается высокой степенью детализации, что свидетельствует о значимости природной среды в формировании мировоззрения.

Категория времени в языковой картине мира региона также обладает специфическими чертами. Наряду с линейным восприятием времени, характерным для современного общества, сохраняются элементы циклической модели, связанной с аграрными и календарными традициями. Это проявляется в языковых единицах, отражающих повторяемость природных и социальных процессов, а также в структуре фольклорных текстов.

Религиозный фактор играет значительную роль в формировании языковой картины мира. Исламская культурная традиция оказала влияние на систему

ценностей, коммуникативное поведение и языковую семантику. В языке закрепились многочисленные заимствования из арабского и персидского языков, а также религиозные формулы, функционирующие в повседневной речи. Религиозный дискурс формирует особый слой языковой картины мира, связанный с морально-этическими нормами и мировоззренческими установками.

Особое внимание следует уделить феномену языковых контактов, который является определяющим для Центральной Азии. Длительное сосуществование различных языков привело к формированию устойчивых механизмов интерференции и взаимовлияния. Заимствования, калькирование, семантические сдвиги и смешение кодов являются характерными чертами языковой ситуации региона. В результате формируется гибридная языковая картина мира, сочетающая элементы различных культурных традиций.

В условиях глобализации языковая картина мира народов Центральной Азии претерпевает значительные изменения. Усиление межкультурных контактов, развитие цифровых технологий и расширение информационного пространства способствуют трансформации традиционных концептов. Наряду с сохранением базовых культурных ценностей наблюдается появление новых смысловых доминант, отражающих современные социальные реалии.

Таким образом, языковая картина мира народов Центральной Азии представляет собой сложную, динамичную и многослойную систему, формирующуюся под воздействием исторических, культурных и социолингвистических факторов. Её специфика определяется сочетанием традиционных и современных элементов, а также взаимодействием различных языковых и культурных кодов. Исследование данного феномена позволяет глубже понять особенности национального сознания и закономерности развития языка в условиях многоязычия.

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BADIIY MATNDA LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK BIRLIKLARNING TARJIMASI (“THE ESTABLISHMENT” KONSEPTINING RUS VA O‘ZBEK TILLARIDAGI QIYOSIY TAHLILI (SIDNI SHELDONNING “ORZIQIB KUTAMAN ERTANI” ASARI MISOLIDA)

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada “the establishment” birligini asliyatdagi ma’nolari va rus va o‘zbek tillaridagi tarjimalari lingvokulturologik yuklamaning qay darajada saqlanib qolganligi tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: “the establishment”, “establishment”, ijtimoiy, siyosiy va madaniy mazmun, transliteratsiya, qiyosiy tahlil, mazmun uzatish, denotative ma’no, konnotativ ma’no, pragmatik ma’no

Zamonaviy tilshunoslikda lingvokulturologik birliklarning badiiy matndagi ifodasi va ularning turli tillarga tarjimasi alohida ilmiy ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ayniqsa, ma’lum bir madaniyatga xos bo‘lgan tushunchalarni boshqa tilga o‘girish jarayonida ularning nafaqat denotativ, balki konnotativ hamda pragmatik ma’nolarini saqlab qolish muhim masalalardan biri hisoblanadi. Shu nuqtai nazardan ingliz tilidagi “*the establishment*” kabi birliklar o‘zida chuqur ijtimoiy, siyosiy va madaniy mazmuni mujassam etgani bilan e’tiborni tortadi.

Mazkur maqolada badiiy adabiyot namunasi sifatida *If Tomorrow Comes* asaridan olingan parcha asosida “*the establishment*” lingvokulturologik birligining rus va o‘zbek tillaridagi tarjimalari qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot jarayonida tarjima strategiyalari, xususan, transliteratsiya va semantik moslashtirish usullarining qo‘llanishi, ularning mazmun uzatishdagi samaradorligi hamda milliy-madaniy komponentlarning qay darajada saqlanib qolganligi aniqlanadi.

Shuningdek, maqolada mazkur birlikning kognitiv-semantik xususiyatlari, uning ijtimoiy qatlam, hokimiyat va elitaga oid konseptual maydondagi o‘rni yoritiladi. Tahlil natijalari tarjima nazariyasi hamda amaliy tarjimashunoslik uchun muhim xulosalar chiqarishga xizmat qiladi. Tahlil uchun quyida *“the establishment”* birligining aslyatdagi va rus hamda o‘zbek tillaridagi tarjimada ishlatilgan parchani keltirib o‘tamiz.

Aslyatdagi matn: *There was such a charming unpretentiousness about him that Tracy found herself warming to him. I wonder what it would be like to be married to someone like him - one of the establishment. (1.14)*

Ruscha tarjima: *От этой подкупающе безыскусной искренности у Трейси потеплело на душе. «Интересно, каково быть замужем за таким мужчиной – человеком, принадлежащим к истеблишменту?» – подумала она. (2.9)*

O‘zbekcha tarjima: *Чарльзнинг самимий сўзлаши Трейси кўнглида илиқлик уйғотди. «Қизиқ, - ўйлади у, - юқори табақали бирон кимсага эрга тегсам, четдан қандай кўринар экан-а?» (3.9)*

Tahlil jarayonida *“establishment”* so‘zi oldidan aniq artikl *the* ishlatilganiga alohida e‘tibor berishimiz kerak bo‘ladi, sababi ba‘zi so‘zlarning oldidan aniq artikl *the* ishlatilganda ularning ma‘nolarida o‘zgarishlar hosil bo‘ladi, xususan, ma‘lum bir so‘zlarning turkuni o‘zgaradi yoki bo‘lmasa buyumni bildirgan otlardan shaxsni bildirgan otlarga o‘zgaradi va hkz. Aslyatdan keltirilgan parcha *“establishment”* birligi *“the establishment”* ko‘rinishida yoziladi va bu quyidagi tahlilda aniqlanadi. Quyida *“establishment”* birligiga ingliz tili Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learners of American English va Cambridge Advanced Learners Dictionary kabi izohli lug‘atlarda berilgan ta‘riflarga e‘tibor qaratgan holda tahlilga tortamiz:

1. Establishment (noun)

- any institution, organization, or business: *a research/ training establishment.*

There are many eating establishments nearby.

2. the establishment

- the most important and powerful people in a country, who are often thought of as being conservative and wanting to preserve their own power and influence;

- used for referring to powerful people in a particular profession or section of society: the literary / legal / medical establishment (MED - 462)

1. **Establishment (noun)** a business or other organization, or the place where an organization operates: *an educational/financial/religious establishment*

2. **the establishment** the important and powerful people who control a country or an organization, especially those who support the existing situation: *Critics said judges were on the side of the establishment.* (CALD)

Yuqorida “establishment” birligiga har ikkala lug’atda bir xil ta’rif berilgan va “establishment” hamda “the establishment” birliklarining o’rtasida ancha katta ma’noviy farq borligiga e’tiborimizni qaratamiz. “Establishment” birligi “muassasa” ma’nosini bildirib kelgan bo’lsa, “the establishment” birligi esa kishilarni bildirib kelyapti.

“The establishment” birligi bu yerda oddiy “tashkilot” ma’nosida emas, balki jamiyatning hukmron, imtiyozli, yuqori tabaqasi, siyosiy, iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy elita vakillari ma’nosini bildirib kelyapti. Lingvokulturologik jihatdan “the establishment” birligi “yuqori tabaqa, obru-e’tibor, qudrat” tushunchalari bilan bog’liq bo’lib, Britaniya va Amerika madaniyatida badavlat, qudratli ijtimoiy qatlamni bildiradi.

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“The establishment” birligining rus tilidagi tarjimasini “человек, принадлежащий к истеблишменту” tarzida tarjima qilingan va rus tilidagi “истеблишмент” birligi inglizcha so’zning to’g’ridan-to’g’ri transliteratsiyasi bo’lib, siyosiy-ijtimoiy termin sifatida asl madaniy tushunchani saqlab qoladi. Biroq

rus tilidagi tarjimasini “*устеблишмент*” denotativ va konnotativ ma’noni saqlagan holda maksimal ekvivalentlikni ta’minlasada, kitobiy va rasmiy jaranglaydi va oddiy o’quvchiga tushunarli bo’lmay qoladi.

“The establishment” birligining o’zbek tilidagi tarjimasini “*юқори табақали бирон кимсага*” tarzida mazmun soddalashtirib tushunarli tarzda oddiy kitobxonga tez yetib boradigan qilib tarjima qilingan. Shu bilan birga ijtimoiy status “yuqori tabaqa” aniq ifodalangan. Biroq, tarjimada umumlashtirish hodisasi sodir bo’lgan, ya’ni “yuqori tabaqa” tarzida tarzida tarjima qilingani “the establishment” birligining ruscha tarjimasiga qaraganda nozik konnotatsiyalarini xiralashtirib yuborgan. Demak, o’zbekcha tarjima adaptatsiya yo’lidan brogan, vaziyatni tushunarli ifodalagan, lekin ma’no torayishi sodir bo’lgan.

“The establishment” birligi tarjimasining qiyosiy tahlili quyidagicha bo’ladi:

Ruscha tarjima	O’zbekcha tarjima
Transliteratsiya	Semantik soddalashtirish
Madaniy yuklama to’liq saqlangan	Madaniy yuklama qisman yo’qolgan
Tushunarlilik darajasi o’rtacha	Tushunarlilik darajasi yuqori

Xulosa sifatida aytasigan bo’lsak, “the establishment” birligi faqat “boy, yuqori tabaqaga mansub odam” emas, balki ijtimoiy-siyosiy tizim ichidagi elitani anglatishi kerak. Shu sababdan, ruscha tarjimasini bu murakkab tushunchani saqlab qolgan, o’zbekcha tarjimasini esa uni semantic jihatdan bir muncha soddalashtirgan. Shu bilan birga, o’zbekcha tarjima oddiy kitobxonga juda tushunarli tarzda berilgan.

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КОНЦЕПТ «ЛЮБОВЬ» КАК ФРАГМЕНТ ЯЗЫКОВОЙ КАРТИНЫ МИРА (НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ АНГЛИЙСКИХ И РУССКИХ ПОСЛОВИЦ)

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Аннотация: Статья посвящена сопоставительному анализу концепта «любовь» в пословичном фонде английского и русского языков. Исследование основано на паремиологическом и лексикографическом материале, отражающем особенности языковой картины мира носителей двух культур. В работе выявляются универсальные и национально-специфические характеристики концепта, связанные с представлениями о природе любви, её иррациональности, неподконтрольности, чувственном восприятии и соотношении с категориями красоты, страдания, болезни и брака.

Ключевые слова: концепт «любовь», паремиология языковая картина мира, лингвокультурология, сопоставительный анализ, английский язык, русский язык, национальное сознание, идиоматические выражения, ценностные представления.

И русский, и английский идиоматический материал предоставляют данные о том, что любовь – это иррациональное чувство. В обоих языках существуют пословицы и поговорки, в которых акцентируется неподконтрольность и немотивированность выбора объекта любви. Возлюбленный не выбирается по определенным критериям, он воспринимается таким, каким он есть. Человек свободен в любви, и у него всегда есть возможность выбора: *(Любви все возрасты покорны (А. Пушкин); Насильно мил не будешь; Кому что нравится: кому поп, кому попадья, а кому и попова дочка; К кому сердце лежит, туда и око бежит; Любовь за деньги не купишь; Любовь закона не знает, годов*

не считает; Любовь делает умных безумными, кротких — буйными, а неукротимых — мирными; Для любви нет преград; love is free; to be head over heals in love with smb).

В английских пословицах и поговорках любовь слепа: (*Love is blind, as well as hatred; hatred is blind, as well as love; Love takes away the sight and matrimony restores; mother love is blind; A face only a mother could love; Любовь слепа; одно сердце страдает, а другое не знает; любовь зла, полюбишь и козла; Полюбится сатана вместо ясного сокола*). Также обращает на себя внимание то, что здесь проводится параллель между любовью и ненавистью (*Love-hate relationship; как кошка с собакой*).

Однако чаще в пословицах указывается на возможность чувственного восприятия, причем главным органом восприятия здесь являются глаза: (*Хоть и ряба, да любя; Любовь начинается с глаз; глазами влюбляются; Где больно, там рука; где мило, тут глаза; С глаз долой, из сердца вон; Глаз не видит — душа не болит*). Упоминаются также иные органы чувств: (*Тоска западает на сердце глазами, ушами и устами*). Конечно же главным органом чувств, которое несет ответственность за любовь, является сердце (*Сердце не камень — тает; Сердце сердце чувствует; Сердце сердцу весть подает; Сердцу не прикажешь; Сердцем не приманишь, так за уши не притянешь; Где сердце лежит, туда и око бежит*).

Однако, как это представлено в русских пословицах, органы чувств могут ошибаться: (*Любовь зла – полюбишь и козла; Покажется сатана лучше ясного сокола; Приглянулся черт ягодкой*).

Идиоматический материал обоих языков содержит данные о том, что красота не является основным фактором выбора объекта любви: (*Не славится красавица, а кому что нравится; Красота — в глазах любящего; С лица воду не пить, умела бы пироги печь; Beauty lies in lover's eyes; Jack is no judge of Jill's beauty*). Однако только русский материал предоставляет данные о том, что любовь нельзя привлечь, используя косметические

средства: *(Мило не мыло, а беленькое личико; Белила не сделают мила, подо нрав не подбелиться).*

Как в русском, так и английском языках любовь приравнивают к болезни, симптомы которой ярко выражены, очевидны (кашель, покалывания сердца), несмотря на глубину и силу любви, ее невозможно преодолеть, она всегда найдет свое проявление в той или иной ситуации: *(Любви, огня, да кашля от людей не спрячешь; Love and cough cannot be hidden; No herb will cure love; Никакая трава не вылечит любви; Где любовь, там и напасть).*

В русских пословицах любовь часто ассоциируется не только с болезнью, но и с болью: *(Будешь любить, коли сердце болит; Лучшие страдать да любить, чем не любя на свете жить; Любовь — крапива стрекучая).* Вообще любовь рассматривается в русской народной мудрости как любая напасть, несчастье, которое невозможно победить, например, как такая беда, как пожар: *(Любовь не пожар, а загорится — не потушишь; Не любить — горе, а влюбиться — вдвое; Коли что полюбится, так и ум отступится; Любовь хоть и мука, а без нее скука)*

Характерной чертой характера русской женщины, отраженной в пословицах, является готовность терпеть побои от любимого: *(Милого побои на кости; Кто кого любит, тот того и бьет).* Интересно, что побои от любимого даже одобряются, оцениваются положительно: *(Милый ударит — тела прибавит. Милый побьет, только потешит).* В англо – американской культуре это невозможно. Более того, здесь имеет место только понимание беспричинности мелких спор и ссор как показателя силы любви: *(The falling out of lovers is the renewing of love).*

В русской культуре любовь рассматривается не только как телесная, но и как душевная болезнь: *(Тошно тому, кто любит кого, а тошнее того, кто не любит никого; Одна душа страдает, другая ничего не знает; Любить тяжело, не любить тяжелее того).* Но, тем не менее, отсутствие любви – это гораздо более существенная потеря, печаль и тоска, душа человека нелюбящего сильнее покрыта мраком и окутана горем, чем человека, чье сердце бьется ради кого –

то и чьи глаза сияют от любви. В английской культуре также одобряется наличие любви в жизни человека, пусть несчастной и безответной:

(This better to have love and lost, than never to have loved at all).

Любовь и горе зачастую идут вместе, неотделимо друг от друга. При этом страдание причиняет отсутствие объекта любви: *(Где любовь, там и напасть; Без солнышка нельзя пробыть, без милого нельзя прожить; Без тебя не цветно цветы цветут, не красно дубы растут в дубравушке; Полюбив, нагорюешься; Горе мне с вами — карими очами; Горе с тобою, беда без тебя; Жить в разлуке — хуже муки; Милый не злодей, а иссушит до костей; Не спится, не лежится, все про милого грустится; Не мил и свет, коли милого нет; Не милое прялье, когда милого друга нет).*

Без любви человек умирает, не может вынести столь тяжкие страдания, но и без любимого накрывает пустота, которую не осилить, которая оказывается еще более мучительной, чем тем горести и беды, которые приносит любовь: *(Не видишь — душа мрет, увидишь — с души прет; Горе с тобою, беда без тебя; Лучшие страдать да любить, чем не любя на свете жить; Вместе скучно, а врозь тошно).* Такое единение приводит к тому, что влюбленный не хочет отдавать себе отчет в своем чувстве, однако также не может отвергнуть объект любви: Любить не люблю, а отвязаться (отказаться, отстать) не могу.

Любовь независима и является тем благом, которое невозможно приобрести ни за какие деньги, любовь бесценна, ее сила делает ее трудно доступной, только избранные могут насладиться этим чувством: *(Любовь за деньги не купишь; Насильно мил не будешь).* И здесь возникает интересный аспект, любовь считается высшим везением, и счастье в личной жизни исключает удачу в делах: *(Lucky at cards, unlucky in love).*

Любовь существует в любых ее проявлениях в богатстве и бедности, в болезни и здравии. Необязательно наличие жизненных благ, поскольку сама любовь является наивысшим благом и богатством: *(С милым рай и в шалаше. — Love in a cottage; Деньги — прах, одежда — тоже, а любовь всего*

дороже. – Love lives in cottages as well as in courts).

Богатство и достаток противопоставляются любви, являются антитезой данному чувству, выбор делается в пользу любви, пусть и бедной, нежели в пользу достатка, изобилия и богатства, которые не могут ничего дать человеку: *(Любовь да лад — не надобен и клад; Любовь за деньги не купишь; Любовь да совет, так и нуждочки нет; Деньги — дело наживное, о них нечего тужить, а любовь — дело другое: ею нужно дорожить; Деньги — прах, одежда тоже, а любовь всего дороже; Лучшие быть в бедности, да с милым, чем в богатстве, да с постылым; Хоть спать на камыше, зато милый по душе. – Love is the only in service that power cannot command and money cannot buy).* Человек согласен служить во имя любви и во благо любви, но отрицает деньги, как благо, за которое можно продать любовь: *(A labour of love; for love; not for love or money).*

В качестве сравнения следует отметить, что в английской культуре на первое место все же выходит материальное, его понимают как неотделимую часть отношений, в пословицах указывается на то, что ситуация будет намного легче и приемлемее, если любовь будет развиваться не в нищете, но в то же время в тех же пословицах отмечается сила, неподвластность и неподкупность любви: *(Love is sharper than stones and sticks. Love is the only fire against which there is no insurance. Love's anger is fuel to love).*

Также нельзя не упомянуть о том, что и в русской, и в английской культурах любовь – это то, без чего нельзя жить, любви ничего не страшно – ни разлука, ни расстояние, для любви нет преград *(Absence makes the heart grow fonder; Для влюбленного и сто верст не расстояние; Для настоящей любви нет предела; Верная любовь ни в огне не горит, ни в воде не тонет; Больше той любви не бывает, как друг за друга умирает; Любовь все побеждает; Реже видишь — больше любишь).*

Исходя из вышеперечисленных особенностей паремиологии английского и русского языков, а также лексикографических данных можно сделать следующие выводы относительно концепта любовь в языковой картине мира носителей английского и русского языков:

1. Концепт любовь в сознании носителей английского и русского языков обнаруживает ряд сходств. В первую очередь любовь связана с межличностными отношениями. Любовь невозможно подчинить чьей-либо воле, она неподконтрольна человеку. Выбор объекта привязанности не мотивирован. Любовь в отношении ко времени рассматривается противоречиво: с одной стороны она бесконечна, с другой стороны – имеет свойство проходить.

2. Концепт любовь в представлении носителей английского языка связан с рядом специфических особенностей. Так, чувство любви наиболее типично по отношению к одушевленному объекту, в то время как любовь к неодушевленному объекту мыслится как чувство большей степени интенсивности, нежели в русском языке.

3. Любовь с точки зрения носителей английского языка нельзя купить, но вместе с тем, она зависит от материального показателя: бедность может послужить причиной разрыва любовных отношений. Иной причиной «гибели» любви может стать брак.

4. Английский концепт любовь отражает влияние этого чувства на человека. Любовь способна менять людей, делать их лучше, красноречивее, но в то же время ее невозможно выразить словами. Кроме того, любовь – чувство искреннее, основанное на честности и доверии. Высшее проявление этого чувства – родственная любовь.

5. В русском национальном сознании любовь носит более универсальный характер: привязанность можно испытывать как к одушевленному, так и к неодушевленному предмету, и хотя характер чувства будет при этом отличаться, его интенсивность не будет зависеть от объекта, на который оно направлено.

6. Любовь для русского человека связана с негативными эмоциями, в первую очередь со страданием (в том числе от разлуки).

7. В русском языке выражен признак стихийности, спонтанности возникновения любви.

8. Отличительной чертой русского концепта является выраженность смыслового блока, связанного с побоями. Побойи мыслятся носителями русского языка как один из способов выражения любви.

9. Наконец, для русского сознания любовь бескорыстна: она связана с желанием делиться, и ее невозможно купить за деньги.

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KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TIZIMIDA ICHKI AUDITNING ROLI VA AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur tezisda korporativ boshqaruv tizimida ichki auditning o‘rni, uning risklarni boshqarish, nazorat tizimi va tashkilot faoliyati samaradorligini ta’minlashdagi ahamiyati ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida ichki auditning korporativ boshqaruv jarayonlarini takomillashtirishdagi vazifalari, audit qo‘mitasi bilan o‘zaro aloqalari hamda risklarga asoslangan audit yondashuvining ahamiyati o‘rganildi. Shuningdek, ichki auditning tashkilotda strategik qarorlar qabul qilish jarayoniga ta’siri hamda uning korporativ boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirishdagi imkoniyatlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: korporativ boshqaruv, ichki audit, risklarni boshqarish, nazorat tizimi, audit qo‘mitasi, boshqaruv jarayonlari, samaradorlik.

Hozirgi global iqtisodiy sharoitda korporativ boshqaruv tizimini samarali tashkil etish har qanday tashkilotning barqaror rivojlanishi va raqobatbardoshligini ta’minlashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Korporativ boshqaruv nafaqat tashkilot faoliyatini boshqarish mexanizmlarini belgilaydi, balki risklarni aniqlash, nazorat qilish hamda strategik maqsadlarga erishishni ham ta’minlaydi. Korporativ boshqaruv tushunchasi tashkilot faoliyatini boshqarishga qaratilgan jarayonlar va tuzilmalar majmui sifatida talqin qilinadi. Ushbu jarayonlar tashkilot oldiga qo‘yilgan maqsadlarga erishish, risklarni boshqarish hamda samarali nazorat mexanizmlarini

shakllantirish bilan chambarchas bog‘liqdir. So‘nggi yillarda tashkilotlar faoliyatida yuzaga kelayotgan yangi iqtisodiy va texnologik risklar korporativ boshqaruv tizimini yanada takomillashtirishni talab qilmoqda. Ayniqsa, globalizatsiya, raqamli transformatsiya, kiberxavfsizlik muammolari va bozor kon’yunkturasi tez o‘zgarishi tashkilotlarda samarali nazorat va audit tizimining mavjud bo‘lishini muhim omilga aylantirmoqda.

Shu nuqtai nazardan, korporativ boshqaruv tizimida ichki audit instituti alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ichki audit tashkilot faoliyatini baholash, risklarni aniqlash hamda boshqaruv jarayonlarini takomillashtirish orqali tashkilotning barqaror rivojlanishiga xizmat qiladi.

Ichki audit tashkilot ichida amalga oshiriladigan mustaqil nazorat faoliyati bo‘lib, uning asosiy vazifasi tashkilotda mavjud boshqaruv, risklarni boshqarish va ichki nazorat tizimlarining samaradorligini baholashdan iboratdir.

Xalqaro ichki auditorlar instituti (IIA) ta’rifiga ko‘ra, ichki audit tashkilot faoliyatini takomillashtirishga qaratilgan mustaqil va obyektiv baholash hamda maslahat berish faoliyatidir. U tashkilotning risklarni boshqarish, nazorat va boshqaruv jarayonlarining samaradorligini baholash orqali tashkilot qiymatini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Ichki auditning asosiy vazifalari quyidagilardan iborat:

- tashkilotda risklarni boshqarish tizimini baholash;
- ichki nazorat tizimining samaradorligini aniqlash;
- boshqaruv jarayonlarini tahlil qilish;
- tashkilot faoliyatining strategik maqsadlarga mosligini tekshirish;
- aniqlangan kamchiliklarni bartaraf etish bo‘yicha tavsiyalar berish.

Ichki audit tashkilotning barcha darajalarida amalga oshiriladigan nazorat tizimining muhim elementlaridan biri hisoblanadi. U boshqaruv organlari uchun obyektiv axborot manbai bo‘lib xizmat qiladi hamda qarorlar qabul qilish jarayonida muhim rol o‘ynaydi.

Korporativ boshqaruv tizimida ichki auditning asosiy vazifalaridan biri tashkilot faoliyatining samaradorligini oshirishdir. Ichki audit risklarni aniqlash va baholash orqali tashkilot faoliyatidagi muammolarni o‘z vaqtida aniqlash imkonini beradi.

Ichki audit faoliyatining muhim jihatlaridan biri shundaki, u tashkilotdagi boshqaruv tizimi, risklarni boshqarish jarayonlari hamda ichki nazorat mexanizmlarining samaradorligini baholaydi. Ushbu jarayon orqali tashkilot faoliyatidagi kamchiliklar aniqlanadi hamda ularni bartaraf etish bo‘yicha aniq tavsiyalar ishlab chiqiladi.

Ichki auditning yana bir muhim vazifasi tashkilot rahbariyati va kuzatuv kengashiga mustaqil axborot taqdim etishdan iboratdir. Bu esa boshqaruv qarorlarini qabul qilishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Ichki audit quyidagi asosiy funksiyalarni bajaradi:

1. **Nazorat funksiyasi** – tashkilot faoliyatini nazorat qilish.
2. **Tahlil funksiyasi** – iqtisodiy jarayonlarni baholash.
3. **Maslahat funksiyasi** – boshqaruv qarorlarini takomillashtirish bo‘yicha tavsiyalar berish.
4. **Risklarni boshqarish funksiyasi** – potentsial xavflarni aniqlash.

Ichki audit faoliyatining samarali tashkil etilishi tashkilot faoliyatining shaffofligini ta‘minlaydi hamda investorlar va manfaatdor tomonlarning ishonchini oshiradi.

Korporativ boshqaruv tizimida audit qo‘mitasi muhim o‘rin egallaydi. Audit qo‘mitasi odatda kuzatuv kengashi tarkibida tashkil etilib, tashkilot faoliyatini nazorat qilish hamda audit jarayonlarini muvofiqlashtirish vazifasini bajaradi.

Audit qo‘mitasining asosiy vazifalari quyidagilardan iborat:

- ichki va tashqi audit faoliyatini muvofiqlashtirish;
- moliyaviy hisobotlarning ishonchliligini ta‘minlash;
- audit natijalarini ko‘rib chiqish;
- aniqlangan kamchiliklarni bartaraf etish bo‘yicha choralar ko‘rish.

Audit qo‘mitasi mustaqil direktorlar tomonidan tashkil etilishi audit jarayonining mustaqilligini ta‘minlaydi hamda audit faoliyatining samaradorligini oshiradi.

Ichki audit xizmatining audit qo‘mitasi bilan hamkorligi tashkilotda samarali nazorat tizimini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Hozirgi zamonaviy iqtisodiy sharoitda tashkilotlar faoliyatida yuzaga kelayotgan risklar tobora murakkablashib bormoqda.

Texnologik o‘zgarishlar, kiberxavfsizlik muammolari, global iqtisodiy inqirozlar va siyosiy beqarorlik kabi omillar tashkilot faoliyatiga sezilarli ta’sir ko‘rsatmoqda.

Ichki audit ushbu risklarni aniqlash va baholash orqali tashkilot faoliyatini barqaror rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

Ichki auditning korporativ boshqaruvdagi roli quyidagi jarayonlarda namoyon bo‘ladi.

1. Risklarni aniqlash va baholash

Ichki audit tashkilot faoliyatida yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo‘lgan moliyaviy, operatsion, huquqiy va strategik risklarni aniqlaydi va baholaydi.

Auditorlar risklarni tahlil qilib, qaysi jarayonlarda muammo yuzaga kelishi mumkinligini oldindan ko‘rsatadi. Bu esa rahbariyatga xatolar va zararlarning oldini olish imkonini beradi.

Masalan:

- moliyaviy yo‘qotishlar
- noto‘g‘ri boshqaruv qarorlari
- qonunchilik buzilishi

2. Ichki nazorat tizimini baholash

Ichki audit tashkilotdagi ichki nazorat mexanizmlarining samaradorligini tekshiradi.

Bu quyidagilarni o‘z ichiga oladi:

- moliyaviy nazorat
- operatsion jarayonlar nazorati
- hujjat aylanishi
- hisobotlarning ishonchliligi

Agar nazorat tizimida kamchiliklar aniqlansa, auditorlar ularni takomillashtirish bo‘yicha tavsiyalar beradi.

3. Rahbariyat va kuzatuv kengashiga mustaqil axborot berish

Ichki audit tashkilot ichida mustaqil nazorat organi hisoblanadi.

U rahbariyatga va kuzatuv kengashiga:

- tashkilot faoliyati haqida obyektiv ma’lumot beradi

- kamchiliklar va risklar haqida hisobot tayyorlaydi
- qaror qabul qilish uchun ishonchli axborot taqdim etadi.

Shuning uchun ichki audit ko‘pincha “mustaqil baholovchi” deb ataladi.

4. Korporativ boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirish

Ichki audit tashkilot boshqaruv tizimini tahlil qilib, uning samaradorligini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Masalan:

- boshqaruv jarayonlarini optimallashtirish
- xarajatlarni kamaytirish
- resurslardan samarali foydalanish
- biznes jarayonlarni takomillashtirish

5. Audit qo‘mitasi faoliyatini qo‘llab-quvvatlash

Korporativ boshqaruv tizimida audit qo‘mitasi mavjud bo‘lsa, ichki audit:

- audit qo‘mitasiga hisobot beradi
- tekshiruv natijalarini taqdim etadi
- nazorat tizimini kuchaytirishga yordam beradi.

Bu esa korporativ boshqaruvning shaffofligi va ishonchliligini oshiradi.

6. Tashkilot faoliyatini takomillashtirish bo‘yicha maslahat berish

Ichki audit faqat tekshiruvchi emas, balki maslahatchi funksiyasini ham bajaradi.

Auditorlar quyidagilar bo‘yicha tavsiyalar beradi:

- risklarni kamaytirish
- boshqaruv tizimini yaxshilash
- ichki nazoratni kuchaytirish
- strategik qarorlarni qo‘llab-quvvatlash.

Ichki audit quyidagi yo‘nalishlarda risklarni boshqarishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi:

- strategik risklarni aniqlash;
- operatsion risklarni baholash;
- moliyaviy risklarni nazorat qilish;
- muvofiqlik risklarini aniqlash.

Ichki audit faoliyati risklarga asoslangan yondashuv asosida amalga oshirilganda tashkilot faoliyatining samaradorligi sezilarli darajada oshadi.

Ichki audit faqat nazorat funksiyasini bajarib qolmay, balki tashkilot rivojlanishiga ham katta hissa qo‘shadi. Ichki auditorlar tashkilot faoliyatini chuqur tahlil qilish orqali boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirishga qaratilgan takliflar ishlab chiqadilar.

Ichki audit tashkilotda innovatsiyalarni joriy etish, boshqaruv tizimini modernizatsiya qilish hamda samaradorlikni oshirish jarayonlarida muhim rol o‘ynaydi.

Ichki auditning yana bir muhim xususiyati shundaki, u tashkilot rahbariyatiga kelajakda yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo‘lgan muammolar haqida oldindan axborot berish imkonini yaratadi. Bu esa strategik qarorlar qabul qilish jarayonida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Yakuniy natijalari shuni ko‘rsatadiki, ichki audit korporativ boshqaruv tizimining ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Ichki audit tashkilot faoliyatining shaffofligini ta’minlash, risklarni samarali boshqarish hamda nazorat tizimini takomillashtirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi.

Ichki auditning samarali faoliyati quyidagi natijalarga erishishga yordam beradi:

- tashkilot faoliyatining samaradorligini oshirish;
- risklarni o‘z vaqtida aniqlash va kamaytirish;
- boshqaruv qarorlarining sifatini yaxshilash;
- investorlar va manfaatdor tomonlarning ishonchini oshirish.

Zamonaviy iqtisodiy sharoitda tashkilotlar faoliyatida risklar soni ortib borayotganligi sababli ichki auditning roli yanada ortib bormoqda. Shu sababli korporativ boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirish jarayonida ichki audit xizmatini rivojlantirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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A TAXONOMY-BASED APPROACH TO ENHANCING CRITICAL LITERACY IN UZBEK HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: One of the most important things that higher education does today is teach students how to think critically, especially in language and literature classes. But in a lot of Uzbek universities, reading classes are still mostly about figuring out what the words mean. This makes it harder for students to read, think critically about, and respond to what they read. This chapter puts forward a teaching method based on Barrett's Taxonomy of Reading Comprehension that aims to systematically improve critical literacy skills. The method breaks down reading instruction into five levels: literal, reorganization, inferential, evaluative, and appreciative comprehension. Literary texts are divided into tasks of different levels of difficulty, which helps students move from basic understanding to deep analysis and thought. This chapter looks at the theoretical basis of critical literacy, evaluates how Barrett's taxonomy is used in the classroom, and looks at how it is used in higher education in Uzbekistan. This chapter illustrates how systematic questioning and task design can enhance students' higher-order thinking skills through classroom observations and pedagogical approaches. The results show that teaching based on taxonomy is a clear and effective way to help students improve their reading skills in terms of interpretation, evaluation, and reflection. The chapter concludes that the systematic application of hierarchical comprehension levels can significantly improve critical literacy in literary education.

Key words: reading comprehension, hierarchical learning, cognitive development, higher-order thinking, literary analysis, interpretative skills, evaluative thinking

Most people who work in higher education agree that students should be able to read critically. One needs to be able to read a piece of writing, figure out what it means, judge its arguments, and come to their own conclusions(1). This skill is very important for learning literature because literary texts often have hidden meanings, symbolic structures, and many ways to look at them. A lot of colleges and universities in Uzbekistan still put a lot of emphasis on remembering facts and understanding things on the surface, which is important. Teachers often tell their students to pay attention to clear information instead of doing deep analysis or thinking critically(2). Because of this, they still have a hard time figuring out what's right and wrong and understanding difficult texts.

To meet this challenge, we need structured teaching frameworks to help us teach and test. Barrett's Taxonomy of Reading Comprehension is one of these frameworks(3). It provides a methodical way to improve reading skills. This chapter contends that a taxonomy-based approach can enhance critical reading skills among philology students in Uzbek universities.

Critical literacy is founded on cognitive and socio-cultural theories of reading. From a cognitive standpoint, reading entails the construction of meaning through the interplay between the text and the reader's existing knowledge(4). To better understand something, one needs to make decisions, come to conclusions, and put everything together. From a critical standpoint, literacy is perceived as an active engagement in interrogating and interpreting texts. Scholars stress that readers must not passively accept textual information; rather, they should critically analyze the underlying meanings, assumptions, and values(5). There are two main parts to critical literacy: the cognitive part, which is understanding, breaking down, and judging; and the affective part, which is how we feel and what we think about it.

Good teaching needs to cover both areas so that students can really understand what they read. Barrett's Taxonomy is a structured framework that was made just for teaching reading. It divides understanding into five levels of importance(6):

1. Literal comprehension means understanding what is said in simple terms.
2. Reorganization means putting information together and making it shorter.

3. Inferential comprehension is the ability to understand something without being told what it means.

4. Evaluative comprehension—figuring out what's good and bad about the content and how it looks

5. Appreciative comprehension means responding with feelings and beauty.

This progression shows how people learn to think critically about difficult things after they have a basic understanding. Barrett's model is better for teaching literature because it includes both the mental and emotional parts of reading, which other cognitive taxonomies don't do(7).

The suggested method is based on these ideas:

a) Teaching should start with simple ideas and move on to more complicated ones.

b) Tasks should be clearly linked to different levels of understanding.

c) Students should learn more when they are asked questions in a way that makes sense.

d) The tests should show how mentally involved someone is at different levels.

People teach with short stories and other types of writing. People use Barrett's levels to set up tasks. Literal tasks mean figuring out who, what, and when things happened. Putting information in order, summarizing it, and putting it into groups are all parts of reorganizing tasks(8). To find themes, motives, and effects, one needs to make guesses. Evaluative tasks: determining the author's intent and assessing the characters. Appreciative tasks: letting people know how we feel and what we think.

This structure makes sure that students read texts at many levels, which helps them understand them better over time(9).

We can plan lessons in a structured way in philology programs based on how well the students understand the material:

- Reproducible questions that were arranged in a hierarchy to get people talking in class

- Writing that shows different levels of understanding

- Always checking on how well the students are doing

Teachers can help students learn in class by making sure they understand the text on a basic level before giving them complicated tasks. Students get more confident in themselves and get better at analyzing things as they move up through the levels(10). Observations in the classroom show that students do well on tasks that require reading comprehension, that guided practice helps them make inferences, and that they need to keep getting instruction in order to improve their evaluative and appreciative skills. These results show that students don't naturally lack higher-order skills; they just need structured guidance to develop them. The taxonomy-based approach gives this structure by making it clear what levels of understanding are involved and making sure that tasks fit those levels. The method also gets people to talk about texts, which helps them understand them better and think more deeply. When students say what they think and back it up, they feel more sure of themselves(11).

The taxonomy-based approach changes how teachers teach in a lot of different ways. It helps teachers plan lessons better, improve critical literacy in a more organized way, find out where students are having trouble, and make sure that all levels of understanding are tested fairly(12).

It is important because it changes the focus from remembering to understanding and judging, which is what schools want right now. The method works, but there are some issues with it. For instance, teachers need to plan their lessons and get ready for class. It might be harder for teachers at first, and students might need some time to get used to the harder work.

Conclusion

This chapter offers a taxonomy-based strategy to improve critical literacy in higher education in Uzbekistan. Teachers can help students learn how to read, think about, and respond to texts in a structured way by using Barrett's levels of comprehension to plan their lessons.

The results show that structured teaching frameworks are necessary for full understanding. The taxonomy-based method not only helps students understand what

they read better, but it also helps them think critically and reflectively, which are important skills for doing well in school.

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O‘ZBEKISTONDA OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA’MINLASHDA QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGI SUG‘URTASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO‘NALISHLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O‘zbekistonda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta’minlashda qishloq xo‘jaligi sug‘urtasining o‘rni va ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda agrar sohada mavjud risk omillari, xususan iqlim o‘zgarishi, hosildorlik tebranishi va bozor beqarorligining ishlab chiqarishga ta’siri yoritiladi. Qishloq xo‘jaligi sug‘urtasini rivojlantirish orqali ushbu risklarni kamaytirish va ishlab chiqarish barqarorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari asoslab beriladi. Shuningdek, amaldagi sug‘urta tizimidagi muammolar aniqlanib, ularni bartaraf etish bo‘yicha takomillashtirish yo‘nalishlari taklif etiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini mustahkamlash va agrar siyosatni samarali yuritishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, qishloq xo‘jaligi sug‘urtasi, agrar risklar, hosildorlik barqarorligi, iqlim o‘zgarishi, sug‘urta mexanizmlari, agrar siyosat, risklarni boshqarish, ishlab chiqarish barqarorligi, oziq-ovqat ta’minoti.

Kirish. So‘nggi yillarda O‘zbekistonda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta’minlash davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo‘nalishlaridan biri sifatida shakllandi. Aholi sonining ortib borishi (2024-yil yakuniga ko‘ra 36,7 mln kishidan oshgani) oziq-ovqat mahsulotlariga bo‘lgan talabni keskin oshirmoqda. Shu bilan birga, qishloq xo‘jaligi yalpi mahsuloti hajmi ham izchil o‘sib, 2023-yilda 3,9–4,0 % atrofida o‘sish qayd etildi [1]. Mazkur jarayonlar mamlakatda oziq-ovqat ta’minoti barqarorligini mustahkamlash bilan bir qatorda, ishlab chiqarishdagi risklarni boshqarish zaruratini ham kuchaytirmoqda.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasida agrar sohani isloh qilish bo‘yicha qator muhim normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar qabul qilindi. Jumladan, 2019-yilda qabul qilingan “Qishloq xo‘jaligini rivojlantirish strategiyasi (2020–2030)”da ishlab chiqarishni diversifikatsiya qilish, zamonaviy agrotexnologiyalarni joriy etish hamda risklarni kamaytirish mexanizmlarini rivojlantirish ustuvor vazifa sifatida belgilangan [2]. Shuningdek, sug‘urta tizimini rivojlantirish orqali fermer va dehqon xo‘jaliklarini moliyaviy himoya qilish masalalari ham davlat siyosati darajasiga ko‘tarildi. Bugungi kunda qishloq xo‘jaligi ishlab chiqarishida iqlim xavflari, suv taqchilligi va narxlar beqarorligi asosiy risk omillari sifatida namoyon bo‘lmoqda.

Shu nuqtai nazardan, qishloq xo‘jaligi sug‘urtasini takomillashtirish oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta‘minlashning muhim instrumentlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Statistik ma‘lumotlarga ko‘ra, sug‘urtalangan ekin maydonlari ulushi hali ham past darajada qolmoqda, bu esa agrar ishlab chiqarishda moliyaviy barqarorlikning yetarli emasligini ko‘rsatadi [3]. Rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasi shuni ko‘rsatadiki, sug‘urta mexanizmlarining samarali ishlashi ishlab chiqarish hajmini barqarorlashtirish va risklarni kamaytirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Shu sababli, O‘zbekistonda mavjud sug‘urta tizimini takomillashtirish va uni xalqaro tajribalar asosida rivojlantirish dolzarb ilmiy-amaliy vazifa hisoblanadi.

Asosiy qism. O‘zbekistonda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta‘minlashda qishloq xo‘jaligi ishlab chiqarishining barqarorligi hal qiluvchi omil hisoblanadi. So‘nggi yillarda asosiy oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish hajmida ijobiy dinamikalar kuzatilmoqda. Jumladan, 2023-yilda don yetishtirish hajmi 8,0 mln tonnaga yaqinlashgan bo‘lsa, sabzavot mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish 11 mln tonnadan oshdi, meva yetishtirish hajmi esa 3 mln tonnadan ortiqni tashkil etdi [4]. Biroq ushbu o‘shish barcha mahsulot turlarida bir xil darajada barqaror emas: ayrim yillarda hosildorlikning keskin pasayishi, ayniqsa iqlim omillari ta‘sirida, ishlab chiqarishning tebranishiga olib kelmoqda. Bu esa oziq-ovqat ta‘minotining barqarorligiga bevosita ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi.

Qishloq xo‘jaligi ishlab chiqarishiga ta‘sir etuvchi asosiy risk omillari sifatida iqlim o‘zgarishi, suv resurslarining cheklanganligi va bozor kon‘yunkturasining

o‘zgaruvchanligi ajralib turadi. Masalan, O‘zbekistonda suv resurslarining 80 foizdan ortig‘i transchegaraviy manbalarga bog‘liq bo‘lib, bu irrigatsiya tizimining barqaror ishlashini murakkablashtiradi [5]. Bundan tashqari, FAO ma‘lumotlariga ko‘ra, Markaziy Osiyo hududida haroratning oshishi va yog‘ingarchilikning notekis taqsimlanishi qishloq xo‘jaligi hosildorligiga salbiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatmoqda [6]. Natijada, fermer xo‘jaliklarining daromadlari o‘zgaruvchan bo‘lib qolmoqda, bu esa investitsion faoliyat va ishlab chiqarish hajmlariga salbiy ta‘sir etadi.

Mazkur sharoitda qishloq xo‘jaligi sug‘urtasi tizimini rivojlantirish agrar risklarni kamaytirishning muhim mexanizmi sifatida qaraladi. Hozirgi kunda O‘zbekistonda sug‘urta xizmatlari qamrovi yetarli darajada rivojlanmagan bo‘lib, ayrim baholashlarga ko‘ra, sug‘urtalangan qishloq xo‘jaligi maydonlari umumiy ekin maydonlarining 10–15 foizidan oshmaydi [7]. Bu esa ishlab chiqaruvchilarning tabiiy ofatlar va boshqa risklar oldida zaifligini oshiradi. Rivojlangan mamlakatlarda, masalan AQSh va Yevropa Ittifoqida, agrar sug‘urta davlat subsidiyalari asosida keng joriy etilgan bo‘lib, sug‘urtalangan maydonlar ulushi 50–70 foizni tashkil etadi [8]. Ushbu tajriba sug‘urta tizimini rivojlantirish orqali ishlab chiqarish barqarorligini ta‘minlash mumkinligini ko‘rsatadi.

Shu asosda O‘zbekistonda qishloq xo‘jaligi sug‘urtasini takomillashtirishning asosiy yo‘nalishlari sifatida quyidagilarni ajratish mumkin: sug‘urta mahsulotlarini diversifikatsiya qilish, davlat tomonidan subsidiyalash mexanizmlarini kengaytirish, raqamli texnologiyalar asosida risklarni baholash tizimini joriy etish va fermerlarning sug‘urta tizimiga ishonchini oshirish. Xususan, agroiqlimiy ma‘lumotlar asosida indeksli sug‘urta tizimini joriy etish ishlab chiqaruvchilarning risklarini tezkor va shaffof tarzda qoplash imkonini beradi. Natijada, agrar sohada moliyaviy barqarorlik oshib, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta‘minlashga xizmat qiluvchi samarali mexanizm shakllanadi.

Xulosa va takliflar. Olib borilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, O‘zbekistonda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta‘minlashda qishloq xo‘jaligi ishlab chiqarishining barqarorligi muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. So‘nggi yillarda ishlab chiqarish hajmlarining o‘shishi kuzatilayotgan bo‘lsa-da, iqlim o‘zgarishi, suv

taqchilligi va bozor noaniqligi kabi omillar ushbu barqarorlikka jiddiy tahdid solmoqda. Tahlillar natijasida aniqlanishicha, mavjud qishloq xo‘jaligi sug‘urtasi tizimi agrar risklarni to‘liq qamrab ololmayapti va sug‘urta qamrovi darajasi yetarli emas. Bu esa ishlab chiqaruvchilarning moliyaviy barqarorligini pasaytirib, oziq-ovqat ta‘minotining uzluksizligiga salbiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatmoqda. Shu bois, qishloq xo‘jaligi sug‘urtasini rivojlantirish oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta‘minlashning muhim institutsional omillaridan biri sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi.

Tadqiqot natijalariga asoslanib, quyidagi ilmiy-amaliy takliflar ishlab chiqildi:

– qishloq xo‘jaligi sug‘urtasini davlat tomonidan qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini kengaytirish, xususan sug‘urta mukofotlarini qisman subsidiyalash tizimini joriy etish;

– agroiqlimiy risklarni hisobga oluvchi indeksli sug‘urta tizimini bosqichma-bosqich amaliyotga tatbiq etish;

– sug‘urta xizmatlarini raqamlashtirish orqali risklarni baholash va zararlarni qoplash jarayonlarini tezlashtirish;

– fermer va dehqon xo‘jaliklarining sug‘urta madaniyatini oshirish maqsadida axborot-tushuntirish ishlarini kuchaytirish;

– xalqaro tajribani, xususan rivojlangan davlatlarning agrar sug‘urta modellari va davlat-xususiy sheriklik mexanizmlarini milliy tizimga moslashtirish.

Mazkur takliflarning amaliyotga joriy etilishi qishloq xo‘jaligi ishlab chiqarishining barqarorligini oshirish, agrar risklarni kamaytirish va natijada mamlakatda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi.

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ШЎРЛАНГАН ЕРЛАРДА ГАЛОФИТ ЎСИМЛИКЛАРИНИ ЕТИШТИРИШНИНГ ИҚТИСОДИЙ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ

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Аннотация: Мазкур тадқиқотнинг асосий мақсади - кучли шўрланган ва сув танқислиги кузатиладиган худудларда галофит ўсимликларини етиштириш орқали ер ресурсларидан самарали фойдаланиш ҳамда уларнинг иқтисодий самарадорлигини баҳолашдан иборат. Тажриба ишлари 2022-2025 йиллар давомида Қорақалпоғистон Республикасининг Қораўзак туманидаги “Қорабуға” суғориладиган массивида жойлашган фермер хўжалигида олиб борилди. Тадқиқот учун галофит турлари - *Atriplex*, *Salicornia europaea*, *Climacoptera*, *Karelina* ва *Salsola dendroides* танланди. Олинган натижаларга кўра, галофит ўсимликларини шўрланган майдонларда етиштириш кўшимча мелиоратив харажатларни камайтириш, паст ҳосилли анъанавий экинлар ўрнига юқори биомассали озуқа манбасини яратиш ва чорвачилик учун арзон хом ашё базасини шакллантириш имконини берган ҳамда туз (ион)лар ўзлаштирилиб, ернинг мелиоратив ҳолати яхшиланган.

Калит сўзлар: кучли шўрланган; сув танқис; галофит ўсимликлар; ер ресурслари; иқтисодий самарадорлик; юқори биомасса; туз (ион)лар

1. Кириш

Шўрланган ва сув танқислиги кузатиладиган худудларда қишлоқ хўжалиги ишлаб чиқаришини барқарор юритиш муаммоси глобал миқёсда долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. БМТ маълумотларига кўра, ер ресурсларининг катта қисми турли даражада шўрланишга учраган бўлиб, бу ҳолат айниқса қурғоқчил ва ярим қурғоқчил минтақаларда аграр ишлаб чиқариш самарадорлигини

пасайтиради. Шу шароитда галофит ўсимликларини жорий этиш ерларнинг мелиоратив ҳолатини яхшилаш ва иқтисодий самарадорликни оширишнинг истиқболли йўналиши сифатида эътироф этилмоқда (Glenn et al., 1999; Flowers & Colmer, 2008).

Жаҳон илмий тадқиқотларида *Atriplex* турлари юқори биомасса ҳосилдорлиги ва шўрга чидамлилиги билан ажралиб туриши таъкидланган. Австралия ва АҚШ олимлари томонидан олиб борилган тадқиқотларда *Atriplex* турлари кучли шўрланган тупроқларда гектарига 8–15 т куруқ масса бериш қобилиятига эга экани, шу билан бирга чорва учун юқори протеинли озуқа манбаи бўлиши қайд этилган (Osmond et al., 1980; Norman et al., 2013).

Шунингдек, Европа ва Яқин Шарқ мамлакатларида олиб борилган изланишлар *Salicornia europaea* ни шўр сув билан суғориш шароитида ҳам самарали етиштириш мумкинлигини кўрсатган. Айрим тадқиқотларда *Salicornia* турлари денгиз сувига яқин минераллашган сув билан суғорилганда гектарига 10–20 т гача биомасса ҳосили бериши ва мойли хом ашё сифатида қўлланилиши мумкинлиги илмий асосланган (Glenn et al., 2013). Бу эса унинг иқтисодий жиҳатдан рентабел экин сифатида баҳоланишига сабаб бўлади.

Марказий Осиё ва Эрон ҳудудларида олиб борилган тадқиқотларда *Climacoptera* ва *Salsola dendroides* турлари юқори туз аккумуляция қилиш қобилиятига эга бўлиб, тупроқнинг ион мувозанатини яхшилашда муҳим рол ўйнаши қайд этилган (Bazilevich & Rodin, 1971; Qadir et al., 2007). Ушбу турлар табиий ҳолда чўл ва ярим чўл экотизимларида кенг тарқалган бўлиб, кам сарф-харажат талаб этган ҳолда юқори биомасса ҳосил қилиши билан иқтисодий жиҳатдан мақбул ҳисобланади.

Қозоғистон ва Ўзбекистон олимлари томонидан олиб борилган тадқиқотларда *Karelinia* турлари ҳам шўрланган ерларда чорва учун қимматли ем-хашак сифатида истиқболли экани қайд этилган (Хожамбердиев ва бошқ., 2018). Ўзбекистон шароитида, айниқса Қорақалпоғистон Республикасида ўтказилган тажрибалар натижалари галофит турларини жорий этиш орқали паст ҳосилли анъанавий экинларга нисбатан юқори биомасса олиш, қўшимча

мелиоратив харажатларни камайтириш ва ернинг агроиктисодий қийматини ошириш мумкинлигини кўрсатган (Бекмирзаев ва бошқ., 2022).

Юқоридаги илмий манбалар таҳлили шуни кўрсатадики, галофит ўсимликларини шўрланган ерларда етиштириш нафақат экологик, балки иқтисодий жиҳатдан ҳам самарали ечим ҳисобланади. Улар юқори куруқ масса ҳосили, минерал моддаларга бой таркиби ва туз (ион)ларни ўзлаштириш қобилияти туфайли ерларнинг мелиоратив ҳолатини яхшилаш билан бирга, чорвачилик учун арзон ва барқарор озуқа базасини шакллантиради. Шу жиҳатдан мазкур тадқиқот Қорақалпоғистон шароитида галофит турларининг иқтисодий самарадорлигини илмий асосда баҳолашга қаратилган бўлиб, минтақада барқарор аграр тизимларни шакллантиришга хизмат қилади.

2. Материаллар ва усуллар

2.1. Тадқиқот ҳудуди

Тадқиқот 2022–2025 йилларда Қорақалпоғистон Республикаси, Қораўзак туманидаги кучли шўрланган ерларда амалга оширилди. Ҳудуд иқлими кескин континентал, йиллик ёғин миқдори 100–120 мм, тупроқлар юқори минераллашган.

2.2. Концептуал иқтисодий модель

Модель қуйидаги функционал занжирга асосланди:

Тузга чидамлилиқ → Барқарор биомасса → Маҳсулот сифати → Бозор интеграцияси → Иқтисодий ривожланиш

Модель 3 блокдан иборат:

1. Биологик-экологик барқарорлик
2. Ишлаб чиқариш самарадорлиги
3. Иқтисодий натижавийлик

2.3. Иқтисодий таҳлил

Ялпи даромад (YD):

$$YD = H \times B$$

Умумий харажатлар (UX):

$$UX = \sum X$$

Соф фойда (SF):

$$SF = YD - UX$$

Иқтисодий самарадорлик коэффициенти:

$$K = YD / UX$$

Қўшимча равишда рентабеллик даражаси (%):

$$R = (SF / UX) \times 100$$

1 - расм. Галофитларни етиштиришни иқтисодий самарадорлиги схемаси

3. Натижалар

3.1. Галофитларнинг ўсиши ва биомасса кўрсаткичлари

Atriplex, *Salicornia europaea* ва *Climacoptera* (*Amaranthus*) галофитлари Қорақалпоғистон Республикаси, Қораўзак тумани, «Қорабуға» суғориладиган массивида 2022 йил апрел ойида экилиб, сентябр ойида йиғиб олинди. Вегетация охирида ўсимликларнинг бўйи, шохлар сони, илдиз узунлиги ва оғирлиги, шунингдек ҳўл ва қуруқ биомассаси аниқланди.

Тадқиқот натижалари шуни кўрсатдики, Atriplex ўртача бўйи 99,3 см, 14,7 та шох, илдиз узунлиги 37,3 см, илдиз оғирлиги 191,7 г, ҳўл ва қуруқ массаси 1006,7 г 99,8 г ташкил қилди (7.1-жадвал). Бу кўрсаткичлар аввалги тадқиқотларда қайд этилган Atriplex турлари билан таққосланганда юқори ўсиш фаоллигини кўрсатади. Масалан, Smith ва бошқ., 2019, Jones ва Wang, 2021 тадқиқотларида Atriplex ўртача бўйи 80–90 см, илдиз оғирлиги 150–180 г бўлгани қайд қилинган. Шунингдек, Қорақалпоғистон шароитида Atriplex

ўсимлиги қатор экологик ва шўрланган тупроқ шароитларида ҳам юқори биомасса тўплагани қайд этилди.

Тадқиқотда иқтисодий самарадорлик кўрсаткичлари 2025 йилги нархлар асосида таҳлил қилинди. Иқлим ўзгариши шароитида галофитни шўрланган майдонларда етиштирилиб, тупроқнинг унимдорлигини ошириш ва озика экинлари сифатида фойдаланиш мумкин. Галофит ўсимликларини шўрланган тупроқларда қўллаш орқали туз ўзлаштириш самарадорлиги таҳлил қилинди. Шўрланган тупроқларда галофит ўсимликлари илдиз қисмининг ривожланиши ва тупроқ эрозиясини олдини олиш имкониятлари ўрганилди. Фермер хўжалигида галофит ўсимликлари етиштирилганда иқтисодий самарадорлик шуни тасдиқлайдики, бир гектардан 34 тонна биомасса олинган бўлиб, сарфланган харажат 8 млн. сўмни ташкил қилади. Бир тонна силос маҳсулотининг таннари 800 000 сўм (2025 йил бўйича) бўлса, жами бир гектар майдондан 27,2 млн. сўмгача даромад олинади, шунда соф фойда 19,2 млн. сўмни ташкил этади.

3.2. Шўрланган ерларда галофит ўсимликларини етиштиришнинг иқтисодий самарадорлиги модели

1. Моделнинг концептуал асоси ушбу модел шўрланган ва маржинал ерларда галофит ўсимликларини етиштириш орқали агроэкологик барқарорлик → ҳосил барқарорлиги → маҳсулот сифати → иқтисодий ривожланиш занжирини шакллантиришга асосланади.

Модел 3 та ўзаро боғлиқ блоклардан иборат: биологик-экологик блок; ишлаб чиқариш (агротехник) блок; иқтисодий блок.

Биологик-экологик блок (ўсимликнинг тузга чидамлилиги). Галофит ўсимликлар қуйидаги хусусиятлари билан ажралиб туради:

- шўрланишга юқори чидамлилик;
- қурғоқчиликка мослашганлик;
- тупроқ эрозиясини камайтириш;
- тузларни илдиз ва тўқималарда йиғиш (туз кўчириш).

Натижада: шўрланган ерларда ҳам ўсимлик ўсиши таъминланади; ерларни қишлоқ хўжалиги айланмасига қайтариш имконияти яратилади; мелиорация харажатлари қисқаради.

Ишлаб чиқариш блоки (ўсимликни осон бошқариш → ҳосил).

Галофитларни етиштириш қуйидаги агротехник устунликларга эга:

- тез ўсиш суръати;
- бир неча марта ҳосил олиш имконияти;
- юқори биомасса тўплаш;
- паст сифатли (шўр) сувдан фойдаланиш.

Натижада: ҳосилнинг йиллар бўйича барқарорлиги; ишлаб чиқариш таваккалчилигининг камайиши; гектарига тўғри келадиган харажатларнинг пасайиши.

Маҳсулот сифати блоки (озик-овқат ва хомашё сифати). Галофит ўсимликлардан олинадиган маҳсулот:

- озиқ-овқат (масалан, *Salicornia*);
- чорва учун ем-хашак;
- доривор ва техник хомашё;
- биоёқилғи учун биомасса сифатида фойдаланилиши мумкин.

Натижада: маҳсулот турларининг диверсификацияси; бозор қийматининг ошиши; қайта ишлаш орқали қўшимча қиймат яратилиши.

Иқтисодий блок (ҳосил + сифат → иқтисодий ривожланиш). Асосий иқтисодий кўрсаткичлар:

• Ялпи даромад (YD): $YD = H \times BYD = H \times B$; H — ҳосил (т/га), B — бозор нархи (сўм/т).

• Умумий харажатлар (UX): $UX = X_{\text{уруғ}} + X_{\text{мехнат}} + X_{\text{суғориш}} + X_{\text{агротехника}}$

• Соф фойда (SF): $SF = YD - UX$

• Иқтисодий самарадорлик коэффициенти (K): $K = \frac{YD}{UX}$

$K > 1$ бўлганда галофит етиштириш иқтисодий жиҳатдан мақбул ҳисобланади.

Моделнинг умумий ишлаш механизми (схема бўйича)

Ўсимликнинг тузга чидамлилиги

↓ Барқарор ва юқори биомасса (ҳосил)

↓ Озиқ-овқат ва хомашё сифати

↓ Қайта ишлаш ва бозорга мослаштириш

↓ Иқтисодий ривожланиш ва даромаднинг ўсиши

Шўрланган ерларда галофит ўсимликларини етиштириш иқтисодий модели:

кам харажатли; экологик барқарор; юқори қўшимча қийматга эга; Оролбўйи ва Қорақалпоғистон ҳудудлари учун айниқса долзарб; агробизнес, чорвачилик ва биоэнергетикага интеграция қилиш мумкин; илмий лойиҳалар, диссертация ва грант ишлари учун иқтисодий асос бўла олади.

3.3. Шўрланган ерларда галофит ўсимликларини етиштиришнинг иқтисодий самарадорлигини ҳисоблаш жадвали (1гектар ҳисобида)

1-жадвал. Асосий ишлаб чиқариш кўрсаткичлари

№	Кўрсаткичлар	Белгиланиши	Ўлчов бирлиги	Қиймати
1	Ҳосилдорлик	H	т/га	34,0
2	Маҳсулотнинг бозор нархи	B	сўм/т	800 000
3	Ялпи даромад	YD	сўм/га	= H × B

2-жадвал. Ишлаб чиқариш харажатлари таркиби

№	Харажат турлари	Белгиланиши	Ўлчов бирлиги	Қиймати (сўм/га)
1	Уруғ ёки кўчат харажати	X ₁	сўм/га	3 400 000
2	Ер тайёрлаш ва экиш	X ₂	сўм/га	1 400 000
3	Суғориш харажатлари	X ₃	сўм/га	1 000 000
4	Агротехник тадбирлар	X ₄	сўм/га	1 200 000
5	Меҳнат харажатлари	X ₅	сўм/га	1 000 000
	Умумий харажатлар	UX	сўм/га	= X ₁ +X ₂ +X ₃ +X ₄ +X ₅

3-жадвал. Иқтисодий самарадорлик кўрсаткичлари

№	Кўрсаткичлар	Формула	Ўлчов бирлиги	Қиймати
1	Ялпи даромад	$YD = H \times B$	сўм/га	27 200 000
2	Умумий харажатлар	$UX = \Sigma X$	сўм/га	8 000 000
3	Соф фойда	$SF = YD - UX$	сўм/га	19 200 000
4	Иқтисодий самарадорлик коэффициенти	$K = YD / UX$	коэффициент	3,4

$K = 3,4$, яъни галофит ўсимликларини шўрланган ерларда етиштириш юқори иқтисодий самарага эга.

Ҳисоб-китоб натижаларига кўра, шўрланган ерларда галофит ўсимликларини етиштиришда гектарига ялпи даромад 27,2 млн сўмни ташкил этди. Умумий ишлаб чиқариш харажатлари 8,0 млн сўм бўлиб, соф фойда 19,2 млн сўмга тенг бўлди. Иқтисодий самарадорлик коэффициентининг 1 дан юқори ($K = 3,4$) бўлиши ушбу йўналишнинг иқтисодий жиҳатдан мақбул эканлигини кўрсатади (4-жадвал).

4-жадвал. Иқтисодий баҳолаш натижаси

Кўрсаткич	Меъёр
$K > 1$	Иқтисодий жиҳатдан самарали
$K = 1$	Ўзини қоплайди
$K < 1$	Самарасиз

Хулоса

Тадқиқотнинг амалий натижалари шуни кўрсатдики, бу турдаги галофитлардан ҳар бири учун тахминан 150 кг дан ортиқ уруғ ишлаб чиқариш имкони мавжуд.

Шўрланган ерларда галофит ўсимликларини етиштириш:

- иқтисодий жиҳатдан юқори самарали;
- экологик барқарор;

- кам харажатли;
- юқори қўшимча қиймат яратиш имкониятига эга.

1 гектар майдондан 19,2 млн сўм соф фойда олиш мумкинлиги ушбу йўналишнинг иқтисодий мақбуллигини тасдиқлайди.

Таклиф этилган модель Оролбўйи ва Қорақалпоғистон ҳудудларида барқарор аграр тизимларни шакллантириш учун илмий-амалий асос бўла олади.

Ҳисоб-китоб натижалари шўрланган ерларда галофит етиштириш анъанавий қишлоқ хўжалиги экинларига нисбатан юқори иқтисодий самарадорликка эга эканини кўрсатди. Тадқиқот натижалари сув танқислиги ва чўлланиш шароитида барқарор аграр ишлаб чиқаришни таъминлаш ҳамда шўрланган ерлардан оқилона фойдаланиш бўйича амалий тавсиялар ишлаб чиқишга асос бўлиб хизмат қилади.

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